

Chapter 4

OVERCOMING THE CHALLENGES OF ACHIEVING TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE TOWARDS A SUSTAINABLE WORLD¹

COORDINATING LEAD AUTHORS:

Niki Frantzeskaki (Greece/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Sergio A. Lambertucci (Argentina), Edward R. Carr (United States of America).

LEAD AUTHORS:

Mialy Andriamahefazafy (Madagascar), Wiebren Johannes Boonstra (Sweden, Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Ruishan Chen (China), Jessica Dempsey (Canada), Edgar Espinoza-Cisneros (Costa Rica, United States of America/Costa Rica), Keisha Garcia (Trinidad and Tobago), Esmail Karamidehkordi (Iran), Kanako Morita (Japan), Valerie Nelson (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Diana Ojeda (Colombia), Tobias Plieninger (Germany), Andy Stirling (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Kanae Tokunaga (Japan/United States of America), Coleen Vogel (South Africa).

FELLOWS:

Fernanda Rojas Marchini (Chile), Asmita Sengupta (India).

CONTRIBUTING AUTHORS:

Clare Adams (Australia), Francisco Alpizar (Costa Rica/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Jeffrey Althouse (United

States of America/France), Nathan Bawaan (United States of America/Canada), Loretta Bellato (Australia), Josephine Chambers (United States of America/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Rosemary Collard (Canada), Janneke den Dekker-Arlain (Saint Lucia, Netherlands [Kingdom of the]/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Tova Gaster (United States of America/Canada), Renske Guddé (Netherlands [Kingdom of the]/Germany), Audrey Irvine-Broque (United States of America/Canada), Jianguo Liu (United States of America), Rainer M. Krug (Germany/Switzerland), Patience Mguni (Zimbabwe/Denmark), Julián Padró (Argentina/Argentina, Germany), Pablo Plaza (Argentina), Darren Ranco (United States of America), Laila Sandroni (Brazil), Shahryay Sarabi (Iran, Netherlands [Kingdom of the]/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Charlotte Stijnen (Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Isak Stoddard (Sweden, United States of America/Sweden), Romain Svartzman (France, Argentina/Italy), Alexandra Tsatsou (Greece), Esther Turnhout (Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Leonardo van den Berg (Netherlands [Kingdom of the], Brazil/Netherlands [Kingdom of the]), Sebastián Villasante (Argentina, Spain/Spain).

REVIEW EDITORS:

Jean Paul Metzger (France/Brazil), Margaret (Peggy) Smith (Canada).

TECHNICAL SUPPORT UNIT:

Laurence Périanin, Camille Guibal, Anouk Renaud.

1. Authors are listed with, in parentheses, their country or countries of citizenship, separated by a comma when they have more than one; and, following a slash, their country of affiliation, if different from that or those of their citizenship, or their organisation if they belong to an international organisation. The countries and organisations having nominated the experts are listed on the IPBES website (except for contributing authors who were not nominated).

THIS CHAPTER SHOULD BE CITED AS:

Frantzeskaki, N., Lambertucci, S., Carr, E., Dempsey, J., Karamidehkordi, E., Sengupta, A., Rojas Marchini, F., Vogel, C., Andriamahefazafy, M., Boonstra, W., Espinoza-Cisneros, E., Garcia, K., Morita, K., Nelson, V., Ojeda, D., Plieninger, T., Stirling, A., Tokunaga, K., Chen, R., Metzger, J.-P., Smith, P., and Guibal, C. (2024). Chapter 4: Overcoming the challenges of achieving transformative change towards a sustainable world. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., and Agrawal, A. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382246>

Table of Contents

Chapter 4

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	165
4.1 INTRODUCTION	168
4.2 FIVE OVERARCHING CHALLENGES TO TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE	170
4.2.1 Challenge #1: persistent relations of domination, particularly those that emerged and were propagated in colonial eras	170
4.2.2 Challenge #2: Economic and political inequalities	174
4.2.3 Challenge #3: Inadequate policies and unfit institutions	176
4.2.4 Challenge #4: Unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices	181
4.2.5 Challenge #5: Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems	186
4.3 OVERCOMING CHALLENGES: OPPORTUNITIES FOR TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE	189
4.4 KNOWLEDGE GAPS	192
4.5 CONCLUSION	192
REFERENCES	194

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 4.1 Relationship between the five main challenges to transformative change, the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and the direct drivers of global change	165
Figure 4.2 Relationship between challenges and barriers to transformative change	169
Figure 4.3 Prevailing world view and implications	173
Figure 4.4 The vicious cycle of political and economic inequalities and biodiversity loss	176
Figure 4.5 Reformist approaches that reinforce challenges to transformative change	178
Figure 4.6 Different types of institutional misfits that relate to the unaccountability of socio-ecological complexity and dynamics (social, temporal, functional, spatial) that these institutions are set to regulate and govern	180
Figure 4.7 Unsustainable production and consumption patterns	182
Figure 4.8 Global trends associated with production and consumption patterns	184
Figure 4.9 Challenges and barriers to transformative change	188
Figure 4.10 Case studies illustrating the principles for overcoming the five identified challenges	191

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4.1 Examples illustrating the challenges that diverse kinds of telecouplings pose to transformative change	185
---	-----

LIST OF BOXES

Box 4.1 Examples of reformist approaches that reinforce challenges to transformative change	178
--	-----

LIST OF SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Annex 4.1 Identifying challenges	
Annex 4.2 Linking challenges with the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment scoping report	
Annex 4.3 Case studies	
Annex 4.4 Additional information on challenges	

Chapter 4

OVERCOMING THE CHALLENGES OF ACHIEVING TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE TOWARDS A SUSTAINABLE WORLD

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Despite growing awareness of the human causes of biodiversity loss and environmental degradation, and their impact on human well-being, anthropogenic pressures on nature persist and intensify. This chapter identifies the main challenges that prevent the translation of evidence and concern about biodiversity loss into transformative changes (Figure 4.1). Some of these challenges exacerbate the difficulties inherent in transformative change. These challenges are reflected in what people think and feel (views), what people do (practices) and how society is organized

(structures), which correspond to the three interwoven dimensions of transformative change defined in Chapter 1.

1 Transformative change is impeded at multiple scales by views, structures and practices that are complex, power-laden, systemic, persistent and pervasive (well established) {4.1; 4.2}. Achieving transformative change involves addressing five salient and omnipresent challenges: 1) persistent relations of domination over people and nature, particularly those that emerged and were propagated in the colonial era {4.2.1}; 2) economic and political inequalities {4.2.2}; 3) long-standing policies and institutions that facilitate short-term benefits from

Figure 4.1 Relationship between the five main challenges to transformative change, the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and the direct drivers of global change.

By identifying these interrelated and pervasive challenges and understanding how they manifest across different contexts (barriers), the chapter demonstrates that each challenge also represents a starting point for catalyzing transformative change. Such a process involves new ways of overcoming barriers, including through active disruption of views, structures and practices that reinforce the challenges and harm biodiversity. This Figure builds on Figure SPM.2 of the IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2019).

overexploitation of biodiversity {4.2.3}; 4) unsustainable consumption and production patterns, reinforced by individual habits and conformity with social norms {4.2.4}; and 5) limited access to clean technologies that benefit biodiversity conservation and lack of coordination across knowledge and innovation systems that hinder the achievement of a sustainable world {4.2.5}. These challenges are interrelated and reinforce one another and the status quo of unsustainable views, structures and practices (**Annex 4.2**). Reconfiguring them is a critical step towards transformative change.

2 Persistent and pervasive relations of domination, especially those that emerged and were propagated in colonial eras, are blocking the transformation of the relationship between people and nature towards a just and sustainable future (*established but incomplete*) {4.2.1}.

While relations of domination have been a part of many societies, contemporary relations of domination that act as challenges to transformation emerged from the convergence of various prior relations and the extraction-focused character of colonialism. These relations of domination, which exist not only between countries and their peoples, but also within both former colonizing and formerly colonized places, reduce people and biodiversity to their instrumental values, facilitating current patterns of exploitation and extraction of knowledge, labour and resources. These relations are durable because they reproduce power imbalances and institutional structures that benefit the privileged and the powerful {4.2.1}. While the scientific classification and measurement of nature is a critical tool for understanding and managing the state and trends of the environment, there are also historical cases where it has been used to delegitimize Indigenous and local claims to or about the environment {4.2.1}. Such claims are further delegitimized through their association with groups often classified as less capable or deserving of the right to manage the environment {4.2.1}. The combination of “illegitimate” ways of knowing the world and “inferior” populations serves to reinforce and legitimize the expropriation of natural resources from such groups, who are assumed to be unable to manage these resources themselves. In this way, these relations of domination lie at the heart of unsustainable and unequal patterns of consumption and production {4.2.4}, while obscuring or delegitimizing potentially transformative views of how people live with nature {4.2.1}. The enduring legacies of domination manifest in current views, structures and practices and inhibit transformative change.

3 Economic and political inequalities are a challenge to transformative change because they contribute to maintaining the status quo (*well established*) {4.2.2}. Concentrations of wealth and power reinforce the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and are potent challenges to transformative change at various scales.

Marginal or vulnerable populations can view transformative change as introducing unacceptable, even existential, risks into their already precarious lives. Powerful actors, whether individuals or institutions, can resist transformations that might reduce their privileges {4.2.2}. The power dynamics in the international monetary and financial system, including inequalities within income-rich and income-poor countries, further entrench structural inequalities by impeding policy autonomy and preventing institutional change towards distributional equity {4.2.2; 4.2.3}. For example, countries that issue soft currencies experience vulnerabilities around external macroeconomic conditions, volatile international capital flows and foreign indebtedness, which in nature-resource dependent economies entrenches dependence on extractive exports to gain foreign currency for imports, to manage the value of their local currency and to repay foreign creditors {4.2.3}. There is substantial evidence from around the world that current access to resources and benefits derived from the ocean and impacts on the ocean, are characterized by a high concentration of capital shared between a few large fishing and aquaculture companies. For example, in the Indian Ocean, tuna species such as yellowfin, bigeye or Spanish mackerel continue to be overfished by industrial fleets incentivized by current framings of capitalism (**Figure 4.10, Annex 4.3**) {4.3.1}. Some countries with primary product export-based economies struggle to make incentives for conservation competitive with globalized market incentives to cultivate biodiversity-detracting cash crops. For example, high rents for non-native forest plantations make biodiversity-detracting afforestation more profitable for landowners than conserving native forests (**Annex 4.3, Figure 4.10**). Harmful subsidy lock-in is also a symptom of international capital mobility and political influence to entrench export-oriented natural resource markets (**Annex 4.3**) {4.3.2}. For example, loopholes in Chile’s National Forest Law align closely with policy proposals put forward by forestry industry lobbyists, who argue that landowners have the right to prioritize international markets over national and local conservation priorities to garner the most value from their property (**Figure 4.10, Annex 4.3**) {4.3.2}.

4 Institutions that do not account for nor fit the dynamics and magnitude of biodiversity-related problems limit the effectiveness of actions for transformative change (*well established*) {4.2.3}.

Challenges preventing transformative change include institutions that focus on extractivism and profit-maximization, coordinate poorly with other institutions, and lack accountability in the design and implementation of biodiversity policies {4.2.3}. Biodiversity policies are at times not informed by evidence lessening their accountability and reducing their coherence with other sectoral policies, including climate policy. To add to this weak accountability, neoliberal reforms can weaken institutions that can regulate or halt biodiversity-harming practices {4.2.3}. This is further reinforced by the real or potential reluctance of governments

to strengthen environmental policies for fear of capital flight {4.2.2; 4.2.3}. Spatial, temporal and social institutional misfits limit opportunities for dealing with biodiversity loss and hamper the effectiveness of biodiversity-focused policies and practices – where they exist. The spatial misfit, where administrative boundaries and the geographical areas of biodiversity and environmental degradation do not match, lead to disjointed decisions that fail to adequately deal with biodiversity loss {4.2.3}. For example, in the Yahara agricultural watershed in Wisconsin, United States of America, the analysis of 30 policies and four key services (freshwater supply, groundwater and surface water quality and flood regulation) pointed to spatial misfits between water policy implementation (the administrative boundaries) and the relevant water quality areas (the ecosystem boundaries). As a result, policy instruments in this case were not effectively targeting the main causes of water quality problems, particularly in agriculture-dominated regions, which has important consequences for the sustainability of key water resources in the region (**Figure 4.6; Annex 4.3**) {4.3.4}. Another example concerns marine fisheries governance. A problem of institutional fit remains in adopting integrated and coherent conservation and management measures within ecologically meaningful boundaries (or ecosystem-based units/functional units). Their sector-focused approach to management still poses an obstacle to managing threatened species. Species like sharks, for example, have seen drastic global decline despite the adoption of conservation measures almost 15 years ago within regional fisheries management organizations or the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (**Figure 4.10, Annex 4.3**) {4.3.1}.

5 Reformist responses to biodiversity loss can hinder transformative change by obscuring or even strengthening the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss (established but incomplete) {4.2.3}. Biodiversity offsets and environmental impact assessments have been used to legitimize extractive activities threatening biodiversity, while making more transformative options appear unnecessary {4.2.3}. As a reformist approach, biodiversity markets-based mechanisms have been linked to continued dispossession and violations of the rights of Indigenous Peoples, as in the case of the Cordillera Azul National Park (**Box 4.1**). Non-State market-driven governance, such as certification, has weak or ineffective outcomes and strengthens underlying drivers of inequality and biodiversity loss by strengthening corporate power over land use. Voluntary corporate or financial efforts to address biodiversity loss can also give the illusion of action with little to no evidence of widespread improvement (**Figure 4.5**) {4.2.3}.

6 The unchecked pursuit of economic growth, mainly measured by changes in per capita incomes and Gross Domestic Product, drives unsustainable production and consumption. Unquestioned habits

and norms around consumption and growth reinforce socioeconomic disparities and prevent transformative change by disrupting people-nature relationships (well established) {4.2.4}. Production and consumption systems, often influenced by lifestyle visions disconnected from nature, support market and policy arguments that encourage extant unsustainable patterns. These patterns manifest as a 66 per cent increase in global domestic material consumption in just two decades, an increase in demand for water by 600 per cent over the past 100 years and a 28-fold increase in energy consumption between 1800 and 2019 (**Figure 4.8**). Globally, the human Ecological Footprint exceeds the world's biocapacity, but the trends vary widely within and between regions (**Figure 4.8**). Consumption patterns are likely to remain a more significant driver of biodiversity loss than population growth in the coming years {4.2.4}. The societal emphasis on economic growth underpins modern-day consumerism. Strategies to maximize profits, such as planned obsolescence and premature aging of technologies, reinforce consumerism and its associated unsustainable production and consumption patterns {4.2.4; 4.2.5}. The long distances and complex supply chains between production and consumption (telecouplings) conceal impacts on biodiversity and perpetuate unsustainability {4.2.4}.

7 Ways of thinking, organizing and doing that harm biodiversity tend to persist and propagate, through habits and conformity with social norms, when individuals lack awareness of their impact on nature. Hence, transformative change occurs when people are empowered to break habits that harm them and biodiversity (well established) {4.2.4}. Many consumers are separated from the environmental impacts of their decisions by great distances, leaving them unaware of or with a limited understanding of the telecouplings and the impact of their actions on people and nature. In the absence of this experiential information, people conform with and confirm social practices and structures (including values, norms and institutions), making them stable and hence difficult to change {4.2.4} (**Annex 4.4**). Discontinuing actions that threaten biodiversity and creating the space for transformative actions to take hold is key to transformative change toward sustainability. The hold of habits and norms on social life is never absolute because people have the capacity and opportunities to consciously reflect upon the consequences of their own and others' actions {4.3}. However, individual change has to first go through a process of habitualization and then be copied and emulated by others before it can transform institutions and social structures {4.2.4} (**Annex 4.4**).

8 Lack of knowledge about and limited access to sustainability innovations prevent resource and energy-intensive producers and consumers from adopting technologies that support transformative

change for global sustainability (established but incomplete) {4.2.5}. Knowledge and innovation systems for biodiversity management are poorly integrated across and within public, private and non-governmental sectors. Limited attention to sustainability and biodiversity in curricula prevents shifts in views {4.2.5}. Structural barriers and path-dependent institutions impede shifts to sustainable technologies {4.2.5}. Many producers continue to rely on inefficient technologies that harm people and biodiversity because of the limited availability and high costs of cleaner technologies. Unsustainable technologies have mostly been maintained by an exclusive production and market-oriented perspective ignoring ecosystem health, sustainable livelihoods and important social factors such as justice, equity, poverty reduction and addressing the voice, needs and rights of local communities. Inadequate environmental institutions, regulatory and monitoring frameworks and lack of incentive systems for the shift to biodiversity safeguarding alternatives further constrain the adoption of these technologies {4.2.1; 4.2.2; 4.2.3; 4.2.5}.

9 The marginalization of Indigenous and local worldviews, knowledges and practices, and their lack of recognition, hinder transformative change (well established) {4.2.1; 4.2.3; 4.2.4; 4.2.5}. The value of different types of knowledge, embodied in local and Indigenous practices, is often excluded from discussions of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. Current scientific systems reflect relations of domination that privilege one way of knowing and living in the world over others. The reliance upon this one way of knowing the world dismisses alternative views and knowledge that might have transformative potential {4.2.1}. The dominant focus on market-led development and investment promotes the reduction of nature to a single economic value, thereby marginalizing other ways of valuing nature and biodiversity {4.2.1; 4.2.3}. When Indigenous views of nature clash with corporate interests and government policies and their associated ways of measuring and valuing nature, it can create barriers to the identification and implementation of pro-environmental behaviours and transformative ideas {4.2.3}. For example, in contexts where environmental impact assessments legitimize extractive development, the participation of Indigenous Peoples in these assessments often requires their adoption of language and assumptions that clash with and obscure their values and views. Indigenous Peoples and local communities find their views reduced to simplified narratives that devalue their knowledge and sometimes cast them as sources of degradation to be managed, rather than holders of valuable knowledge and perspectives with transformative potential {4.2.1; 4.2.4}. Finally, Indigenous and local knowledge is often treated as unsuitable for inclusion in knowledge transfer efforts. Instead, such knowledge is disrupted by the transfer of western scientific knowledge to Indigenous Peoples and local communities without recognition of their knowledge {4.2.5}.

10 Overcoming the challenges to transformative change demands active disruption and careful phase-out actions (well established) {4.3}. Challenges to transformative change offer strategic opportunities to catalyze actions that address multiple challenges. These opportunities can be realized through active disruption of powerful regimes of knowledge and practice that block change, empowering new views, structures and practices for transformative change, and carefully – to reduce undesired effects on people – phasing out industries and institutions that block transformative change {4.3}. Policy, programme and project design aimed at transforming biodiversity conservation and restoration involves strategies and context-specific actions that empower new views, structures and practices. There are many cases where this is already happening. For example, in the non-violent Chipko movement in India, villagers hugged trees to prevent them from being felled, thereby disrupting management practices that allowed for forest degradation, and inspired similar movements until India passed the Forest Conservation Act. Actions that empower new views, structures and practices can bring to light ideas for transformative change. The Len Ko Winkul Mapu initiative aims to halt biodiversity degradation in Patagonia. Started by the Lof Cayun Panicheo, a trans-Andean Mapuche community, the project has elaborated a conservation plan to strengthen its resistance to several industrial projects, including hydroelectric dams and salmon farming alongside unsustainable tourism and land privatization (Figure 4.10). Durable, effective phasing-out of institutions and industries that contribute to biodiversity losses can be facilitated by the co-creation and embodiment of transformative structures, views and practices. For example, to phase out incentives and structures that promoted deforestation, Brazil launched a collaboration between the environment ministry and the central bank to restrict access to agricultural credit in counties with the highest rates of deforestation (Figure 4.10).

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Growing evidence of anthropogenic environmental degradation has led to the establishment of internationally agreed-upon frameworks such as the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and, more recently, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework² for curbing biodiversity loss under the Convention on Biological Diversity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022; Ripple *et al.*, 2017, 2019; United Nations, 1972). Despite these efforts, extraction and pressure on biodiversity² continue to escalate sharply (Dirzo *et al.*, 2014; Steffen *et al.*, 2007; Venter *et al.*, 2016) endangering the stability of the biosphere (IPBES, 2019a; Rockström *et al.*, 2009; Steffen *et al.*, 2018). This situation is one aspect of a growing body of evidence for

2. See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>).

Figure 4.2 Relationship between challenges and barriers to transformative change.

Wheel of the interconnected challenges (different colours) and barriers (different letters) to transformative change. This figure illustrates the relationship between the five challenges, which are interrelated at the level of views, structures and practices. Their entangled character at this deep level explains how they reinforce one another, but also shows how each barrier within a challenge is an entry point to catalyze transformative change that can alter views, structures and practices and thus trigger wider changes across other challenges (Section 4.3).

the need to transform how people live with and in nature² to secure a sustainable future (IPBES, 2019b; Schipper *et al.*, 2022). The perpetuation of unsustainable behaviours and structures in the face of both evidence and a stated need for transformation focuses attention on what and who is preventing or impeding transformative change.²

A transformative change is a fundamental shift in views,² structures² and practices² that influence ways of thinking, doing, organizing, relating and knowing (**Chapter 1**) with the aim of achieving just and sustainable futures for people and nature (Feola, 2015; Frantzeskaki & de Haan, 2009; Loorbach *et al.*, 2017; Patterson *et al.*, 2017). Transformative change is hard to accomplish, mired in conflicts, and hard to govern or direct (Fischer-Kowalski *et al.*, 2019; Loorbach *et al.*, 2017; Patterson *et al.*, 2024). This chapter identifies challenges² that impede or prevent transformative change, either by exacerbating inherent difficulties or by introducing new and/or intentional obstacles to change. Such challenges are manifest across contexts in the form of barriers.² They embody what people think and feel (views and values²), what people do (practices) and how society is organized (structures).

Persistent challenges that impede efforts to bring about transformative change have a long history, are related to the underlying causes² of biodiversity loss, and are important to overcome for a just² and sustainable world. This chapter identifies the most important of these challenges to facilitate efforts to address them and examines available opportunities across contexts to initiate and accelerate transformative change (**Chapter 5**). The chapter also identifies barriers to every challenge, which are the ways challenges manifest across different contexts (**Figure 4.1 and Table 4.1**). This chapter identified five overarching challenges to transformative change (**Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2**) through a five-step process that included expert solicitation and evidence collected through different review and synthesis strategies (**Annex 4.1**, and the related data management reports³):

- Persistent relations of domination particularly those that emerged and were propagated in colonial eras;
- Economic and political inequalities;
- Inadequate policies and unfit institutions;

3. Review of literature on the persistent and pervasive relations of domination forged in colonial eras (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10250609>); Review of literature on power imbalances and inequalities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251325>); Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252250>); Review of literature on unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252304>); Review of literature on limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251408>).

- Unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices;
- Inaccessible clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems.

4.2 FIVE OVERARCHING CHALLENGES TO TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE

4.2.1 Challenge #1: persistent relations of domination, particularly those that emerged and were propagated in colonial eras

The relationship between people and biodiversity is characterized by a prevailing world view² marked by a propensity to adopt more rigidly categorical views of people, nature and the world than seen in the multiplicity of relational understandings and ethical concerns in diverse societies (Cortés-Capano *et al.*, 2022; IPBES, 2022a). This world view reflects forms of modernity shaped by colonialism² (Chakrabarty, 1993; Manning & Gills, 2011; Menon, 2002) which extend into the present (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2013; Wynter, 2003) as parts of a globalizing formation of modernity/coloniality² (Collins *et al.*, 2021; Quijano & Ennis, 2000).

This world view is a significant barrier to transformations toward biodiversity conservation, restoration² and long-term human well-being² (Collins *et al.*, 2021; Gunderson, 2023). The concept of coloniality refers to expansive patterns through which the appropriation and extraction of resources both fuels and reproduces the wealth, power² and privilege of specific groups (Quijano, 2007). While notions of modernity² contain relations of domination² that precede the colonial era, contemporary forms of these relations were shaped by coloniality, resulting in specific relations of domination, both of people over nature and people over other people. These relations pervade modern societies, idealizing and promoting control-oriented, mechanistic and reductionist ways of reasoning, generating knowledge, organizing structures and political representation (Stirling, 2019). They have become dominant while other ways of thinking and being have been excluded and marginalized² (Escobar, 2020; Hajer *et al.*, 2015; Jasanoff, 2005; Plumwood, 1993; Scoones *et al.*, 2015; Ulloa, 2017). Their predominance lies, in part, in their ability to link understandings of society and nature. For example, views of biodiversity as separate from humans and as such, to be controlled, managed and exploited, prioritize understanding nature as a commodity. This defines

appropriate use and management of nature in a manner that excludes customary, sustainable uses (B. Adams, 2008; B. Adams & Mulligan, 2012; W. Adams, 2017; Cock & Fig, 2000; Gasteyer & Butler Flora, 2000; IPBES, 2021; Landry *et al.*, 2018; Lightfoot *et al.*, 2013). These relations construct racial, gendered and anthropocentric hierarchies, with those deemed part of, or closer to, nature being devalued, sacrificial, vulnerable, or in need of protection, development, or change – namely women, Indigenous Peoples, elderly, people living with disabilities and racialized peoples (Merchant, 1980; Plumwood, 1993; Tong & Botts, 2019; Quijano, 2007). This cohesive linking of specific understandings of nature, control and value prevents alternatives from (re)gaining support (S. Arora *et al.*, 2020; Collins *et al.*, 2021).

There has been limited recognition of the ways in which these relations of domination act as barriers to transformative change (S. Arora *et al.*, 2020). Much of the literature that engages these relations of domination in the context of nature focuses on (1) their role as an underlying cause of environmental challenges, broadly speaking along with (2) conceptual arguments about their role as either reinforcing existing systems² and structures or otherwise serving as a barrier to transformation. However, a small but growing body of literature provides empirical, case-based evidence for how one or more dimensions of these relations of domination act as barriers to transformations in human relationships with nature and biodiversity.² This literature, discussed below, makes the connection between relations of domination and barriers to transformation implicitly, in the context of specific cases that are aimed at illustrating other points about human-environment relationships.

This chapter organizes the empirical connections between relations of domination and barriers to transformative change into seven dimensions: (1) categorizing nature and people; (2) stratifying and separating different groups in a way that promotes subordination; (3) reducing people and ecologies to singular, often standardized dimensions that lend themselves to management; (4) quantifying and aggregating values of nature; (5) technocratic approaches to conservation and other relationships with biodiversity; (6) justifying the appropriation and extraction of resources for accumulation; (7) concentrating and accumulating resources on behalf of the most privileged interests (Collins *et al.*, 2021) (**Figure 4.3**).

Questions of land use and value highlight how forms of categorization associated with prevailing relations of domination become barriers to transformative change, particularly when such categories reinforce State legitimacy in the face of contestation from civil society actors² (Bluwstein & Lund, 2018; M. Fletcher *et al.*, 2021; Igba & Liaga, 2021; Kashwan *et al.*, 2021; Mei-Singh, 2016; Romero-Toledo, 2023; Witter & Satterfield, 2019; Ybarra,

2012). This is apparent in many disputes over land tenure, where Indigenous and communal land tenure systems (Asher & Ojeda, 2009; Bryant, 2002; Domínguez & Luoma, 2020; Enters & Anderson, 1999; Hendlin, 2014; Hopwood, 2022), Indigenous and local practices (Dressler & Roth, 2011; Fairhead & Leach, 1995), and Indigenous and local knowledge² (Trisos *et al.*, 2021) are categorized as inefficient, unproductive, or otherwise less valuable and valid than western scientific framings. Another barrier to transformative change emerges in situations where Indigenous resource management systems are categorized separately from scientific land management and thus not integrated into environmental management and conservation planning (Dressler & Roth, 2011; Fairhead & Leach, 1995; Gandy, 2022; Goldman, 2003; P. J. S. Jones, 2009).

Claims about control over nature and biodiversity are reinforced by a stratification that ranks certain bodies as inferior by such categories as race, ethnicity, caste, age and gender. In different sites around the world, these claims about inferiority, for example, are reflected in claims about individual or group capacities to manage natural resources and justify their dispossession and displacement by dominant groups (Finney, 2014; Li, 2010; Lunstrum, 2018). Legal protections represent a crucial strategy for many Indigenous Peoples to advance their rights, centering on clarifying land titles and establishing private land regimes. However, the connection between classification and prevailing relations of domination often renders such strategies insufficient to transform either the limited access that local communities have to those aspects of nature upon which their ways of life depend or their systematic exclusion from the governance of that nature (Ballvé, 2013; German, 2022; Grajales, 2011; Harris, 1993; Hetherington, 2009; Ojeda, 2022; Rocheleau & Edmunds, 1997; Roy *et al.*, 2021; Sikor & Lund, 2009; Ybarra, 2009).

Prevailing relations of domination rest on and enable systems of simplification and quantification intended to make complex realities legible and manageable (Scott, 1998). Such simplification and quantification enable the measurement of biodiversity and its loss, and the development of priorities for action. However, the simplification and quantification aligned with this world view also reduce complex socio-ecologies into singular understandings of their value that tend to reinforce the underlying relations of domination (Bennett *et al.*, 2015; Collins *et al.*, 2021; Enters & Anderson, 1999; Gandy, 2022; Hoben, 1995; Massé & Lunstrum, 2016; Rocheleau & Edmunds, 1997; Rossiter, 2007). For example, the reduction of nature and biodiversity to quantifiable values not only serves as a means of understanding and managing biodiversity (Clay, 2016; Fairhead & Leach, 1995; Ishikawa & Soda, 2020; Kashwan *et al.*, 2021; Requena-i-Mora & Brockington, 2021), it also presents a

contrast to understandings grounded in Indigenous and local knowledge, justifying the exclusion of other systems of value and reinforcing existing regimes of management (Apostolopoulou *et al.*, 2012; Asher & Ojeda, 2009; Ginn, 2008; Kashwan *et al.*, 2021). In this way, the relations of domination that underpin contemporary systems of measurement and simplification present challenges to transformative change at an epistemological² level. These same systems of measurement and simplification also create institutional and political barriers to transformation (Prévost & Rivaud, 2019). For example, in contexts where the State's legitimacy is in question, the simplification of property rights and territory can become means by which the State reinforces its legitimacy and capacity without having to change environmental management practices (Apostolopoulou *et al.*, 2012; Asher & Ojeda, 2009; Asiyambi, 2016; Domínguez & Luoma, 2020; Dressler & Roth, 2011; Ginn, 2008; Goldman, 2003; Hopwood, 2022; MacKinnon, 2018; Rocheleau & Edmunds, 1997; Romero-Toledo, 2023; Schleicher *et al.*, 2017; Whatmore & Thorne, 1998).

Technocracy² is a form of governance² that is strongly reliant on technical experts, whose understandings are distinctively based on forms of scientific and technical knowledge that emphasize prevailing forms of categorization, simplification and measurement of nature and the classification and stratification of people or societies described above (Arias-Maldonado & Trachtenberg, 2019; Stirling, 2023; Stirling, 2019). Technocracy becomes a barrier to transformative change through this emphasis on various dimensions of the prevailing relations of domination that legitimize and enable specific kinds of control, management and extraction of biodiversity and nature to the exclusion of alternatives (Bryant, 2002; De Santo *et al.*, 2011; German *et al.*, 2006; Goldman, 2003). This is particularly true where technocratic framings of environmental management align with efforts to simplify the value of natural resources to forms of capital that can be circulated in markets (Dempsey & Suarez, 2016; Hansen, 2013; McAfee, 1999; Mei-Singh, 2016; Münster & Münster, 2012; Toly, 2004), a process that reinforces State constructions of territory, resources, ownership and legitimate knowledge.

The taking of resources, people's autonomy and even people's lives is a well-recognized, persistent and all-too-frequent outcome of biodiversity and environmental management that rests on these relations of domination (W. Adams & Hutton, 2007; Brockington & Igoe, 2006; Gasteyer & Butler Flora, 2000). There are many examples of technocratic approaches to environmental management being used to justify the appropriation and extraction of territory and resources in the name of their protection (Asiyambi, 2016; Clay, 2016; Domínguez & Luoma, 2020; Hansen, 2013; Hübschle, 2017; Massé & Lunstrum, 2016; Münster & Münster, 2012; Schleicher *et al.*, 2017;

Toly, 2004). Such appropriation, which draws upon the simplifications and categorizations described above, becomes a barrier to transformative change when it reinforces market-centric framings of value, while obscuring other sorts of relationships between people and nature that might validate the management strategies and practices of Indigenous Peoples and local communities² (Clay, 2016; IPBES, 2021). For example, reducing natural resources to market values facilitates the management of natural resources while enabling their extraction and appropriation by powerful actors² to their benefit (Apostolopoulou *et al.*, 2012; Asiyambi, 2016; Carmody & Taylor, 2016; Lunstrum, 2018; Mei-Singh, 2016; Romero-Toledo, 2023; Weldemichel, 2020). As noted above, this appropriation rests on the categorization and simplification of Indigenous Peoples and local communities to actors responsible for environmental degradation, which then justifies their dispossession and displacement (Finney, 2014; Li, 2010; Lunstrum, 2018), including the use of force and militarization to maintain certain extractive actions (Asiyambi, 2016; P. J. S. Jones, 2009; Mabele, 2017). The resulting forms of extraction become a barrier to transformative change when States seeking revenue and legitimacy involve the extraction of value from biodiversity for foreign revenue, for example through tourism (Weldemichel, 2020).

Taken together, the dimensions of currently prevailing relations of domination legitimize and perpetuate political-economic systems, including State socialism² (S. Arora & Stirling, 2023) and capitalist structures, that facilitate the concentration of control over resources to a small number of people. Such concentration becomes a barrier to transformative change when it draws on systems of classification and stratification that emerge from these relations of domination (Federici, 2004; Gilmore, 2002; Hall, 2016; Mies, 1986), to normalize and reproduce inequalities that enable large-scale wealth accumulation, justifying maldistributions of wealth, land and power and unequal conditions of labour (Alimonda, 2011; Federici, 2004; Gilmore, 2002; Gunderson, 2023; Svampa & Viale, 2014). For example, contemporary capitalist economic systems rely upon and (re)produce social hierarchies visible in patriarchy⁹ and racism⁹, reinforcing inequalities that drive ecological destruction and biodiversity loss. These environmental consequences, in turn, reproduce (intersectional) inequalities defined by racial (Bullard, 2001; Carruthers, 2008; Schroeder *et al.*, 2008) and gender categories (Federici, 2004; Mies, 1986; Nightingale, 2011; Ojeda, 2021; Plumwood, 1993; Shiva, 1988). Environmental injustices are reproduced due to capital accumulation and new expansions of political authority over natural resources², leading to convergences between affected groups based on labour (Sikor & Newell, 2014).

Figure 4.3 Prevailing world view and implications.

While the world is marked by diverse ways of knowing and living with nature, a prevailing world view that is based on persistent relations of domination forged in the colonial era obscures these alternatives and their transformative potential². Various dimensions of this world view include the stratification of different forms of knowledge that privileges quantifiable measures over other experiential understandings of the world to the simplification of biodiversity to singular, often instrumental functions or values. This prevailing world view promotes the exclusion of alternative understandings of nature and biodiversity from decision-making about management, the exploitation of people and nature in line with prevailing assumptions about value and appropriate use, and the concentration of control over resources in the hands of those whose knowledge and decision-making reinforce existing approaches to biodiversity and nature. This world view does not erase alternative world views, but it renders them illegitimate or unimportant in the context of addressing biodiversity.

4.2.2 Challenge #2: Economic and political inequalities

Economic and political inequalities can act as significant barriers to transformative change. One common result of high levels of inequality is the protection of the status quo, which in turn prevents shifts in the drivers² of biodiversity loss. For example, asset owners and wealthy individuals wield economic and political influence to block regulatory change against their interests. Power dynamics in the international monetary and financial systems, including inequalities within and between rich and poor countries and between public and private spheres, further entrench structural inequalities. Power dynamics impede policy² autonomy of States and limit the creation of institutions² to promote distributional equity² and transformative change (Alami *et al.*, 2023; Svartzman and Althouse 2020; Muchhala, 2022).

Current global economic and political inequalities are substantial, and fall along gendered, racialized and geographic lines (Chancel *et al.*, 2022; Stanley, 2022; United Nations Women, 2024; World Economic Forum, 2021). In 2021, the share of global wealth owned by the top 1 % of global population was 39.2 %, while the bottom 50 % owned 1.85 % of global wealth (Osakwe & Solleder, 2023). There are significant disparities between rich and poor regions along both income and wealth lines. For example, Europe and North America held 84 % of the world's wealth in per-capita terms in 2015, with the rest of the world holding only 16 % (Hickel, 2017). These wealth disparities have persisted through and since the colonial era; between-country inequality in 2020 was roughly at the same level as it was in 1900 (Chancel *et al.*, 2022). This persistent inequality² reflects well-understood neocolonial relations between former colonies and the countries that benefited from their primary production (A. G. Frank, 1967, 1979). There are also increasing inequalities between the public and private spheres, with the former shrinking, and the latter expanding (Chancel *et al.*, 2022), which limits government fiscal capacities and policy choices, including for biodiversity (Chancel *et al.*, 2022). These economic inequalities and the policy choices both arise from longer colonial histories of uneven exchange (Piketty, 2014) and ecological debts (Hickel *et al.*, 2022) operating as barriers to transformative change at various scales²: from individual to institutional to global.

At the individual scale and at both wealth extremes, material inequality between people exacerbates the reluctance of the more powerful to support transformative change (Downey, 2015; F. Green & Healy, 2022; Kenner, 2019, 2019; Page *et al.*, 2013). Insecurity among those at the lower end of income and wealth limits their capacity to mobilize for transformative change out of fear that it will negatively affect employment and development (D. Arora & Rada, 2017;

Bardasi & Wodon, 2010; F. Green & Healy, 2022; Ward, 2013). Policy proposals that point to transformative change precipitate opposition when they are perceived as a threat, for example, in terms of job losses or increased living costs (F. Green & Healy, 2022). There is significant evidence of such dynamics. Many communities accept developments with negative environmental or health² impacts due to felt precarity (Bruno & Jepson, 2018; Ejdemo & Söderholm, 2011; Ward, 2013).

At the other end of the wealth extreme, a small minority of the beneficiaries of status quo distributions of wealth and power has the resources to resist transformative change (Wiedmann *et al.*, 2020). Affluent individuals have a financial interest in the status quo because they benefit as consumers, investors and capital owners from (among others) extractive activities driving biodiversity loss (Ceddia, 2020; Downey, 2015; Kenner, 2019; Wiedmann *et al.*, 2020). Concentrated corporate and financial power also challenge efforts to achieve transformative change. Corporate consolidation (e.g., mergers, acquisitions) has created what some scholars call “keystone actors”, equating the influence of transnational corporations over economic and environmental systems to the impact of keystone species (Folke *et al.*, 2019; Österblom *et al.*, 2015; Virdin *et al.*, 2021). Concentrated wealth facilitates the disproportionate representation of the interests of capital owners in policy formulation (Clapp & Purugganan, 2020; Lucas, 2021), for example through the capacity to lobby governments for policy outcomes that advance industry interests and avoid transformative changes that might limit the further concentration of wealth (Barbier, 2022; Clapp & Purugganan, 2020; Corson, 2010; Folke *et al.*, 2019; Kim & Milner, 2019; Knight *et al.*, 2017; Kröger, 2017; Lucas, 2021; Österblom *et al.*, 2015; Santos *et al.*, 2024; Virdin *et al.*, 2021).

When industry lobbying promotes deregulatory environmental policy outcomes it challenges transformative change (Edwards *et al.*, 2014; Lindenmayer & Laurance, 2012), including the deregulation of environmental impact assessments to downplay ecological and social impacts (Fearnside, 2002; G. Williams, 2017), the maintenance of harmful subsidies (Bernstein, 2002; Buchanan & Badham, 2020; Bulte *et al.*, 2007; Dempsey *et al.*, 2020; Folke *et al.*, 2019; Lucas, 2021; McCulloch, 2023; Österblom *et al.*, 2015; Spash & Aslaksen, 2015; Suttor-Sorel & Hercelin, 2020; Turnhout *et al.*, 2021; Virdin *et al.*, 2021), and the reduction of duties/taxes to consolidate profit and power and providing amnesties for environmental crimes (Meira-Neto & Neri, 2017). These efforts render the significant externalities of economic development on nature invisible (Dasgupta, 2021), allowing “keystone actors” to adopt the language of sustainability² without having to change (Folke *et al.*, 2019; Virdin *et al.*, 2021). For example, the combination of increasing “shareholder primacy” financial governance,

where decision-making prioritizes shareholder interests above all else (Lazonick & O'Sullivan, 2000; Samanta, 2019), combined with an increasing proportion of wealth and productive assets being held privately, drives investment decisions toward shareholder interests and profit rather than the public interest (Cordelli, 2020; Lazonick & Shin, 2019). This becomes a barrier to transformative change when such change is viewed as a threat to owners of capital, who are fearful of asset devaluation (Cory *et al.*, 2021; Downey, 2015; F. Green & Healy, 2022), leading asset managers to either ignore or explicitly oppose environmental, or social principles in their investing strategies (Reuters, 2022).

Increased public finance is recognized as necessary to achieve biodiversity goals and targets (Kedward *et al.*, 2023a, 2023b), but in 2022 public financing for nature-based solutions² (\$165 billion) was less than 10 per cent of public financing producing nature-negative impacts (an estimated \$1.7 trillion in 2022) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2023). Global public explicit subsidies to sectors directly driving nature's decline ranged within \$1.4 and \$3.3 trillion for 2022, depending on the source. Further, the current majority of biodiversity finance is generated in and used by the United States of America, Canada, Europe and China (OECD, 2020). To address public financing shortfalls, international institutions and agreements, including the Convention on Biological Diversity, have called for mobilizing flows of private capital to solve public problems, including blended finance approaches that use public and philanthropic funding to incentivize private investment (Gabor, 2020; United Nations Environment Programme, 2023). Yet, over the past two decades, the track record for private investment in biodiversity has been marginal (Dempsey & Suarez, 2016; Kedward *et al.*, 2023a; United Nations Environment Programme, 2023).

As key financial actors, central banks serve as barriers to transformative change because their mandates and de facto priorities and operations are increasingly geared to protect financial interests and wealth owners over community well-being and environmental health (August *et al.*, 2022; Tucker, 2018; Vallet, 2021; Woodruff, 2019). This narrow focus and the blunt monetary tools used to enforce it (e.g., interest rate policy), tend to entrench the status-quo (Gabor, 2021) and side-step opportunities to support socio-ecological well-being and transformative change. Central bank policies to ensure financial stability, such as bailouts and large-scale asset purchase programmes (e.g., quantitative easing), redistribute income and wealth towards the wealthiest groups (Lee, 2024; Moosa *et al.*, 2024) while both directly and indirectly supporting environmentally harmful activities (Bailey, 2023; Bunn *et al.*, 2014; Cojoianu *et al.*, 2020; Kedward *et al.*, 2021; Matikainen *et al.*, 2017). While some central banks are devoting increasing attention to whether and how to address climate change² and environmental degradation ("nature loss"), efforts are

overwhelmingly concentrated on attempting to assess and quantify risks to financial stability (Aguila & Wullweber, 2024b, 2024a; Christophers, 2024; Kedward *et al.*, 2023a; Oman *et al.*, 2024), which is not the same as acting to prevent environmental crises from intensifying (Gabor, 2020; Kedward *et al.*, 2023a; Oman *et al.*, 2024; Svartzman *et al.*, 2021; Svartzman & Althouse, 2022).

At the international scale, low income, particularly, lower-income countries, have fewer domestic resources to expend on transformative change actions and are also at a disadvantage in accessing needed capital. A recent United Nations Development Programme Biodiversity Finance Initiative survey of 22 countries (including many considered "megadiverse" such as Ecuador and Peru) found that budget limitations and State capacity posed primary barriers to achieving Aichi Biodiversity Targets (BIOFIN, 2021). These limited resources are rooted in a long history of resource transfer from poor countries to wealthy ones. Meanwhile, at the bottom of the hierarchy are countries that issue "soft" currencies. These currencies – predominantly emitted by low- and middle-income countries – are not accepted as a stable store of value, medium of exchange or unit of account for global transactions. As such, soft currency countries face high borrowing costs and a structural need for 'hard' currency to finance external payment commitments and engage in trade (Korinek, 2018). A soft currency leaves countries vulnerable to environmental and financial instability, privileges over-indebtedness in foreign currency and restricts their possibilities for tax collection (Alami, 2019; Alami *et al.*, 2023; Alves *et al.*, 2022). High levels of foreign currency denominated short-term debt, economic volatility and limited ability to collect taxes leaves these countries with less resources to invest in transformative change that would support biodiversity. Indeed, their position within the International Monetary Fund means they face greater pressure to continue biodiversity-harming activities to pay for these debts (Dempsey *et al.*, 2020). For example, countries with a soft currency are structurally dependent on hard currencies, placing them in direct competition to attract foreign investment and consumer demand from countries emitting such currencies (Korinek, 2018). This dependency causes them to prioritize short-term, export-led growth strategies. Such strategies reinforce their reliance on exporting products with low added value, such as agricultural commodities and the extraction and processing of natural resources (Vernengo, 2006). Furthermore, countries that issue soft currencies are particularly vulnerable to external macroeconomic conditions, volatile international capital flows, and excessive foreign indebtedness. These vulnerabilities further entrench their dependence on extractive exports as a means to maintain foreign currency inflows to pay for imports, manage the value of their local currency, and to repay foreign creditors (Althouse & Svartzman, 2022; Elliott *et al.*, 2014; Erten *et al.*, 2021; Korinek, 2018). As extractive activities

intensify in low-income countries, flows of ‘cheap’ resources and profits are then frequently repatriated to high-income regions (Alonso-Fernández & Regueiro-Ferreira, 2022; Torslöv *et al.*, 2023; Wright & Zucman, 2018). In this way, the international monetary and financial system constrains the development capacities of low-income countries by concentrating environmentally harmful activities within their borders and limiting their capacity to fund new projects that would support transformative changes (De Paula *et al.*, 2017; Murau & Klooster, 2022; Stubbs *et al.*, 2023). In sum, the international monetary and financial system tends to reinforce structural inequalities within and among countries, sustaining drivers of environmental degradation and constraining, in particular, lower-income countries’ policy autonomy². Political economy and economic and financial institutions need to transform urgently, including prioritizing collective (public) over individual (private) interests, long-term interests over short-term and human-in-nature connections over anthropocentrism².

4.2.3 Challenge #3: Inadequate policies and unfit institutions

The combination of inadequate environmental and biodiversity policies and unfit institutions can severely limit transformative change (Frantzeskaki *et al.*, 2016; Young, 2008). The barriers to transformative change outlined in this section include: a) the lack of accountability in biodiversity policies, b) the neoliberal (re)structuring of state policies (including liberalization and austerity), c) the reformist responses to biodiversity loss² that create a fallacy of action while legitimizing underlying drivers of biodiversity loss, and d) institutional misfits² that create oversights for dealing with biodiversity loss and, as a result, limit the effectiveness of biodiversity-focused policies.

Biodiversity policies, often viewed as levers for transformative change, become challenges when they lack accountability. This problem has several sources.

Figure 4.4 The vicious cycle of political and economic inequalities and biodiversity loss.

Capital flows from extractive activities fuel economic inequality, where the influence of economic powerful actors and interests in policy formulation result in weakening biodiversity regulation that allows for biodiversity harming structures and industries to maintain their activities.

First, policy effectiveness is difficult to measure (Jokinen *et al.*, 2018). Many policy instruments² lack accountability because of the imprecise definition of targeted practices and the lack of responsible actors to perform systematic assessment and monitoring (Esgalhado & Guimaraes, 2020; Newig *et al.*, 2016). Second, policies across sectors may also conflict with each other. For example, those related to biodiversity protection generally benefit climate action, but the reverse is not always true (Pörtner, Scholes, *et al.*, 2021; Shin *et al.*, 2022). Third, there are limited tools to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of policy instruments for the achievement of biodiversity goals and targets across sectors that account for the complexity of socio-ecological systems² (Perino *et al.*, 2022). Fourth, interest groups interpret and employ policy arguments differently (Jokinen *et al.*, 2018). Biodiversity policies should be rooted in evidence. However, evidence, including scientific evidence, is at times ignored in policymaking (C. Carroll *et al.*, 2017; Lemly & Skorupa, 2012; Rose *et al.*, 2020; Spierenburg, 2012; Wallington *et al.*, 2005). Moreover, connecting scientific evidence with the policy cycle stages can be challenging (Jokinen *et al.*, 2018), creating a barrier when translating global biodiversity targets to actionable, achievable national (and local) policies and agendas (Franks, 2021; I. Jones *et al.*, 2022; OECD, 2021; Terton *et al.*, 2022).

Transformative change for nature and biodiversity involves significant government action. However, many States have been slow to implement such changes (Hay, 1994; M'Gonigle & Takeda, 2013). Corruption is one factor impacting how environmental protection policies are enforced, resulting in weakening environmental policy enforcement and in blocking efforts to achieve transformative change (Robbins, 2000; Sundström, 2015). To maintain legitimacy, States are tasked with facilitating economic growth for supporting job creation and funding public services (Akbulut *et al.*, 2019; Chapron *et al.*, 2017; MacDuffee *et al.*, 2023). The State's role as a promoter of economic development often sets a 'glass ceiling' on State environmental action that is formalized through institutions (Hausknost, 2020; Wiedmann *et al.*, 2020). In many countries, for example, environmental policies are subject to regulatory review which assesses their alignment with economic growth, trade and investment goals (Tienhaara, 2018). Therefore, if environmental policies threaten economic growth, they are usually not pursued or followed through (M'Gonigle & Takeda, 2013; Wiedmann *et al.*, 2020), even in jurisdictions with significant formal environmental institutions and budgets dedicated to environmental management (Duit *et al.*, 2016; Hausknost, 2020).

Neoliberal (re)structuring of State policies, including liberalization and austerity, further constrains States' ability to advance transformative change (McCarthy & Prudham, 2004; Peck *et al.*, 2010). While neoliberal policies are

heterogeneously applied throughout the globe with a wide range of effects (Liverman & Vilas, 2006), the common trajectory has been governmental policy increasingly focused on market-led development and investment – a narrow set of market-oriented values – alongside a shift away from State-led to market-based approaches to achieve environmental outcomes (Cashore *et al.*, 2008; Dempsey *et al.*, 2016; Heynen *et al.*, 2007). Under conditions of increased capital mobility, policymakers and elected officials worry that investment will flow elsewhere if more stringent environmental policies are implemented, which may lead policymakers and elected officials not to implement those policies or even to relax environmental standards (Engel, 1997; Esty & Geradin, 1998; Neumayer, 2001). Importantly, whether or not businesses do relocate, policy makers reportedly perceive the threat of relocation or litigation and make decisions accordingly, creating a "regulatory chill", meaning that the State becomes less inclined to enact stronger laws and policies for fear of capital flight (Konisky, 2007; Tienhaara, 2018; Tienhaara *et al.*, 2022). Multilateral trade and investment agreements can also make it challenging for States to prioritize environmental health (McCarthy, 2004; Tienhaara *et al.*, 2022). Trade and investment liberalization and austerity have been and continue to be central policy planks of international financial institutions like the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, which enforce neoliberal conditions in exchange for debt restructuring for countries experiencing fiscal crises (**Section 4.2.2**). Some of these conditions pose significant barriers to the fiscal capacity of States to enact biodiversity protection policies and can encourage export-oriented resource extraction linked to biodiversity loss (De la Vega-Rivera & Merino-Pérez, 2021; Orozco-Ramirez *et al.*, 2017; Shandra *et al.*, 2010).

Reformist responses related to biodiversity that attempt to reduce impact while leaving underlying drivers intact can become barriers to transformative change by creating a fallacy of action while legitimizing and obscuring the underlying drivers of biodiversity loss (**Figure 4.5**). Inadequate, reformist policies may create the illusion of transformative action, such as with "greenwashing"² of corporate policies (Holt-Giménez, 2019; Moore, 2017; Nelson & Flint, 2019). Such approaches are not just weak, ineffective and distracting but also barriers to transformative change in at least three ways. They: 1) legitimize and obscure the underlying drivers of biodiversity loss (Li, 2015); 2) strengthen, entrench or expand the systems driving biodiversity loss (Lister, 2018; Nelson & Tallontire, 2014) in part by assimilating or absorbing people and places into these systems (Dokis, 2015); and 3) create the illusion of action on biodiversity loss while little changes materially in terms of overextraction and rates of biodiversity loss (Sikor *et al.*, 2013; Zu Ermgassen *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 4.5 Reformist approaches that reinforce challenges to transformative change.

Reformist approaches² that reinforce challenges to transformative change entrench and/or expand biodiversity harming practices and structures, create an illusion of action and delegitimize and obscure efforts to transform views, structures and practices to curb biodiversity loss.

Box 4.1 Examples of reformist approaches that reinforce challenges to transformative change.

Within the context of biodiversity, reformist responses² refer to interventions that work through existing systems to modify structures and practices, while leaving underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline intact (Acosta, 2013; Santika *et al.*, 2024). Examples of reformist approaches that challenge transformative change include:

- Responses that treat biodiversity loss as a technical problem (e.g., a lack of information, lack of institutions, or lack of markets) have been favoured in lieu of transformative changes to social, economic and political systems (Büscher, 2010; Chausson *et al.*, 2023; Davis & Robbins, 2018; Parris-Piper *et al.*, 2023).
- Biodiversity offsets² permit activities that put biodiversity at risk, making other policy options² appear unnecessary (Zu Ermgassen *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, available evidence counteracts claims about the effectiveness of biodiversity offsets (Moreno-Mateos *et al.*, 2015; Robertson, 2004).

Problems include a lack of methodologies for assessing compliance difficulties in achieving no-net-loss (Gutierrez *et al.*, 2021; Kujala *et al.*, 2022; Robertson, 2000; Zu Ermgassen *et al.*, 2019), and difficulties in estimating the baselines to support effectiveness of offsetting measures (Maron *et al.*, 2015). Additional problems include complexities in rebuilding ecosystems² through restoration initiatives (Moreno-Mateos *et al.*, 2015), and the application of “ecological equivalence” (IPCC, 2018; Pörtner, Scholes, *et al.*, 2021). The limitations could be worsened considering that, according to Sonter *et al.* (2020), there is not enough land on the planet that can be dedicated to compensation measures under the projected development rates. Finally, biodiversity market-based mechanisms have been linked to dispossession and violations of the rights of Indigenous Peoples, as the Bribri Indigenous leader Levi Sucre Romero argues (2022), and as the case of the Cordillera Azul National Park illustrates (Forest Peoples Programme, 2023).

Box 4 1

- Environmental impact assessment processes meant to regulate the impacts of extractive projects on biodiversity (particularly endangered species) have often had little impact on project approval, despite documented impacts on nominally protected species. Some scholars argue that environmental impact assessments legitimize extractive projects and that the participation of Indigenous Peoples in environmental impact assessments requires their conformity to and adoption of colonial norms, including language and governance (Dokis, 2015).
- Risk and disclosure reforms to calculate corporate exposure to losses from environmental change have failed in “materially reducing the flows of finance to unsustainable activities” (Kedward *et al.*, 2020). Instead, they have created a new problem concerning the lack of models to calculate this financial risk, delaying needed policy actions.

The risk-based approach is an effort to protect assets from devaluation, not to directly address environmental problems (Christophers, 2017; Irvine-Broque & Dempsey, 2023). Efforts to incorporate climate and nature risks into sovereign credit ratings is predicted to reduce creditworthiness the most in lower-income countries already facing challenges accessing capital (Agarwala *et al.*, 2022). Increased borrowing costs, in turn, creates challenges for investing in biodiversity and ecosystem conservation and climate mitigation and adaptation² and ecosystem conservation (Dempsey *et al.*, 2022; Dibley *et al.*, 2021).

“Non-State, market driven governance” has had weak or ineffective outcomes. These governance mechanisms have strengthened underlying drivers of inequality and biodiversity loss by advancing corporate power over land use.

Spatial, temporal and social institutional misfits limit opportunities for dealing with biodiversity loss and hamper the effectiveness of biodiversity-focused policies and practices. A considerable challenge is the effective management of social-ecological systems given the incongruences between institutional factors and ecosystem dynamics. Institutional arrangements – the set of norms, rules and decision-making procedures that seek to regulate human-environment processes – and governance schemes often do not match the spatial boundaries and/or the spatiotemporal functioning of the biophysical systems they are embedded in (Becker *et al.*, 2015; Bergsten *et al.*, 2014; Widmer *et al.*, 2019). Known as the problems of “institutional fit” (Cox, 2012; Duraipappah *et al.*, 2014; Folke *et al.*, 2007; Trembl *et al.*, 2015; Young, 2008), these can be of several types. Spatial misfits occur when jurisdictional and biophysical boundaries do not match (Moss, 2012; Newig *et al.*, 2016; Trembl *et al.*, 2015), leading to disjointed decisions among jurisdictional entities that do not correspond with the interconnected and interdependent character of social-ecological dynamics (e.g., upstream-downstream interdependencies in a watershed) (Clement *et al.*, 2016; Cumming *et al.*, 2006; Folke *et al.*, 2007; Grigg, 2016; Tiffany *et al.*, 2022; Widmer *et al.*, 2019). Spatial misfits may also arise when State policies prioritize State-level economic development objectives and short-term economic gains over the needs of local communities and long-term socio-ecological sustainability (Melnykovich *et al.*, 2018). Further, policies may not align with the local context if institutions are solely or almost exclusively crafted top-down (O’Rourke, 2019; Pittman, 2019), leading to unintended negative impacts on biodiversity as well as local opposition (Frederiksen *et al.*, 2017; O’Rourke, 2019).

Temporal misfits occur when there is a time gap between management decisions (e.g., electoral cycles) and ecological

dynamics, such as when institutions cannot cope in time with ecological effects or when structural measures cannot be implemented fast enough in response to – usually abrupt – environmental changes (e.g., institutional response to extreme events) (Beever *et al.*, 2019; Galaz *et al.*, 2008). Relatedly, biodiversity conservation typically involves long-term policy support, but this is hindered by the short-sighted and fluctuating nature of individual and public decisions (Steinberg, 2009). Underlying the temporal misfits are the path dependencies with changing jurisdictional boundaries, poor institutional diversity or lack of institutional actions that correct these mismatches (DeFries & Nagendra, 2017; Epstein *et al.*, 2015; Mader, 2020).

The “social fit” problem (Epstein *et al.*, 2015), can be an important impediment for transformative change in certain contexts. It includes mismatches between broad sociocultural views (worldviews, values, preferences, etc.) (Pascual *et al.*, 2023) and formal institutional culture² (Acton *et al.*, 2021; Lute & Carter, 2020) and may lead to challenges associated with delegitimization or distrust in institutions (Nana *et al.*, 2022; Wamsler, Mundaca, *et al.*, 2022; Wamsler, Osberg, *et al.*, 2022) and lack of compliance (Frederiksen *et al.*, 2017; Kalikoski *et al.*, 2002). For instance, environmental public works or ecosystem restoration policies that involve public funding may not materialize due to divided public views (Okada *et al.*, 2021; Sieber *et al.*, 2018; Tokunaga *et al.*, 2020). Achieving social fit can be challenging when social groups are heterogeneous with diverse and often conflicting interests, values and preferences (Brown, 2003; O’Rourke, 2019; Pahl-Wostl *et al.*, 2023; Wamsler & Raggars, 2018). The social fit problem underlies why individuals refrain from materializing pro-environmental practices when those are incongruent with the dominant institutional culture (Bosone *et al.*, 2022). For

instance, Indigenous views on ecosystem management may clash with economic policies that favour large-scale natural resource extraction in Indigenous territories. Moreover, addressing these mismatches may cause new problems of fit or exacerbate other existing ones (Galaz *et al.*, 2008).

For example, creating a river basin governance authority to match the physical boundaries of hydrological systems may lead to mismatches with political, institutional, economic or cultural factors that exert their influence beyond the watershed system (Moss, 2012; Widmer *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 4.6 Different types of institutional misfits that relate to the unaccountability of socio-ecological complexity and dynamics (social, temporal, functional (social-ecological), spatial) that these institutions are set to regulate and govern.

Common examples relate to institutional factors mismatching with social-ecological dynamics. In the Mekong River basin, for instance, broader institutional arrangements such as transboundary agreements fail to account for more nuanced, finer-scale social-ecological dynamics such as local subsistence fisheries as well as rice cultivation (Sneddon & Fox, 2006). This misfit is a key challenge for transformative change as the livelihood conditions of millions of people are affected by these broader governance arrangements that are disconnected from these local and vital social-ecological processes. In another example from the Yahara agricultural watershed in Wisconsin, United States of America, important mismatches were found between water policies and water-related ecosystem services (Qiu *et al.*, 2017). In this example, a total of 30 policies and four key services (freshwater supply, groundwater and surface water quality and flood regulation) were analyzed and spatial misfits were identified between water policy implementation and the relevant water quality areas.

4.2.4 Challenge #4: Unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices

Many of the ways in which people use natural resources, generate and dispose of waste, and move and settle result in unsustainable patterns of consumption and production that place growing pressure on the biosphere (Awasthi *et al.*, 2019; Benton *et al.*, 2021; Castano Garcia *et al.*, 2021; Jouffray *et al.*, 2020; Meyerson *et al.*, 2007; Persson *et al.*, 2022). For example, the world saw a 66 per cent rise in global domestic material consumption between 2000 and 2019, a 28-fold increment in energy expenditure between 1800 and 2019 and a 600 per cent surge in demand for water over the past 100 years (Boretti & Rosa, 2019; FAO, 2024; Liu, 2022; United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2022; WWF, 2020) (**Figure 4.7**). As much as 45% of the Earth's land surface is used for agriculture and only 13% of the ocean area remains pristine as claims to marine resources for food, materials and space have accelerated in the past half century (FAO, 2020; E. Jones *et al.*, 2019; Jouffray *et al.*, 2020; Ritchie & Roser, 2024; WWF, 2020). At the same time 30.2% of food is wasted at supply and domestic and/or retail levels (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023). Further, current cycles of production and consumption, from the extraction of raw material to manufacturing, sale, consumption and disposal often generate a large amount of hazardous chemicals and waste that affect terrestrial, aerial and aquatic ecosystems (Benton *et al.*, 2021; IPBES, 2019b; Orecchia & Zoppoli, 2007; Pietzsch *et al.*, 2017; Zuluaga *et al.*, 2021). For instance, food systems² consume 2.5 million tons of pesticide annually (Benton *et al.*, 2021; FAO, 2022b). Commodity life cycles also include the production and release of hazardous entities such as plastics, in many cases as microplastic, into the biosphere at levels that exceed safe planetary boundaries for novel entities (Persson *et al.*, 2022). Approximately 7 billion of the 9.2 billion tons of plastic produced between 1950 and 2017 ended up in landfills or were dumped, affecting people and wildlife (Al-Dailami *et al.*, 2022; Hemidat *et al.*, 2022; UNEP, 2023) (**Figure 4.7**). Overall, global consumption far exceeds the capacity of ecosystems to produce resources and absorb generated waste, thereby creating an ecological deficit (Global Footprint Network *et al.*, 2023).

The global urban area is projected to rise by 1.2 million square kilometers between 2000 and 2030 (Seto *et al.*, 2012) and the urban population is expected to grow by 2.5 billion people between 2018 and 2050 (Baynes & Musango, 2018; Seto *et al.*, 2012; Simkin *et al.*, 2022; United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2018) (**Figure 4.8**). This is expected to increase urban domestic material consumption by approximately 50 billion tons per year between 2010 and 2050 (Baynes & Musango, 2018) (**Figure 4.7**).

Several proximate factors deter transformative change towards sustainable practices. Planned obsolescence, i.e., to ensure that technologies become obsolete (dis- or malfunctioning) after a predetermined period (Satyro *et al.*, 2018), has increasingly become a strategy for profit maximization over the last century and has negatively affected the environment (Rivera & Lallmahomed, 2016) (**Section 4.2.5**). The lack of technical capabilities for managing and reducing solid waste and inadequate infrastructure for recycling and recovery of raw materials continue to generate waste and pollution in many regions (WWF, 2020). Similarly, the dearth of adequate regulations of chemicals (**Section 4.2.3**), coupled with poor knowledge about the health and environmental effects, prevent a shift away from their use (Blumenthal *et al.*, 2022; Diamond *et al.*, 2015; Kirchhübel & Fantke, 2019). Paucity of data, temporal and spatial variability in data resolution, and differences in data quality – especially in remote areas or those of civil unrest – also act as barriers to the understanding of the impact of human movement patterns on biodiversity and the formulation of appropriate solutions (A. Frank & Schäffler, 2019; J. Williams, 2013).

The highly intensive and deeply entrenched ways of doing associated with these consumption and production patterns represent significant barriers to transformative change, especially because these patterns are directly related to meeting basic human needs (e.g., food, fresh water and energy). Consumerism, amplified by unsustainable lifestyle visions²/imaginaries (**Chapter 2**), underlies market and policy arguments for protecting current unsustainable practices (Pocas Ribeiro, 2023; Toth & Szigeti, 2016). The societal emphasis on economic growth reinforces modern-day consumerism² (Otero *et al.*, 2020). Markets and consumer demand for resources further reinforce these unsustainable practices, while the lack of relevant regulations (**Section 4.2.3**) and social and economic vulnerabilities (**Section 4.2.2**) act as barriers to transformative change (Jacobsen *et al.*, 2022; Kibria *et al.*, 2023; Pietzsch *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, supply chains relying on biodiversity often face influence from large business conglomerates. These conglomerates have an interest in minimizing regulations and maintaining economic policies that offer incentives – either directly or indirectly – for engaging in practices harmful to the environment (e.g., use of fossil fuels) (Folke *et al.*, 2019; Galaz *et al.*, 2018; IPBES, 2019b; OECD, 2005), (**Sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3**). System lock-ins such as path dependencies, export orientation, compartmentalized and/or short-term thinking and concentration of power, to name a few, also impede transformative practices (Benton *et al.*, 2021; Frison, 2016), (**Sections 4.2.2, 4.2.3**).

Existing governance strategies are often not coordinated across agencies at local, national, regional and global scales, leading to situations where environmental policies

Figure 4.7 Unsustainable production and consumption patterns.

Unsustainable production and consumption patterns prevail across the world and the global ecological footprint exceeds the global biocapacity². These patterns vary widely across regions (A) (including across Africa, Asia-Pacific, Middle East/Central Asia, the 28 members of the European Union (EU-28), rest of Europe, North America, Central America/Caribbean and South America) and countries belonging to different income groups (B) (categories include Low, Lower-Middle, Upper-Middle and High income). Such disparities are reinforced and further complicated by telecouplings – both across land (C) and the oceans (D). Conformist practices,

Figure 4.7

rooted in individual habits and social norms underlie the persistence of these trends (E). Unless transformative change is brought about, the global ecological deficit will continue to increase at alarming rates. Note: Production, consumption and biocapacity vary widely between countries belonging to the same geographic and/or economic category and within each country – this has not been reflected in the figure. Data sources for (A) and (B): York University Ecological Footprint Initiative & Global Footprint Network (2023); (C) adapted from Hull & Liu (2018); (D) represents the marine telecoupling proportion, with reddish colours corresponding to higher telecouplings, adapted from (Liu, 2023); References for (E) in Section 4.2.4 (see also more details in Annex 4.3).

and those related to migration and infrastructure development are incongruent (Adaawen *et al.*, 2019; Geddes & Jordan, 2012) (also stemming from unfit institutions, Section 4.2.3). This tension between economic and biodiversity goals is exacerbated by the fact that decisions to move or relocate are underlain by several environmental, political, socio-economic and demographic factors and their interactions. Targeted actions to address all these dimensions are difficult to develop and implement (Black *et al.*, 2011; D. L. Carr, 2004; E. R. Carr, 2005; Cripps & Gardner, 2016; Meyerson *et al.*, 2007; J. Williams, 2013). For example, migrations from rural to urban areas ease proximate pressures on biodiversity in sending areas. However, they may also lead to changing lifestyles, generally characterized by increasing consumption, encouraging farmers to convert forests to croplands (Anderson *et al.*, 2013; Güneralp *et al.*, 2017; Rudel, 2013). The resulting increase in food demand in urban areas may drive agricultural extensification into forests (Anderson *et al.*, 2013). While urban areas in the global North have material consumption levels ten times those in the global South (Venditti, 2022), many regions undergoing rapid urbanization are in the global South and represent some of the most densely populated and biodiverse areas of the world (Cincotta *et al.*, 2000) (Figure 4.8). For example, by 2050, Africa is projected to account for 21 % of the global urban population and the largest extent of urban expansion in the vicinity of protected areas² (Güneralp & Seto, 2013; United Nations, 2014). Land speculation by urban residents leads to the loss or fragmentation of natural habitats near cities and towns and beyond (Cadieux & Taylor, 2013; Flintan, 2011). For example, the growing construction of “second homes”, to be used seasonally in areas characterized by natural beauty and landscape, is detrimental to biodiversity (Adamiak, 2016; Alipour *et al.*, 2017; Long & Hoogendoorn, 2014). Urbanization is associated with the construction and expansion of transportation networks that further fragment habitats (Güneralp *et al.*, 2017; WWF, 2020). For instance, urbanization in the outskirts of Bengaluru, India, has substantially reduced and fragmented forest habitats, disrupting migratory corridors of Asian elephants and leading to human-wildlife conflict (Venkataramana *et al.*, 2017). The failure to understand these complex interrelations impedes policy and spatial planning efforts for transformative change (Adger *et al.*, 2020).

Simplified narratives² blaming overpopulation for environmental challenges take attention away from actual

drivers of biodiversity loss and therefore hinder efforts to foster transformative change in the context of production, consumption, habits and practices (A. Green *et al.*, 2022; Hughes *et al.*, 2023; E. K. Merchant, 2022) (Figure 4.6). Resource extraction and use are not evenly distributed amongst and within nations (Sun *et al.*, 2022), (Section 4.2.2; Figure 4.7). The material footprint per capita of high-income countries is at least thirteen times higher than low-income nations, many of which are home to large populations (Rammelt *et al.*, 2022). For example, an average modern lifestyle in the United States of America requires less than or equal to 9.5 hectares of land for its sustenance compared to less than or equal to one hectare required by individuals in India or Africa (Green *et al.*, 2022; Lin *et al.*, 2018). While population growth rates are declining and moving towards stabilization in several regions of the world, unless these larger underlying structures of consumption are recognized and addressed, pressure on biodiversity and nature will persist and transformative change will continue to be elusive (Hughes *et al.*, 2023; J. Williams, 2013) (Figure 4.8).

Telecoupling becomes a barrier to transformative change when it produces metabolic rifts that disrupt natural cycles and separate people from nature. A metabolic rift occurs when telecoupling delinks the impacts of human decisions and practices from their immediate and local ecosystems. By separating people from the environmental consequences of their policies, institutions and actions (J. Coenen *et al.*, 2023), these rifts can support prevailing relations of domination (Sections 4.2.1, 4.2.2). They can also obscure the dependence of consumer practices on the appropriation of and control over goods and services in distant ecosystems. For example, commodity production in low-income countries is often driven by the demand for materials and food in high-income countries, while sizeable foreign direct investments are made by these high-income countries to outsource their biodiversity footprints to lower income nations (Santika *et al.*, 2024; Schwarzmueller & Kastner, 2022; Wouterse *et al.*, 2011) (Section 4.2.2). Bjelle *et al.* (2021) found that 10.2 per cent of the biodiversity footprint of high-income countries occurred in Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines and Papua New Guinea. Other examples of telecoupling include beef and soybean production in the Amazon and palm oil production in South East Asia for consumption in China, the United States of America and Europe (Delaroche *et al.*, 2023; Escobar, 2020; Munroe *et*

Figure 4.8 Global trends associated with production and consumption patterns.

Historical trends of global (A) biocapacity (per capita in global hectares), population (in millions of people) and ecological footprint (per capita) between 1961 and 2021 across income groups (data obtained from World Bank; York University Ecological Footprint Initiative & Global Footprint Network (2023)), (B) share of population living in urban areas (European Commission, Joint Research

Figure 4.8

Centre (JRC), 2023), freshwater use (IGB – processed by Our World in Data, 2017), plastic production (Geyer *et al.* & OECD, 2017) and direct primary energy consumption (Energy Institute & Smil, 2017) (see more details in Annex 4.3). Production, consumption and biocapacity vary widely between countries belonging to the same economic category and within each country and this has not been reflected in the figure. Trends vary widely between countries belonging to the same economic category and within each country, this has not been reflected in the figure.

Another barrier to transformative change in the context of unsustainable consumption and production are multiple social-ecological-economic telecouplings and metabolic rifts² (Foster, 1999; Liu *et al.*, 2019; Schneider & McMichael, 2010; SEI/JNCC, 2023). ‘Telecoupling’ is a phenomenon of social-ecological systems where unseen yet pervasive practices and structures in one location impact ecosystems, biodiversity and societies across great distances (L. Coenen *et al.*, 2012) (Figure 4.7). Telecouplings are found in a broad range of spheres, covering political, legal, technological, physical, socio-cultural, psychological, economic/financial and other aspects (Table 4.1) (Liu *et al.*, 2013; Seto *et al.*, 2012). Some of the most visible vehicles for telecoupling include trade, tourism, human migration, species dispersal, energy transfer, financial investment and transfer of knowledge, water, waste and technology² (Hull & Liu, 2018) (Figure 4.7).

Table 4.1 Examples illustrating the challenges that diverse kinds of telecouplings pose to transformative change.

Case example	Global furniture and timber trade	Commodity-driven phosphorus fertilizer use	Nature-based tourism	Global labour markets of smallholder farmers
Telecoupling type	Trade	Trade	Tourism	Human migration
Sending system	Congo Basin	Soybean production areas, Brazil	Areas sending international and domestic tourists	Cochabamba, Bolivia
Receiving system	China	China, European Union, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, Sweden	Qinghai (China)	United States of America, Argentina, Spain
Key effect on biodiversity and ecosystems	Forest-cover loss	Water eutrophication, hypoxia and algal blooms; loss of ecologically valuable habitats	Increased consumption of water, crop and livestock products; infrastructure development	Conservation of agrobiodiversity through remittances, diversified livelihoods and part-time farming
Key challenges to transformative change	Economic: United States of America demand for Chinese wood products	Socio-cultural: increase in per-capita resource use met by imports that obscure environmental consequences	Knowledge-related: limited understanding of complex interactions between tourism and sustainability	Legal: vulnerability to safety, health and political risks related to informal employment
References	Fuller <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Eliasson <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Chung <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Zimmerer <i>et al.</i> (2018)

al., 2019; Song *et al.*, 2021; Tasmim *et al.*, 2022; Többen *et al.*, 2018), as well as fish caught in West-African waters but consumed in Europe (Alder & Sumaila, 2004).

Telecouplings through trade may create economic incentives to increase consumption through efficiencies of scale and obscure environmental impacts because they occur in far-away places (Fuller *et al.*, 2019), (Table 4.1). For example, 26 per cent of deforestation impacts have been attributed to trade rather than domestic demand (Pendrell *et*

al., 2019), and an estimated 30 per cent of global species threats are due to international trade (Lenzen *et al.*, 2012). Such telecouplings can result in rebound effects², such as when efficiency improvements result not in lower but higher consumption rates. This is because lower production costs result in lower costs of consumption (e.g., an increase a product’s energy consumption efficiency leads to an increase in its use (Font Vivanco *et al.*, 2022; Maestre Andrés *et al.*, 2012; Mashhadi Rajabi, 2022). Telecouplings and their associated metabolic rifts produce political barriers

to change, as actors seek to maintain existing unequal power relations² (**Section 4.2.2**) regarding the benefits and burdens of biodiversity conservation (Schröter *et al.*, 2020), (**Table 4.1**). Finally, telecouplings present challenges to legal/regulatory avenues for transformative change when they cross different jurisdictions and legal systems that may disagree about the responsibility or liability of actors for harm (Zimmerer *et al.*, 2018), (**Table 4.1**). Understanding the ways in which telecouplings occur is an important leverage to chart transformative change for safeguarding biodiversity.

The unsustainable structures of production and consumption are marked by policy incongruencies and teleconnections that make full consequences difficult to perceive at the level of individual choices and decisions. It is important to realize how people's everyday practices are strongly habitual. These habits in and of themselves form another barrier to transformative change because they maintain and reinforce unsustainable patterns and structures of production and consumption (**Annex 4.4**). Habits remain underexplored in relation to transformative change and sustainability (Linder *et al.*, 2022). They are often only used to denote a certain type of routine and automatic behaviour (Longoria *et al.*, 2021) and not understood as a fundamental motivation and explanation for human social practices (Lizardo, 2021). Habits form and are learned within certain contexts and create a fit between human needs and the restrictions and opportunities of social and environmental conditions.

Habits often reinforce several of the other barriers identified in this chapter. For example, telecouplings and metabolic rifts appear to allow for the unlimited appropriation of resources, space, territories, labour and sinks elsewhere resulting in practices that have been called an “imperial mode of living” (Brand & Wissen, 2018) and “habits of capitalism”² (Wilhite, 2016), (**Section 4.2.1**). Habitual behaviours conform and confirm social practices (Shove *et al.*, 2015) and structures (including values, norms and institutions), making them stable and hence difficult to change (E. R. Carr, 2019). For example, an important institution that can both reinforce or transform habits is marketing (Ribeiro, 2023). Nonetheless, the hold of habits and institutions over social life is never absolute; otherwise, people would not have been able to change themselves and their societies (E. R. Carr & McCusker, 2009). However, breaking individual habits can only really transform ways of organizing and doing (structures and practices) when transformation is imitated and emulated by enough other people. Hence transformative change paradoxically also crucially depends on the habitualization of new social practices (E. R. Carr, 2020) (**Annex 4.4**).

4.2.5 Challenge #5: Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems

An overarching challenge for transformative change lies in the generation of knowledge and innovation systems². Limited access to technologies that can benefit biodiversity restoration and conservation and the lack of coordination within and between innovation systems can frustrate and stall transformative change. This challenge is manifested in five main barriers, consisting of: a) poor availability of or access to sustainable technologies, b) ineffective coordination of knowledge and innovation systems, c) inappropriate knowledge transfer, d) marginalization of Indigenous and local knowledge and e) unregulated emergent technologies (**Figure 4.9**).

The structural-strategic limitations (Bagherzadeh *et al.*, 2020) relating to poor availability of or limited access to sustainable technologies refer to various factors, including the traditional research, development and dissemination paradigm and approaches to technology and innovation (FAO, 2022a; Wu *et al.*, 2017). It also includes the resistance of industries to adopt lower impact technologies which might entail higher costs (Mehmood *et al.*, 2021), or policies promoting more trade and resource extraction (Campling & Havice, 2018) (reinforced by relations of domination forged in colonial eras, **Section 4.2.1** and economic inequalities, **Section 4.2.2**). Planned obsolescence and premature ageing of technologies, exacerbated by ‘rebound effects’, cause unsustainable production and use (Font Vivanco *et al.*, 2022; Mellal, 2020; Satyro *et al.*, 2018; Zallio & Berry, 2017). Moreover, efficiency gains from technological innovation are often annulled due to the decreasing costs of use (Alcott, 2005), so they do not automatically lead to a reduction in consumption (see **Section 4.2.4**).

Shifting to green or clean technologies is impeded by structural-strategic barriers posed by extractive technological systems, which are entrenched by path-dependent institutions (Hess & Sovacool, 2020; Kimura & Kinchy, 2019; Kinchy *et al.*, 2018) (**Section 4.2.3**). These structural patterns persist, not only through the expression of power dynamics and resistance to change from political institutions but also within science. Prevalent assumptions guide how science should relate to policy and society (Alexander, 2019; Andersson & Westholm, 2019; Berkhout, 2002; Dunkley *et al.*, 2018; Gustafsson & Hysing, 2023; Lahsen & Turnhout, 2021; Redvers *et al.*, 2023; Turnhout *et al.*, 2016) (**Section 4.2.1**) and which scholarly fields are considered in policymaking or for funding (Arora-Jonsson & Wahlström, 2023; Rayner, 2014; Stirling, 2019). There is a long history of science contributing to the exploitation of nature and supporting State governments, colonial rulers and large companies in their ambitions to

maximize the extraction of natural resources (Agrawal, 2005; Ghosh, 2021; Scott, 1998; Smith & O’Keefe, 1980).

Extractive technologies shape the way natural resources are accessed, produced and processed (Leclère *et al.*, 2020). These conventional approaches have largely ignored ecosystem health, sustainable livelihoods, and often exclude vulnerable and marginalized groups, including women, youth, landless individuals and Indigenous Peoples, from accessing technological advancements (FAO, 2022a; Karamidehkordi, 2007; Wu *et al.*, 2017) **(Section 4.2.1)**. The result of this situation is a set of barriers to the transformation of knowledge flows and systems that might facilitate transformative changes in the technologies people employ and in how they use them.

Poor availability and access to sustainable technological innovations that can replace unsustainable, conventional technologies can impede transformative change. Operational-procedural limitations on access to sustainable technology, primarily associated with managing, operationalizing and supporting sustainable innovations (Abhari & McGuckin, 2023; Durst, 2013; Ghasemi *et al.*, 2021; Greco *et al.*, 2022) constrain the adoption and embedding of clean technologies that can shift practices from harmful to biodiversity-friendly ones (Awanyo, 2007; Porto *et al.*, 2020; Rubino, 2000; Shwartz *et al.*, 2013). Companies, organizations and producers in low to middle income nations suffer from weak market institutions and professionals inadequately trained to operate or maintain these technologies (Abdildin *et al.*, 2021; Chan *et al.*, 2018; Kaliakparova *et al.*, 2020; Samari *et al.*, 2013). They fail to produce or adopt clean technologies due to lack of resources, weak leadership, non-comprehensive strategies, risk aversion and resistance to innovative processes towards sustainability (Abdildin *et al.*, 2021; Lippolis *et al.*, 2023; Milana & Ulrich, 2022; Müller *et al.*, 2018; Pappas *et al.*, 2018; Singh & Maheswaran, 2023; Wolf *et al.*, 2018). Inadequate environmental institutions, limited regulatory and monitoring frameworks **(Section 4.2.3)** and the lack of incentive systems to facilitate a shift to biodiversity safeguarding alternatives further constrain the adoption of these technologies (Abdildin *et al.*, 2021; Abhari & McGuckin, 2023; Henke *et al.*, 2020; Horváth & Szabó, 2019; Natalicchio *et al.*, 2017; Rahbar & Abdul Wahid, 2011; Singh & Maheswaran, 2023). Examples include those related to chemical inputs – including hazardous pesticides and fertilizers, agricultural intensification **(Section 4.2.4)**, intensive fossil-fuel practices in agriculture or more efficient vessels and equipment in fisheries (Lanz *et al.*, 2018; Pauly *et al.*, 2005; Rani *et al.*, 2021; Schütte *et al.*, 2017; Zhang, 2018).

Inadequate or ineffective coordination between public sector, private sector and non-governmental actors limits the transformative potential of transferred knowledge for

policy and practice (Chinseu *et al.*, 2022; Gurca *et al.*, 2021; Hempattarasuwan *et al.*, 2021; Joffre *et al.*, 2018; Karamidehkordi, 2013; Lippolis *et al.*, 2023; Natalicchio *et al.*, 2017; Sarkar (Paria) & Maji, 2022; Settre & Wheeler, 2017; Shtaltovna, 2016; Weber & Rohrer, 2012). The stakeholders in knowledge and innovation systems are diverse, having differing levels of expertise and readiness to adopt sustainable technologies that can benefit biodiversity (Abdildin *et al.*, 2021; Abhari & McGuckin, 2023; Grimaldi *et al.*, 2021; Han & Yang, 2022; Khan *et al.*, 2021; Kumar *et al.*, 2021; Malhotra *et al.*, 2017; Singh & Maheswaran, 2023; Torres de Oliveira *et al.*, 2022; von Briel & Recker, 2017). Knowledge transfers that do not connect stakeholders have been documented to limit the effective flow of information and knowledge between, for example, researchers and farming communities (Agbamu, 2000; Faborode & Ajayi, 2015; Fukugawa, 2019; German & Stroud, 2007; Kassem *et al.*, 2018; Pezeshki-Raad & Karamidehkordi, 2006; Ragasa, 2011; Rathore *et al.*, 2008; Shtaltovna, 2016) and among multiple stakeholders in the governance of an ecosystem (Creed *et al.*, 2017; Es’haghi & Karamidehkordi, 2023; Lynch *et al.*, 2016; Sarkar (Paria) & Maji, 2022; Yu *et al.*, 2018).

The poor access of decision-makers, change agents, practitioners and Indigenous Peoples and local communities to sustainable knowledge and innovations, driven by ineffective knowledge transfer, can create a lack of awareness of the negative impacts of detrimental activities on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people² (Böhm & Collen, 2015; Folke *et al.*, 2021; IPBES, 2019b; Raymond *et al.*, 2010; Sachs *et al.*, 2019). Even when coordination between knowledge actors exist, many organizations are concerned that open innovation approaches could expose them to risks by revealing sensitive information and leaking knowledge to outsiders, particularly commercial details relating to their intellectual capital (Alberti & Pizzurno, 2017; Camilleri *et al.*, 2023; Chaudhary *et al.*, 2022; Gomes *et al.*, 2021; Madanaguli *et al.*, 2023) and loss of competitive advantage (Cao & Song, 2016; Chaudhary *et al.*, 2022). This results in withholding knowledge and innovation and in constraining knowledge transfer that might have benefited biodiversity conservation and restoration.

Large inequities between disciplines and knowledge systems exist that limit the effectiveness of knowledge transfer **(Section 4.2.1)**. The lack of knowledge co-production² between academic disciplines results in an incomplete understanding of the barriers and opportunities for knowledge and innovation systems to be levers for transformative change (Arora-Jonsson & Wahlström, 2023; Rayner, 2014; Stirling, 2019). The paucity of funding for collaborative research, conventional approaches to knowledge exchange, science in-accessibility and traditional academic reward systems discourage interdisciplinary collaboration deterring knowledge exchange and transfer

Figure 4 9 **Challenges and barriers to transformative change.**

The challenges and related barriers to transformative change manifest in different ecosystems and different geographies. **(A)** In the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment case study database⁴, there is a total of 777 challenges identified across 391 case studies. The above percentages represent the mentioning and recognition of each of the challenges in the recorded 391 case studies. All five challenges are identified in the recorded case studies and there are 260 out of 777 responses that identify more than one challenge present in a case study of transformative change taking place. **(B)** Subsidies case study (supported by detailed material in **Annex 4.3**). **(C)** Fisheries case study (supported by detailed material in **Annex 4.3**).

within and between countries (Bensaude-Vincent, 2009; Cook *et al.*, 2012; Cvitanovic *et al.*, 2014, 2015; Fox *et al.*, 2006; Leviston & Walker, 2012; Raymond *et al.*, 2010; Shanley & López, 2009).

Limited or unequal knowledge transfer can prevent the use of effective tools that provide information about unresearched ecosystems or monitor activities affecting biodiversity (Chandra & Idrisova, 2011; Harden-Davies, 2021). The value of non-scientific knowledge, such as that found in local and Indigenous practices, for innovation and transformative change is often not recognized (Antonelli, 2023; Dei, 2000; Mellegård & Boonstra, 2020). Traditional practices and Indigenous and local knowledge are frequently disrupted and abandoned by western, scientific knowledge, such as in areas where industrial and scientific agricultural techniques predominate (Altieri, 2004; Makate, 2020). Within global biodiversity practice, knowledge and technology transfer² has been complex and varied, including hard technologies (such as resources, machinery and technologies) to soft technologies (training, strategy and know-hows), rendering its effectiveness difficult to evaluate (Böhm & Collen, 2015; Prip *et al.*, 2015). The lack of effective knowledge sharing, access to appropriate technologies and technology transfer for biodiversity can prevent the recognition, adoption and implementation of locally appropriate management tools (Harden-Davies, 2021; Miloslavich *et al.*, 2019). For example, knowledge exchange or technology transfer is widely promoted for biodiversity-friendly agriculture, even in local contexts where farmers might already have effective local knowledge and practices that benefit biodiversity restoration that are locally adapted and effective (Johns *et al.*, 2013; Winter, 1997).

The absence of regulations governing research and the development of emergent technologies also pose a significant barrier to transformative change. Gene editing is an emerging new technology with applications evolving faster than regulatory processes (Hurlbut, 2019; Jordan *et al.*, 2017; Kofler *et al.*, 2018; Monast, 2018) (also relating to unfit institutions, **Section 4.2.3**). As such, it serves as a prime example of how regulatory challenges around emergent technologies could impede both transformative progress and effective biodiversity governance. Gene editing involves rigorous risk assessments in real scenarios² (Agapito-Tenfen *et al.*, 2018; Gordon *et al.*, 2021; Pixley *et al.*, 2022). However, the diversity of technologies, applications, mechanisms and research contexts hinder a comprehensive evaluation of gene-editing risks and benefits, necessitating case-specific analysis as well as meta-analyses of impacts and risks (Eckerstorfer *et al.*, 2023; Friedrichs *et al.*, 2019). The advantages of modified organisms could be obscured by some potential collateral

effects that alter human health, ecosystems and food production, leading to negative societal, economic and cultural consequences (Jordan *et al.*, 2017).

Non-inclusive social engagement leads to a lack of input from communities and stakeholders, resulting in the absence of dialogue to incorporate diverse points of view (Baltimore *et al.*, 2015; Gordon *et al.*, 2021). There is thus a need for inclusive and transparent deliberations about this technology (Jasanoff & Hurlbut, 2018). Cultural barriers to adoption could arise if ethical considerations, religious principles and spiritual views of populations where these technologies are applied are overlooked (D. Carroll & Charo, 2015; de Graeff *et al.*, 2019; Monast, 2018). Gaps in gene-editing regulation lead to unclear policy guidance for their application (Monast, 2018; Pixley *et al.*, 2022). This results in potential challenges around managing environmental risks, intellectual property disputes and the potential of benefiting wealthy players (reinforcing existing economic inequalities, **Section 4.2.2**) while disadvantaging smallholders and alternative systems (Pixley *et al.*, 2022) related to gene-editing. This is where international frameworks like the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of benefits Arising from their Utilization become relevant, as they provide guidelines for equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources.

4.3 OVERCOMING CHALLENGES: OPPORTUNITIES FOR TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE

All actors have a role to play in overcoming the challenges that stand in the way of transformative change towards a sustainable world. These challenges are interrelated and cannot be overcome through approaches that focus on a single challenge. Instead, overcoming these challenges requires attention to transformative ways of thinking, doing, organizing, governing, relating and knowing in all contexts and across all scales (Loorbach *et al.*, 2017). For example, an effort to overcome institutional misfit involves action that will not only align that institution (to improve its fit to the socio-ecological and spatial context) (Challenge #3, **Section 4.2.3**), but also address other challenges, such as relations of domination that preserve institutions in their current forms (Challenge #1, **Section 4.2.1**) and the mis-coordination between knowledge systems in providing evidence to support institutional fitness (Challenge #5, **Section 4.2.5**). Overcoming the challenges to transformative change involves the following context-specific actions: active disruption², empowerment² of new

4. Case study database with transformative potential and pitfalls (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260233>).

transformative views, structures and practices, phasing out of institutions and/or industries, and co-creation² of views, structures and practices that are aligned with the principles of transformative change.

First, active disruption is essential to overcoming the challenges of achieving transformative change and breaking path dependencies associated with established powerful regimes (Berkhout, 2002). Disrupting pervasive patterns is a powerful approach to transformative change (Sharma, 2017). For example, biodiversity conservation programmes and policies can challenge the underlying drivers of biodiversity loss such as the separation of people and nature (Büscher & Fletcher, 2019; R. Fletcher & Büscher, 2020). This contributes to overcoming persistent and pervasive relations of domination that obstruct or limit transformative change in biodiversity conservation (**Section 4.2.1**).

Second, transforming biodiversity conservation and restoration involves empowering new views, structures and practices. New structures can be created through reconfiguration that aligns with or promotes biodiversity protection and restoration goals. Such strategies can foster capacities to reveal unsustainable and unjust practices and outcomes among a wide range of stakeholders, opening multiple challenges to existing institutions and creating a political space for transformation (Patterson *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, installing and/or supporting (new) curricula and pedagogical practices that promote knowledge for sustainability, biodiversity and climate change as well as for transformative change may be a way of empowering new structures, views and practices (Grobler & Dittrich, 2024; Leichenko *et al.*, 2022; Slater *et al.*, 2024). For example, practices and processes that engage Indigenous Peoples and local communities in a collaborative, just and equitable manner may create an institutional space for multiple ways of thinking, doing, organizing, relating and knowing. Such practices and process have been shown to reduce power asymmetries and overcome the categories and hierarchies that devalue Indigenous and local knowledges and marginalize other ways of relating to nature (Domínguez & Luoma, 2020; Eriksen, 2021; Gustafsson & Hysing, 2023; IPBES, 2023a, 2023b; Kohler & Brondizio, 2017; Rahut, Dil *et al.*, 2022; Wells & McShane, 2004).

Empowering new structures, views and practices takes views, structures and practices as entry points for transforming biodiversity conservation and restoration. New ways of thinking foster different approaches to relations of domination; new ways of organizing create institutional space for challenging institutional misfits (**Section 4.2.3**); new ways of doing address the unsustainable and unjust consumption practices of a wide range of stakeholders. For example, new ways of thinking, organizing and doing provide opportunities for transdisciplinary integration and collaboration across diverse knowledge systems² (e.g., Indigenous and local

knowledge) to ensure that local and expert knowledges are shared (Bush *et al.*, 2023; DeFries & Nagendra, 2017). It also presents opportunities for engaging Indigenous Peoples and local communities in a collaborative, just and equitable manner, reducing power asymmetries and overcoming the categories and hierarchies that devalue Indigenous knowledges and marginalize other ways of relating to nature (Domínguez & Luoma, 2020; Eriksen, 2021; Gustafsson & Hysing, 2023; IPBES, 2023a, 2023b; Kohler & Brondizio, 2017; Rahut, Dil *et al.*, 2022; Wells & McShane, 2004). Connected to this, empowering different ways of repairing and including diverse knowledges of Indigenous Peoples and local communities may be overcoming separation and exclusion of these communities in planning and policy (Mungekar *et al.*, 2023). This, in turn, may address the relations of domination that often relegate such diverse knowledge to the background of policy conversations. Third, overcoming challenges involves progressively and carefully phasing out unsustainable practices within and among institutions and industries that contribute directly to biodiversity and nature's decline. Abrupt and unplanned phase out of practices can have significant negative effects on many people, industries and sectors, as experienced through the First and Second Industrial Revolutions (Cody, 2000; Hanlon, 2020). To avoid or minimize negative impacts, transformative change to a just and sustainable world involves deliberate phase-out strategies (Caruso, 2018; Schlogl & Sumner, 2018; Schulte *et al.*, 2020) that consider the environmental/sustainability and social impacts (Cheng *et al.*, 2021; Mhlanga, 2022; Siekmann *et al.*, 2023). Deliberate strategies may address unequal power relations and concentrated wealth across multiple scales (**Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2**), as well as the views that support and legitimize the unsustainable practices of such institutions and industries, such as narratives of nature as a commodity, or narratives that restrict Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' rights to nature (Bellato *et al.*, 2023; Bush *et al.*, 2023; IPBES, 2019a; IRP, 2021).

For example, addressing the challenges of transformative change (**Section 4.2.3**) includes in practice phasing out deterministic approaches (i.e., blueprint thinking) in favor of more adaptive approaches (Bodin, 2017; Folke *et al.*, 2007; Olsson *et al.*, 2004), or context-sensitive approaches for crafting institutional regimes (Folke *et al.*, 2007; Meinzen-Dick, 2007). Such approaches challenge linear ways of thinking about biodiversity policy (challenging modernist assumptions at the heart of contemporary relations of domination, **Section 4.2.1**) and promote iterative learning processes with multi-actor collaboration to address problems of fit in certain social-ecological contexts (Bodin, 2017; Guerrero *et al.*, 2015; McGlynn *et al.*, 2023; UNEP, 2021). One vehicle for such work lies in education systems that enable and mobilize alternative worldviews and epistemological paradigms² as valid and appropriate ways of understanding and living in/with/as

nature (IPBES, 2022b; Ocholla, 2020; Redvers *et al.*, 2023; Wamsler *et al.*, 2023).

Common to all these approaches to overcoming the challenges of achieving transformative change is the co-creation of transformative view, structures and practices, which is a fourth way to overcome the challenges. Creativity and collaboration are pivotal to generating alternatives that are aligned with justice² and equity, pluralism and inclusion²,

respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships, and adaptive learning² and action (Chapter 1) (Andrews *et al.*, 2024; Jacobi *et al.*, 2022). This includes incentivizing collaborative learning, including the co-production of knowledge with Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Copete *et al.*, 2023; Deutsch *et al.*, 2023). It also involves building transformative capacities and leadership skills so that all actors can play a role in overcoming challenges and contributing to a just and sustainable world.

5. Case study database with transformative potential and pitfalls (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260233>).

4.4 KNOWLEDGE GAPS

The assessment of evidence for challenges to transformative change and how to overcome them identified several knowledge gaps. The literature that empirically demonstrates how the relations of domination that emerged and were propagated in colonial eras act as barriers to transformation (Challenge #1) is marked by a high degree of agreement but is relatively small and its geographic coverage is uneven. Much of this literature demonstrates how these relations of domination function as challenges to transformative change implicitly, as this specific question has not been a formal focus of research. There is a growing body of work that identifies the international financial and monetary system, as well as both public and private international and national financial institutions and the dynamics of capital investment, as a source of changes that lead to biodiversity loss. Much less attention is given to how these structures and institutions impede transformative change for nature and biodiversity (Challenge #2).

The literature on institutional misfits (Challenge #3) lacks focus on their direct and indirect drivers, the actors involved in reinforcing them and the ways to overcome them. For instance, there is scant research on how to manage mismatches to effectively foster transformative change in specific contexts and at various scales. Filling this gap will involve additional research into how to effectively measure the “fit” between institutions and ecological systems, as well as on how to improve fit in broader scale processes such as telecoupled systems (e.g., commodity flows in a globalized economy). Additionally, there is a disconnect between the grey literature on the evaluation of projects and initiatives with transformative potential and the academic literature on examining how these institutional solutions are organized, perceived and operate in conjunction with existing institutions. This creates a knowledge gap on evaluating the transformative impact of these policies/projects and initiatives building from scientific and tacit/local knowledges.

While there is a large body of literature assessing the impacts of human activities on biodiversity within a social-ecological systems framework, there is much less information on how human lives and livelihoods are affected positively or negatively by actions toward transformative change. How social, economic and political profiles of countries influence consumption and production patterns requires further examination for devising specific mechanisms for overcoming this major challenge to transformative change (Challenge #4). It is also not well understood how system lock-ins, telecouplings, rebound effects and habits drive the persistence of unsustainable practices concurrently. Further research is required to

assess the factors underlying urbanization and human migration patterns, how they interact with each other and how to prevent incongruencies between policies related to these issues. Finally, habits are often not understood as a fundamental motivation and explanation for human social practices, and so they remain underexplored in relation to transformative change and sustainability.

For emerging technologies like artificial intelligence and gene editing (Challenge #5), there is limited evidence on how they can benefit and challenge transformative change for safeguarding biodiversity. In addition, evidence-based policy and planning are not the norm, making it difficult to find corroboration for how scientific findings – stemming from inter- and transdisciplinary research collaborations – can impact regulatory governance and enable transformative change. While there have been increasing calls for the incorporation of Indigenous and local knowledge into policymaking, there has been relatively little research into what is required in global science-policy platforms to make such incorporation transformative in impact. Overall, transdisciplinary research is needed as a paradigm to guide and activate science, society and policy for transformative change (Barth *et al.*, 2023).

4.5 CONCLUSION

Despite the massive amount of evidence gathered over the previous half-century on the deleterious effects of humans on biodiversity, anthropogenic interventions continue unabatedly and threaten to destabilize the biosphere and threaten human civilization as a whole. The numerous studies and efforts that have identified and addressed the underlying drivers impacting the biosphere do not (directly) lead to the needed structures and practices progressing sustainability (IPBES, 2019a). To achieve the visions for a sustainable world (**Chapter 2**) and accelerate progress along the associated desired trajectories towards these visions (**Chapter 3**), it is essential to understand what impedes or drives transformative change.

Challenges to transformative change are significant, systemic, pervasive and power-laden. A key conclusion of this chapter is thus that overcoming the challenges, both at individual and societal levels, includes more than reformist approaches. Transformative change involves discontinuing views, structures and practices that conform to what threatens biodiversity and allowing for transformative actions to create alternative social conditions conducive to a thriving sustainable society on a healthy planet.

Each one of the challenges offers an entry point for transformative action. Thus, new ways of overcoming can inform the design of policies, projects or initiatives from

across sectors to progress transformative change. These involve carefully phasing-out and disrupting biodiversity harming views, structures and practices, empowerment of alternative configurations and co-creation of new ways of thinking, organizing, relating and knowing. The ways of overcoming offer a thinking basis for foregrounding pathways² and strategies for progressing transformative change (**Chapter 5**) that deals with the identified persistent challenges.

REFERENCES

- Abdildin, Y. G., Nurkenov, S. A., & Kerimray, A. (2021). Analysis of Green Technology Development in Kazakhstan. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 11(3). <https://www.econjournals.com/index.php/ijeep/article/view/10897>
- Abhari, K., & McGuckin, S. (2023). Limiting factors of open innovation organizations: A case of social product development and research agenda. *Technovation*, 119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2022.102526>
- Acosta, A. (2013). Extractivism and neoextractivism: Two sides of the same curse. *Beyond Development: Alternative Visions from Latin America*, 1, 61–86. https://www.academia.edu/download/41649774/BeyondDevelopment_complete.pdf#page=62
- Acton, L., Gruby, R. L., & Nakachi, 'Alohi. (2021). Does polycentricity fit? Linking social fit with polycentric governance in a large-scale marine protected area. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112613>
- Adaawen, S., Rademacher-Schulz, C., Schraven, B., & Segadlo, N. (2019). Drought, migration, and conflict in sub-Saharan Africa: What are the links and policy options? In *Current Directions in Water Scarcity Research* (Vol. 2, pp. 15–31). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814820-4.00002-X>
- Adamiak, C. (2016). Cottage sprawl: Spatial development of second homes in Bory Tucholskie, Poland. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 147, 96–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2015.11.003>
- Adams, B. (2008). *Green development: Environment and sustainability in a developing world* (Fourth). Routledge. <https://www.routledge.com/Green-Development-Environment-and-Sustainability-in-a-Developing-World/Adams/p/book/9780415820721>
- Adams, B., & Mulligan, M. (2012). *Decolonizing nature: Strategies for conservation in a post-colonial era*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781849770927>
- Adams, W. (2017). Geographies of conservation I: De-extinction and precision conservation. *Progress in Human Geography*, 41(4), 534–545. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132516646641>
- Adams, W., & Hutton, J. (2007). People, parks and poverty: Political ecology and biodiversity conservation. *Conservation and Society*, 5(2), 147–183. https://journals.lww.com/coas/fulltext/2007/05020/People_Parks_and_Poverty_Political_Ecology_and_1.aspx
- Adger, W. N., Crépin, A.-S., Folke, C., Ospina, D., Chapin, F. S., Segerson, K., Seto, K. C., Anderies, J. M., Barrett, S., Bennett, E. M., Daily, G., Elmqvist, T., Fischer, J., Kautsky, N., Levin, S. A., Shogren, J. F., Van Den Bergh, J., Walker, B., & Wilen, J. (2020). Urbanization, Migration, and Adaptation to Climate Change. *One Earth*, 3(4), 396–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.09.016>
- Agapito-Tenfen, S. Z., Okoli, A. S., Bernstein, M. J., Wikmark, O.-G., & Myhr, A. I. (2018). Revisiting Risk Governance of GM Plants: The Need to Consider New and Emerging Gene-Editing Techniques. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.01874>
- Agarwala, M., Burke, M., Klusak, P., Kraemer, M., & Volz, U. (2022). *Nature Loss in Sovereign Credit Ratings*. <https://www.naturefinance.net/making-change/sovereign-debt/nature-loss-in-sovereign-credit-ratings/>
- Agbamu, J. U. (2000). *Agricultural research-extension linkage systems: An international perspective*. (No. 106). Overseas Development Institute (ODI).
- Agrawal, A. (2005). Environmentality. *Current Anthropology*, 46(2), 161–190. <https://doi.org/10.1086/427122>
- Aguila, N., & Wullweber, J. (2024a). Greener and cheaper: Green monetary policy in the era of inflation and high interest rates. *Eurasian Economic Review*, 14(1), 39–60. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40822-024-00266-y>
- Aguila, N., & Wullweber, J. (2024b). Legitimising green monetary policies: Market liberalism, layered central banking, and the ECB's ongoing discursive shift from environmental risks to price stability. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 0(0), 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2024.2317969>
- Akbulut, B., Demaria, F., Gerber, J.-F., & Martínez-Alier, J. (2019). Who promotes sustainability? Five theses on the relationships between the degrowth and the environmental justice movements. *Ecological Economics*, 165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106418>
- Alami, I. (2019). *Money Power and Financial Capital in Emerging Markets: Facing the Liquidity Tsunami*. Routledge.
- Alami, I., Alves, C., Bonizzi, B., Kaltenbrunner, A., Koddenbrock, K., Kvangraven, I., & Powell, J. (2023). International financial subordination: A critical research agenda. *Review of International Political Economy*, 30(4), 1360–1386. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290.2022.2098359>
- Alberti, F. G., & Pizzurno, E. (2017). Oops, I did it again! Knowledge leaks in open innovation networks with start-ups. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 20(1), 50–79. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-11-2015-0116>
- Alcott, B. (2005). Jevons' paradox. *Ecological Economics*, 54(1), 9–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2005.03.020>
- Al-Dailami, A., Ahmad, I., Kamyab, H., Abdullah, N., Koji, I., Ashokkumar, V., & Zabara, B. (2022). Sustainable solid waste management in Yemen: Environmental, social aspects, and challenges. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-022-02871-w>
- Alder, J., & Sumaila, U. R. (2004). Western Africa: A Fish Basket of Europe Past and Present. *The Journal of Environment & Development*, 13(2), 156–178. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1070496504266092>
- Alexander. (2019). What social science must learn from the humanities. *Sociologia & Antropologia*, 9(1), 43–54. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2238-38752019v9i12>
- Alimonda, H. (Ed.). (2011). *La naturaleza colonizada: Ecología política y minería en América Latina* (1. ed). Ediciones CICCUS : CLACSO.
- Alipour, H., Olya, H. G. T., Hassanzadeh, B., & Rezapouraghdam, H. (2017). Second home tourism impact and governance: Evidence from the Caspian Sea region of Iran. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 136, 165–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2016.12.006>

- Alonso-Fernández, P., & Regueiro-Ferreira, R. M. (2022). Extractivism, ecologically unequal exchange and environmental impact in South America: A study using Material Flow Analysis (1990–2017). *Ecological Economics*, 194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107351>
- Althouse, J., & Svartzman, R. (2022). Bringing subordinated financialisation down to earth: The political ecology of finance-dominated capitalism. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, 46(4), 679–702. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cje/beac018>
- Altieri, M. A. (2004). Linking ecologists and traditional farmers in the search for sustainable agriculture. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 2(1), 35–42. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295\(2004\)002\[0035:LEATF\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295(2004)002[0035:LEATF]2.0.CO;2)
- Alves, F. M., Santos, R., & Penha-Lopes, G. (2022). Revisiting the Missing Link: An Ecological Theory of Money for a Regenerative Economy. *Sustainability*, 14(7), 4309. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14074309>
- Anderson, P., Okereke, C., Rudd, A., & Parnell, S. (2013). Regional Assessment of Africa. In *Urbanization, Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services: Challenges and Opportunities* (pp. 453–459). Dordrecht: Springer. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-94-007-7088-1_23
- Andersson, J., & Westholm, E. (2019). Closing the Future: Environmental Research and the Management of Conflicting Future Value Orders. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 44(2), 237–262. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243918791263>
- Andrews, L. M., Munaretto, S., Mees, H. L. P., & Driessen, P. P. J. (2024). Conceptualising boundary work activities to enhance credible, salient and legitimate knowledge in sustainability transdisciplinary research projects. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103722>
- Antonelli, A. (2023). Indigenous knowledge is key to sustainable food systems. *Nature*, 613(7943), 239–242. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00021-4>
- Apostolopoulou, E., Drakou, E. G., & Padiaditi, K. (2012). Participation in the management of Greek Natura 2000 sites: Evidence from a cross-level analysis. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 113, 308–318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.09.006>
- Arias-Maldonado, M., & Trachtenberg, Z. M. (Eds.). (2019). *Rethinking the environment for the anthropocene: Political theory and sionatural relations in the new geological epoch*. Routledge.
- Arora, D., & Rada, C. (2017). A Gendered Model of the Peasant Household: Time poverty and Farm Production in Rural Mozambique. *Feminist Economics*, 23(2), 93–119. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2016.1220676>
- Arora, S., & Stirling, A. (2023). Colonial modernity and sustainability transitions: A conceptualisation in six dimensions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2023.100733>
- Arora, S., Van Dyck, B., Sharma, D., & Stirling, A. (2020). Control, care, and conviviality in the politics of technology for sustainability. *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy*, 16(1), 247–262. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15487733.2020.1816687>
- Arora-Jonsson, S., & Wahlström, N. (2023). Unraveling the production of ignorance in climate policymaking: The imperative of a decolonial feminist intervention for transformation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103564>
- Asher, K., & Ojeda, D. (2009). Producing nature and making the state: Ordenamiento territorial in the Pacific lowlands of Colombia. *Geoforum*, 40(3), 292–302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2008.09.014>
- Asiyanbi, A. P. (2016). A political ecology of REDD+: Property rights, militarised protectionism, and carbonised exclusion in Cross River. *Geoforum*, 77, 146–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2016.10.016>
- August, M., Cohen, D., Danyluk, M., Kass, A., Ponder, C., & Rosenman, E. (2022). Reimagining geographies of public finance. *Progress in Human Geography*, 46(2), 527–548. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03091325211054963>
- Awanyo, L. (2007). A Janus-faced biodiversity change and the partiality of ecological knowledge in a world biodiversity hotspot in Ghana: Implications for biodiversity rehabilitation. *Geoforum*, 38(4), 739–751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2006.12.003>
- Awasthi, M. K., Zhao, J., Sundari, P. G., Kumar, S., Chen, H., Awasthi, S. K., Duan, Y., Liu, T., Pandey, A., & Zhang, Z. (2019). Sustainable Management of Solid Waste. *Sustainable Resource Recovery and Zero Waste Approaches*, 79–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-64200-4.00006-2>
- Bagherzadeh, M., Markovic, S., Cheng, J., & Vanhaverbeke, W. (2020). How Does Outside-In Open Innovation Influence Innovation Performance? Analyzing the Mediating Roles of Knowledge Sharing and Innovation Strategy. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 67(3), 740–753. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2018.2889538>
- Bailey, D. (2023). ‘Building back better’ or sustaining the unsustainable? The climate impacts of Bank of England QE in the Covid-19 pandemic. *British Politics*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41293-022-00223-w>
- Ballvé, T. (2013). Grassroots masquerades: Development, paramilitaries, and land laundering in Colombia. *Geoforum*, 50, 62–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2013.08.001>
- Baltimore, D., Berg, P., Botchan, M., Carroll, D., Charo, R. A., Church, G., Corn, J. E., Daley, G. Q., Doudna, J. A., Fenner, M., Greely, H. T., Jinek, M., Martin, G. S., Penhoet, E., Puck, J., Sternberg, S. H., Weissman, J. S., & Yamamoto, K. R. (2015). A prudent path forward for genomic engineering and germline gene modification. *Science*, 348(6230), 36–38. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aab1028>
- Barbier, E. B. (2022). The Policy Implications of the Dasgupta Review: Land Use Change and Biodiversity: Invited Paper for the Special Issue on “The Economics of Biodiversity: Building on the Dasgupta Review” in *Environmental and Resource Economics*. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 83(4), 911–935. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-022-00658-1>
- Bardasi, E., & Wodon, Q. (2010). Working Long Hours and Having No Choice: Time Poverty in Guinea. *Feminist Economics*, 16(3), 45–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2010.508574>
- Barth, M., Jiménez-Aceituno, A., Lam, D. P., Bürgener, L., & Lang, D. J. (2023). Transdisciplinary learning as a key leverage for sustainability transformations. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2023.101361>
- Baynes, T. M., & Musango, J. K. (2018). Estimating current and future global urban domestic material consumption. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(6). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aac391>

- Becker, G., Huitema, D., & Aerts, J. C. J. H. (2015). Prescriptions for adaptive comanagement: The case of flood management in the German Rhine basin. *Ecology and Society*, 20(3), art1. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-07562-200301>
- Beever, E. A., Simberloff, D., Crowley, S. L., Al-Chokhachy, R., Jackson, H. A., & Petersen, S. L. (2019). Social-ecological mismatches create conservation challenges in introduced species management. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 17(2), 117–125. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2000>
- Bellato, L., Frantzeskaki, N., tebrakunna country and, Lee, E., Cheer, J. M., & Peters, A. (2023). Transformative epistemologies for regenerative tourism: Towards a decolonial paradigm in science and practice? *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2023.2208310>
- Bennett, N. J., Govan, H., & Satterfield, T. (2015). Ocean grabbing. *Marine Policy*, 57, 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.03.026>.
- Bensaude-Vincent, B. (2009). A Historical Perspective on Science and Its “Others.” *Isis*, 100(2), 359–368. <https://doi.org/10.1086/599547>
- Benton, T., Bieg, C., Harwatt, H., Pudasaini, R., & Wellesley, L. (2021). *Food system impacts on biodiversity loss. Three levers for food system transformation in support of nature*. Chatham House. <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2021/02/food-system-impacts-biodiversity-loss>
- Bergsten, A., Galafassi, D., & Bodin, Ö. (2014). The problem of spatial fit in social-ecological systems: Detecting mismatches between ecological connectivity and land management in an urban region. *Ecology and Society*, 19(4), art6. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-06931-190406>
- Berkhout, F. (2002). Technological regimes, path dependency and the environment. *Global Environmental Change*, 12(1), 1–4. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780\(01\)00025-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780(01)00025-5)
- Bernstein, S. (2002). Liberal Environmentalism and Global Environmental Governance. *Global Environmental Politics*, 2(3), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1162/152638002320310509>
- BIOFIN. (2021). *Understanding mainstreaming as a finance solution: Survey results from 22 BIOFIN countries*. United Nations Development Project. <https://www.biofin.org/knowledge-product/understanding-mainstreaming-finance-solution-survey-results-22-biofin-countries>
- Bjelle, E. L., Kuipers, K., Verones, F., & Wood, R. (2021). Trends in national biodiversity footprints of land use. *Ecological Economics*, 185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107059>
- Black, R., Adger, W. N., Arnell, N. W., Dercon, S., Geddes, A., & Thomas, D. (2011). The effect of environmental change on human migration. *Global Environmental Change*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.10.001>
- Blumenthal, J., Diamond, M. L., Hoffmann, M., & Wang, Z. (2022). Time to break the “lock-in” impediments to chemicals management. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 56(7), 3863–3870. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c06615>
- Bluwstein, J., & Lund, J. F. (2018). Territoriality by Conservation in the Selous–Niassa Corridor in Tanzania. *World Development*, 101, 453–465. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2016.09.010>
- Bodin, Ö. (2017). Collaborative environmental governance: Achieving collective action in social-ecological systems. *Science*, 357(6352). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan1114>
- Böhm, M., & Collen, B. (2015). Toward equality of biodiversity knowledge through technology transfer: Biodiversity Technology Transfer. *Conservation Biology*, 29(5), 1290–1302. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12529>
- Boretti, A., & Rosa, L. (2019). Reassessing the projections of the World Water Development Report. *Npj Clean Water*, 2(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41545-019-0039-9>
- Bosone, L., Chaurand, N., & Chevrier, M. (2022). To change or not to change? Perceived psychological barriers to individuals’ behavioural changes in favour of biodiversity conservation. *Ecosystems and People*, 18(1), 315–328. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2022.2071343>
- Brand, U., & Wissen, M. (2018). *The Limits to Capitalist Nature: Theorizing and Overcoming the Imperial Mode of Living*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Brockington, D., & Igwe, J. (2006). Eviction for conservation: A global overview. *Conservation and Society*, 4(3), 424–470. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26396619>
- Brown, B. L. (2003). Spatial heterogeneity reduces temporal variability in stream insect communities. *Ecology Letters*, 6(4), 316–325. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1461-0248.2003.00431.x>
- Bruno, T., & Jepson, W. (2018). Marketisation of environmental justice: U.S. EPA environmental justice showcase communities project in Port Arthur, Texas. *Local Environment*, 23(3), 276–292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2017.1415873>
- Bryant, R. L. (2002). Non-Governmental Organizations and Governmentality: ‘Consuming’ Biodiversity and Indigenous People in the Philippines. *Political Studies*, 50(2), 268–292. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9248.00370>
- Buchanan, D., & Badham, R. (2020). *Power, Politics, and Organizational Change*. SAGE.
- Bullard, R. D. (2001). Environmental Justice in the 21st Century: Race Still Matters. *Phylon* (1960-), 49(3/4), 151–171. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3132626>
- Bulte, E. H., Damania, R., & López, R. (2007). On the gains of committing to inefficiency: Corruption, deforestation and low land productivity in Latin America. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 54(3), 277–295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2007.05.002>
- Bunn, D. A., Moyle, P. B., & Johnson, C. K. (2014). Maximizing the Ecological Contribution of Conservation Banks. *Wildlife Society Bulletin*, 38(2), 377–385. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wsb.398>
- Büscher, B. (2010). Anti-Politics as Political Strategy: Neoliberalism and Transfrontier Conservation in Southern Africa. *Development and Change*, 41(1), 29–51. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7660.2009.01621.x>
- Büscher, B., & Fletcher, R. (2019). Towards Convivial Conservation. *Conservation & Society*, 17(3), 283–296. <https://doi.org/10.4103/cs.cs.19.75>
- Bush, J., Frantzeskaki, N., Ossola, A., & Pineda-Pinto, M. (2023). Priorities for mainstreaming urban nature-based solutions in Australian cities. *Nature-Based Solutions*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbsj.2023.100065>
- Cadieux, K. V., & Taylor, L. (2013). *Landscape and the ideology of nature in exurbia: Green sprawl*. Routledge. <https://www.routledge.com/Landscape-and-the-Ideology-of-Nature-in-Exurbia-Green-Sprawl/Cadieux-Taylor/p/book/9780415747615?srsltid=AfmBOooYVw-ujrDaRQFHgzsv7yoOcUsSo3MLkKoL9KHURpkkG3XF2SUu>

- Camilleri, M. A., Troise, C., Strazzullo, S., & Bresciani, S. (2023). Creating shared value through open innovation approaches: Opportunities and challenges for corporate sustainability. *Business Strategy and the Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3377>
- Campling, L., & Havice, E. (2018). The Global Environmental Politics and Political Economy of Seafood Systems. *Global Environmental Politics*, 18(2), 72–92. https://doi.org/10.1162/glep_a_00453
- Cao, J., & Song, W. (2016). Risk assessment of co-creating value with customers: A rough group analytic network process approach. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 55, 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2016.02.012>
- Carmody, P., & Taylor, D. (2016). Globalization, Land Grabbing, and the Present-Day Colonial State in Uganda: Ecologization and Its Impacts. *The Journal of Environment & Development*, 25(1), 100–126. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1070496515622017>
- Carr, D. L. (2004). Proximate population factors and deforestation in tropical agricultural frontiers. *Population and Environment*, 25, 585–612. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:POEN.0000039066.05666.8d>
- Carr, E. R. (2005). Placing the environment in migration: Environment, economy, and power in Ghana's Central Region. *Environment and Planning A*, 37(5), 925–946. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a3754>
- Carr, E. R. (2019). Properties and projects: Reconciling resilience and transformation for adaptation and development. *World Development*, 122, 70–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2019.05.011>
- Carr, E. R. (2020). Resilient livelihoods in an era of global transformation. *Global Environmental Change*, 64(August). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102155>
- Carr, E. R., & McCusker, B. (2009). The co-production of land use and livelihoods change: Implications for development interventions. *Geoforum*, 40(4), 568–579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2009.04.010>
- Carroll, C., Hartl, B., Goldman, G. T., Rohlf, D. J., Treves, A., Kerr, J. T., Ritchie, E. G., Kingsford, R. T., Gibbs, K. E., Maron, M., & Watson, J. E. M. (2017). Defending the scientific integrity of conservation-policy processes. *Conservation Biology*, 31(5), 967–975. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12958>
- Carroll, D., & Charo, R. A. (2015). The societal opportunities and challenges of genome editing. *Genome Biology*, 16(1), 242. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-015-0812-0>
- Carruthers, D. V. (Ed.). (2008). *Environmental justice in Latin America: Problems, promise, and practice*. MIT Press.
- Caruso, L. (2018). Digital innovation and the fourth industrial revolution: Epochal social changes? *AI & Society*, 33(3), 379–392. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-017-0736-1>
- Cashore, B., Auld, G., & Newsom, D. (2008). Governing Through Markets: Forest Certification and the Emergence of Non-State Authority. In *Governing Through Markets*. Yale University Press. <https://doi.org/10.12987/9780300133110>
- Castano Garcia, A., Ambrose, A., Hawkins, A., & Parkes, S. (2021). High consumption, an unsustainable habit that needs more attention. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102241>
- Ceddia, M. G. (2020). The super-rich and cropland expansion via direct investments in agriculture. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(4), 312–318. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-0480-2>
- Chakrabarty, D. (1993). The Difference – Deferral of (A) Colonial Modernity: Public Debates on Domesticity in British Bengal. *History Workshop Journal*, 36(1), 1–34. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hwj/36.1.1>
- Chan, A. P. C., Darko, A., Olanipekun, A. O., & Ameyaw, E. E. (2018). Critical barriers to green building technologies adoption in developing countries: The case of Ghana. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, 1067–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.235>
- Chancel, L., Piketty, T., Saez, E., & Zucman, G. (2022). *World Inequality Report 2022*. Harvard University Press. https://wir2022.wid.world/www-site/uploads/2023/03/D_FINAL_WIL_RIM_RAPPORT_2303.pdf
- Chandra, A., & Idrisova, A. (2011). Convention on Biological Diversity: A review of national challenges and opportunities for implementation. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 20(14), 3295–3316. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-011-0141-x>
- Chapron, G., Epstein, Y., Trouwborst, A., & López-Bao, J. V. (2017). Bolster legal boundaries to stay within planetary boundaries. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1(3), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0086>
- Chaudhary, B. R., Erskine, W., & Acciaioli, G. (2022). Hybrid knowledge and climate-resilient agriculture practices of the Tharu in the western Tarai, Nepal. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpos.2022.969835>
- Chausson, A., Welden, E. A., Melanidis, M. S., Gray, E., Hiron, M., & Seddon, N. (2023). Going beyond market-based mechanisms to finance nature-based solutions and foster sustainable futures. *PLOS Climate*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000169>
- Cheng, Y., Awan, U., Ahmad, S., & Tan, Z. (2021). How do technological innovation and fiscal decentralization affect the environment? A story of the fourth industrial revolution and sustainable growth. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120398>
- Chinseu, E. L., Dougill, A. J., & Stringer, L. C. (2022). Strengthening Conservation Agriculture innovation systems in sub-Saharan Africa: Lessons from a stakeholder analysis. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 20(1), 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14735903.2021.1911511>
- Christophers, B. (2017). Climate Change and Financial Instability: Risk Disclosure and the Problematics of Neoliberal Governance. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 107(5), 1108–1127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2017.1293502>
- Christophers, B. (2024). *The Price is Wrong: Why Capitalism Won't Save the Planet*. Verso Books.
- Chung, M. G., Pan, T., Zou, X., & Liu, J. (2018). Complex Interrelationships between Ecosystem Services Supply and Tourism Demand: General Framework and Evidence from the Origin of Three Asian Rivers. *Sustainability*, 10(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10124576>
- Cincotta, R. P., Wisniewski, J., & Engelman, R. (2000). Human population in the biodiversity hotspots. *Nature*, 404(6781), 990–992. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35010105>
- Clapp & Purugganan. (2020). *Contextualizing corporate control in the agrifood and extractive sectors: Globalizations: Vol 17, No 7*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14747731.2020.1783814>

- Clay, N. (2016). Producing hybrid forests in the Congo Basin: A political ecology of the landscape approach to conservation. *Geoforum*, 76, 130–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2016.09.008>
- Clement, M. J., Hines, J. E., Nichols, J. D., Pardieck, K. L., & Ziolkowski, D. J. (2016). Estimating Indices of Range Shifts in Birds Using Dynamic Models When Detection Is Imperfect. *Global Change Biology*, 22(10), 3273–3285. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13283>
- Cock, J., & Fig, D. (2000). From colonial to community based conservation: Environmental justice and the national parks of South Africa. *Society in Transition*, 31(1), 22–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21528586.2000.10419008>
- Cody, L. F. (2000). The Politics of Illegitimacy in an Age of Reform: Women, Reproduction, and Political Economy in England's New Poor Law of 1834. *Journal of Women's History*, 11(4), 131–156. <https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/1/article/17270>
- Coenen, J., Sonderegger, G., Newig, J., Meyfroidt, P., Challies, E., Bager, S., Busck-Lumholt, L., Corbera, E., Friis, C., Frohn Pedersen, A., Laroche, P., Parra Paitan, C., Qin, S., Roux, N., & Zaehring, J. (2023). Toward spatial fit in the governance of global commodity flows. *Ecology and Society*, 28(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-14133-280224>
- Coenen, L., Benneworth, P., & Truffer, B. (2012). Toward a spatial perspective on sustainability transitions. *Research Policy*, 41(6), 968–979. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2012.02.014>
- Cojoianu, T. F., Collins, E., Hoepner, A. G. F., Magill, D., O'Neill, T., & Schneider, F. I. (2020). In the Name of COVID-19: Is the ECB Fuelling the Climate Crisis? *Environmental & Resource Economics*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-020-00450-z>
- Collins, Y. A., Maguire-Rajpaul, V., Krauss, J. E., Asiyambi, A., Jimenez, A., Mabele, M. B., & Alexander-Owen, M. (2021). Plotting the coloniality of conservation. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 28(1). <https://doi.org/10.2458/jpe.4683>
- Convention on Biological Diversity. (2022). *Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework* (No. CBD/COP/15/L.25). Convention on Biological Diversity. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf>
- Cook, B. I., Wolkovich, E. M., & Parmesan, C. (2012). Divergent responses to spring and winter warming drive community level flowering trends. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(23), 9000–9005. <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.1118364109>
- Copete, J. C., Kik, A., Novotny, V., & Cámara-Leret, R. (2023). The importance of Indigenous and local people for cataloging biodiversity. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 38(12), 1112–1114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2023.08.017>
- Cordelli, C. (2020). *The Privatized State*. Princeton University Press.
- Corson, C. (2010). Shifting Environmental Governance in a Neoliberal World: US AID for Conservation. *Antipode*, 42(3), 576–602. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8330.2010.00764.x>
- Cortés-Capano, G., Hausmann, A., Di Minin, E., & Kortetmäki, T. (2022). Ethics in biodiversity conservation: The meaning and importance of pluralism. *Biological Conservation*, 275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109759>
- Cory, J., Lerner, M., & Osgood, I. (2021). Supply Chain Linkages and the Extended Carbon Coalition. *American Journal of Political Science*, 65(1), 69–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12525>
- Cox, M. (2012). Diagnosing Institutional Fit: A Formal Perspective. *Ecology and Society*, 17(4). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05173-170454>
- Creed, I. F., Lane, C. R., Serran, J. N., Alexander, L. C., Basu, N. B., Calhoun, A. J. K., Christensen, J. R., Cohen, M. J., Craft, C., D'Amico, E., DeKeyser, E., Fowler, L., Golden, H. E., Jawitz, J. W., Kalla, P., Kirkman, L. K., Lang, M., Leibowitz, S. G., Lewis, D. B., ... Smith, L. (2017). Enhancing protection for vulnerable waters. *Nature Geoscience*, 10(11), 809–815. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo3041>
- Cripps, G., & Gardner, C. J. (2016). Human migration and marine protected areas: Insights from Vevo fishers in Madagascar. *Geoforum*, 74, 49–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2016.05.010>
- Cumming, G. S., Cumming, D. H. M., & Redman, C. L. (2006). Scale Mismatches in Social-Ecological Systems: Causes, Consequences, and Solutions. *Ecology and Society*, 11(1). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26267802>
- Cvitanovic, C., Fulton, C. J., Wilson, S. K., van Kerkhoff, L., Cripps, I. L., & Muthiga, N. (2014). Utility of primary scientific literature to environmental managers: An international case study on coral-dominated marine protected areas. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 102, 72–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2014.09.003>
- Cvitanovic, C., Hobday, A. J., van Kerkhoff, L., Wilson, S. K., Dobbs, K., & Marshall, N. A. (2015). Improving knowledge exchange among scientists and decision-makers to facilitate the adaptive governance of marine resources: A review of knowledge and research needs. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 112, 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2015.05.002>
- Dasgupta, P. (2021). *The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review*. (The Dasgupta Review). HM Treasury. <https://bibliotecadigital.ciren.cl/handle/20.500.13082/32687>
- Davis, D. K., & Robbins, P. (2018). Ecologies of the colonial present: Pathological forestry from the *taux de boisement* to civilized plantations. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*, 1(4), 447–469. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2514848618812029>
- de Graeff, N., Jongsma, K. R., Johnston, J., Hartley, S., & Bredenoord, A. L. (2019). The ethics of genome editing in non-human animals: A systematic review of reasons reported in the academic literature. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 374(1772). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2018.0106>
- De la Vega-Rivera, A., & Merino-Pérez, L. (2021). Socio-Environmental Impacts of the Avocado Boom in the Meseta Purépecha, Michoacán, Mexico. *Sustainability*, 13(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13137247>
- De Paula, L. F., Fritz, B., & Prates, D. M. (2017). Keynes at the periphery: Currency hierarchy and challenges for economic policy in emerging economies. *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, 40(2), 183–202. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01603477.2016.1252267>
- De Santo, E. M., Jones, P. J. S., & Miller, A. M. M. (2011). Fortress conservation at sea: A commentary on the Chagos marine protected area. *Marine Policy*, 35(2), 258–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2010.09.004>
- DeFries, R., & Nagendra, H. (2017). Ecosystem management as a wicked problem. *Science*, 356(6335), 265–270. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal1950>

- Dei, G. J. S. (2000). Rethinking the role of Indigenous knowledges in the academy. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 4(2), 111–132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/136031100284849>
- Delaroche, M., Dias, V. M., & Massoca, P. E. (2023). The intertemporal governance challenges of Brazil's Amazon: Managing soybean expansion, deforestation rates, and urban floods. *Sustainability Science*, 18(1), 43–58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01149-4>
- Dempsey, J., Irvine-Broque, A., Bigger, P., Christiansen, J., Muchhala, B., Nelson, S., Rojas-Marchini, F., Shapiro-Garza, E., Schuldt, A., & DiSilvestro, A. (2022). Biodiversity targets will not be met without debt and tax justice. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 6(3), 237–239. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-021-01619-5>
- Dempsey, J., Martin, T. G., & Sumaila, U. R. (2020). Subsidizing extinction? *Conservation Letters*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12705>
- Dempsey, J., Rowe, J., & Collard, R. (2016). Re-regulating Socioecologies Under Neoliberalism. In *Handbook of Neoliberalism*.
- Dempsey, J., & Suarez, D. C. (2016). Arrested Development? The Promises and Paradoxes of "Selling Nature to Save It." *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 106(3), 653–671. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2016.1140018>
- Deutsch, S., Keller, R., Krug, C. B., & Michel, A. H. (2023). Transdisciplinary transformative change: An analysis of some best practices and barriers, and the potential of critical social science in getting us there. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 32(11), 3569–3594. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-023-02576-0>
- Diamond, M. L., de Wit, C. A., Molander, S., Scheringer, M., Backhaus, T., Lohmann, R., Arvidsson, R., Bergman, Å., Hauschild, M., & Holoubek, I. (2015). Exploring the planetary boundary for chemical pollution. *Environment International*, 78, 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2015.02.001>
- Dibley, A., Wetzler, T., & Hepburn, C. (2021). National COVID debts: Climate change imperils countries' ability to repay. *Nature*, 592(7853), 184–187. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-00871-w>
- Dirzo, R., Young, H. S., Galetti, M., Ceballos, G., Isaac, N. J. B., & Collen, B. (2014). Defaunation in the Anthropocene. *Science*, 345(6195), 401–406. <https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.1251817>
- Dokis, C. A. (2015). *Where the Rivers Meet: Pipelines, Participatory Resource Management, and Aboriginal-State Relations in the Northwest Territories*. UBC Press.
- Domínguez, L., & Luoma, C. (2020). Decolonising Conservation Policy: How Colonial Land and Conservation Ideologies Persist and Perpetuate Indigenous Injustices at the Expense of the Environment. *Land*, 9(3), 65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land9030065>
- Downey, L. (2015). *Inequality, Democracy, and the Environment*. NYU Press.
- Dressler, W., & Roth, R. (2011). The Good, the Bad, and the Contradictory: Neoliberal Conservation Governance in Rural Southeast Asia. *World Development*, 39(5), 851–862. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2010.08.016>
- Duit, A., Feindt, P. H., & Meadowcroft, J. (2016). Greening Leviathan: The rise of the environmental state? *Environmental Politics*, 25(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2015.1085218>
- Dunkley, R., Baker, S., Constant, N., & Sanderson-Bellamy, A. (2018). Enabling the IPBES conceptual framework to work across knowledge boundaries. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*, 18(6), 779–799. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-018-9415-z>
- Duraipappah, A. K., Asah, S. T., Brondizio, E. S., Kosoy, N., O'Farrell, P. J., Prieur-Richard, A.-H., Subramanian, S. M., & Takeuchi, K. (2014). Managing the mismatches to provide ecosystem services for human well-being: A conceptual framework for understanding the New Commons. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 7, 94–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2013.11.031>
- Durst, S. (2013). Success Factors of Open Innovation—A Literature Review. *International Journal of Business Research and Management*, 4(4), 111–131. <https://www.cscjournals.org/manuscript/Journals/IJBRM/Volume4/Issue4/IJBRM-154.pdf>
- Eckerstorfer, M. F., Dolezel, M., Engelhard, M., Giovannelli, V., Grabowski, M., Heissenberger, A., Lener, M., Reichenbecher, W., Simon, S., Staiano, G., Wüst Saucy, A. G., Zünd, J., & Lüthi, C. (2023). Recommendations for the Assessment of Potential Environmental Effects of Genome-Editing Applications in Plants in the EU. *Plants*, 12(9), 1764. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12091764>
- Edwards, D. P., Magrach, A., Woodcock, P., Ji, Y., Lim, N. T. L., Edwards, F. A., Larsen, T. H., Hsu, W. W., Benedick, S., Khen, C. V., Chung, A. Y. C., Reynolds, G., Fisher, B., Laurance, W. F., Wilcove, D. S., Hamer, K. C., & Yu, D. W. (2014). Selective-logging and oil palm: Multitaxon impacts, biodiversity indicators, and trade-offs for conservation planning. *Ecological Applications*, 24(8), 2029–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11318>
- Ejdemo, T., & Söderholm, P. (2011). Mining investment and regional development: A scenario-based assessment for Northern Sweden. *Resources Policy*, 36(1), 14–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2010.08.008>
- Eliasson, K., West, C. D., Croft, S. A., & Green, J. M. H. (2023). A spatially explicit approach to assessing commodity-driven fertilizer use and its impact on biodiversity. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135195>
- Elliott, M., Golub, B., & Jackson, M. O. (2014). Financial Networks and Contagion. *American Economic Review*, 104(10), 3115–3153. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.104.10.3115>
- Energy Institute & Smil. (2017). *Direct primary energy from biofuels* [Dataset]. <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/global-primary-energy>
- Engel, K. (1997). State Environmental Standard-Setting: Is There a "Race" and Is It "to the Bottom"? *UC Law Journal*, 48(2), 271. https://repository.uclawsf.edu/hastings_law_journal/vol48/iss2/2
- Enters, T., & Anderson, J. (1999). *Rethinking the Decentralization and Devolution of Biodiversity Conservation*. FAO Forestry Department. <https://www.fao.org/4/x3030e/x3030e04.htm>
- Epstein, G., Pittman, J., Alexander, S. M., Berdej, S., Dyck, T., Kreitmair, U., Rathwell, K. J., Villamayor-Tomas, S., Vogt, J., & Armitage, D. (2015). Institutional fit and the sustainability of social–ecological systems. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 14, 34–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.03.005>
- Eriksen, T. H. (2021). The Loss of Diversity in the Anthropocene Biological and Cultural Dimensions. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpos.2021.743610>

- Erten, B., Korinek, A., & Ocampo, J. A. (2021). Capital Controls: Theory and Evidence. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 59(1), 45–89. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.20191457>
- Escobar, A. (2020). *Pluriversal politics: The real and the possible*. Duke University Press.
- Esgalhadó, C., & Guimaraes, M. H. (2020). Unveiling Contrasting Preferred Trajectories of Local Development in Southeast Portugal. *Land*, 9(3), 87. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land9030087>
- Es'haghi, S. R., & Karamidehkordi, E. (2023). Understanding the structure of stakeholders – projects network in endangered lakes restoration programs using social network analysis. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 140, 172–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.12.001>
- Esty, D., & Geradin, D. (1998). Environmental Protection and International Competitiveness: A Conceptual Framework. *Faculty Scholarship Series*. <https://openyls.law.yale.edu/handle/20.500.13051/3943>
- European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC). (2023). *Share of population living in cities, towns and suburbs* [dataset] [Global Human Settlement Layer Dataset 2023-10-31" [original data]]. <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/urban-share-european-commission>
- Faborode, H. F. B., & Ajayi, A. O. (2015). Research-Extension-Farmer-Input Linkage System for Better Communication and Uptake of Research Results in Nigerian Rural Agriculture. *Journal of Agricultural & Food Information*, 16(1), 80–96. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10496505.2015.982461>
- Fairhead, J., & Leach, M. (1995). False forest history, complicit social analysis: Rethinking some West African environmental narratives. *World Development*, 23(6), 1023–1035. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X\(95\)00026-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X(95)00026-9)
- FAO. (2020). *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020: Sustainability in action*. FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9229en>
- FAO. (2022a). *Enabling extension and advisory services to promote agroecology*. FAO. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/cb8221en>
- FAO. (2022b). Pesticides Trade and Pesticides Indicators–Global, Regional and Country Trends, 1990–2020. *FAOSTAT Analytical Briefs*, 46. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc0918en>
- FAO. (2024). *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2024*. FAO ; <https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/cd0683en>
- Fearnside, P. M. (2002). Avanço Brasil: Environmental and Social Consequences of Brazil's Planned Infrastructure in Amazonia. *Environmental Management*, 30(6), 735–747. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-002-2788-2>
- Federici, S. (2004). *Caliban and the Witch*. Autonomedia.
- Feola, G. (2015). Societal transformation in response to global environmental change: A review of emerging concepts. *Ambio*, 44(5). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-014-0582-z>
- Finney, C. (2014). *Black Faces, White Spaces: Reimagining the Relationship of African Americans to the Great Outdoors*. University of North Carolina Press. <https://books.google.com/books?id=hyOiAwAAQBAJ>
- Fischer-Kowalski, M., Rovenskaya, E., Krausmann, F., Pallua, I., & Mc Neill, J. R. (2019). Energy transitions and social revolutions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 138, 69–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.08.010>
- Fletcher, M., Hamilton, R., Dressler, W., & Palmer, L. (2021). Indigenous knowledge and the shackles of wilderness. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 118(40). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2022218118>
- Fletcher, R., & Büscher, B. (2020). Conservation basic income: A non-market mechanism to support convivial conservation. *Biological Conservation*, 244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108520>
- Flintan, F. (2011). *Broken lands: Broken lives? Causes, Processes and Impacts of Land Fragmentation in the Rangelands of Ethiopia, Kenya and Uganda* (p. 159) [Research report]. Regional Learning and Advocacy Programme. <https://dli-hoa.org/assets/upload/key-resilience-and-climate-change/20200804010023501.pdf>
- Folke, C., Österblom, H., Jouffray, J.-B., Lambin, E. F., Adger, W. N., Scheffer, M., Crona, B. I., Nyström, M., Levin, S. A., Carpenter, S. R., Anderies, J. M., Chapin, S., Crépin, A.-S., Dauriach, A., Galaz, V., Gordon, L. J., Kautsky, N., Walker, B. H., Watson, J. R., ... de Zeeuw, A. (2019). Transnational corporations and the challenge of biosphere stewardship. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 3(10), 1396–1403. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-0978-z>
- Folke, C., Polasky, S., Rockström, J., Galaz, V., Westley, F., Lamont, M., Scheffer, M., Österblom, H., Carpenter, S. R., Chapin, F. S., Seto, K. C., Weber, E. U., Crona, B. I., Daily, G. C., Dasgupta, P., Gaffney, O., Gordon, L. J., Hoff, H., Levin, S. A., ... Walker, B. H. (2021). Our future in the Anthropocene biosphere. *Ambio*, 50(4), 834–869. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01544-8>
- Folke, C., Pritchard, L., Berkes, F., Colding, J., & Svedin, U. (2007). The Problem of Fit between Ecosystems and Institutions: Ten Years Later. *Ecology and Society*, 12(1). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26267849>
- Font Vivanco et al. (2022). Rebound effect and sustainability science: A review. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/jiec.13295>
- Forest Peoples Programme. (2023). *Kichwa organizations of San Martín, Peru lament breakdown of dialogue with Cordillera Azul National Park authorities, territorial rights violations continue*. <https://www.forestpeoples.org/en/2023/Kichwa-organizations-San-Martin-lament-dialogue-breakdown-Cordillera-Azul>
- Foster, J. B. (1999). Marx's Theory of Metabolic Rift: Classical Foundations for Environmental Sociology. *American Journal of Sociology*, 105(2), 366–405. <https://doi.org/10.1086/210315>
- Fox, H. E., Christian, C., Nordby, J. C., Pergams, O. R. W., Peterson, G. D., & Pyke, C. R. (2006). Perceived Barriers to Integrating Social Science and Conservation. *Conservation Biology*, 20(6), 1817–1820. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4124711>
- Frank, A. G. (1967). *Capitalism and underdevelopment in Latin America: Historical studies of Chile and Brazil*. Monthly Review Press.
- Frank, A. G. (1979). *Dependent accumulation and underdevelopment*. Monthly Review Press.
- Frank, A., & Schäffler, L. (2019). Identifying key knowledge gaps to better protect biodiversity and simultaneously secure livelihoods in a priority conservation area. *Sustainability*, 11(20). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11205695>

- Franks, P. (2021). *Global Biodiversity Framework: Equitable governance is key*. <https://pubs.iied.org/20386IIED>
- Frantzeskaki, N., & de Haan, H. (2009). Transitions: Two steps from theory to policy. *Futures*, 41(9), 593–606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2009.04.009>
- Frantzeskaki, N., Thissen, W., & Grin, J. (2016). Drifting between transitions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 102, 275–286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2015.09.007>
- Frederiksen, P., van der Sluis, T., Vadineanu, A., Terkenli, T. S., Gaube, V., Gravsholt Busck, A., Vesterager, J. P., Geamana, N., Schistou, D. E., & Pedroli, B. (2017). Misfits and compliance patterns in the transposition and implementation of the Habitats Directive—Four cases. *Land Use Policy*, 62, 337–350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.12.010>
- Friedrichs, S., Takasu, Y., Kearns, P., Dagallier, B., Oshima, R., Schofield, J., & Moreddu, C. (2019). Meeting report of the OECD conference on “Genome Editing: Applications in Agriculture—Implications for Health, Environment and Regulation.” *Transgenic Research*, 28(3–4), 419–463. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11248-019-00154-1>
- Frison, E. A. (2016). IPES-Food (2016) From uniformity to diversity: A paradigm shift from industrial agriculture to diversified agroecological systems. *IPES, Louvain-La-Neuve (Belgium)*. <https://ipes-food.org/report/from-uniformity-to-diversity/>
- Fukugawa, N. (2019). Determinants and impacts of public agricultural research: Product-level evidence from agricultural Kohsetsushi in Japan. *Scientometrics*, 120(3), 1475–1498. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03158-0>
- Fuller, T. L., Narins, T. P., Nackoney, J., Bonebrake, T. C., Sesink Clee, P., Morgan, K., Tróchez, A., Bocuma Meñe, D., Bongwele, E., Njabo, K. Y., Anthony, N. M., Gonder, M. K., Kahn, M., Allen, W. R., & Smith, T. B. (2019). Assessing the impact of China’s timber industry on Congo Basin land use change. *Area*, 51(2), 340–349. <https://doi.org/10.1111/area.12469>
- Gabor, D. (2020). Critical macro-finance: A theoretical lens. *Finance and Society*, 6(1), 45–55. <https://doi.org/10.2218/finsoc.v6i1.4408>
- Gabor, D. (2021). The Wall Street Consensus. *Development and Change*, 52(3), 429–459. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12645>
- Galaz, V., Crona, B., Dauriach, A., Jouffray, J.-B., Österblom, H., & Fichtner, J. (2018). Tax havens and global environmental degradation. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 2(9), 1352–1357. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-018-0497-3>
- Galaz, V., Olsson, P., Hahn, T., Folke, C., & Svedin, U. (2008). *The problem of fit among biophysical systems, environmental and resource regimes, and broader governance systems: Insights and emerging challenges* (pp. 147–182). The MIT Press, Cambridge, USA. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/7920.003.0011>
- Gandy, M. (2022). Chennai flyways: Birds, biodiversity, and ecological decay. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25148486221142494>
- Gasteyer, S. P., & Butler Flora, C. (2000). Modernizing the Savage: Colonization and Perceptions of Landscape and Lifescape. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 40(1), 128–149. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9523.00135>
- Geddes, A., & Jordan, A. (2012). Migration as Adaptation? Exploring the Scope for Coordinating Environmental and Migration Policies in the European Union. *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 30(6), 1029–1044. <https://doi.org/10.1068/c1208j>
- German, L. (2022). *Power / Knowledge / Land: Contested Ontologies of Land and Its Governance in Africa*. University of Michigan Press. <https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.12071412>
- German, L., Charamila, S., & Tolera, T. (2006). Managing Trade-Offs in Agroforestry: From Conflict to Collaboration in Natural Resource Management. *African Highlands Initiative*. <http://www.worldagroforestry.org/downloads/Publications/PDFS/WP06059.pdf>
- German, L., & Stroud, A. (2007). A Framework for the Integration of Diverse Learning Approaches: Operationalizing Agricultural Research and Development (R&D) Linkages in Eastern Africa. *World Development*, 35(5), 792–814. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2006.09.013>
- Geyer et al. & OECD. (2017). *Annual plastic production between 1950 and 2019* [Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made]; OECD, “Global Plastics Outlook – Plastics use by application” [original data]. <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/global-plastics-production>
- Ghasemi, Saeid., Malekian, M., & Tarkesh, M. (2021). Climate change pushes an economic insect to the brink of extinction: A case study for *Cyamophila astragalicola* in Iran. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research*, 59(7, SI), 1632–1641. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jzs.12527>
- Ghosh, K. (2021). A framework to assess the benefits and challenges of ecosystem services of a reservoir-based wetland in the Himalayan foothills. *Environmental Development*, 40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2021.100669>
- Gilmore, R. W. (2002). Fatal Couplings of Power and Difference: Notes on Racism and Geography. *The Professional Geographer*, 54(1), 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0033-0124.00310>
- Ginn, F. (2008). Extension, subversion, containment: Eco-nationalism and (post) colonial nature in Aotearoa New Zealand. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 33(3), 335–353. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-5661.2008.00307.x>
- Global Footprint Network, Footprint Data Foundation, & York University Ecological Footprint Initiative. (2023). *National Footprint and Biocapacity Accounts 2019* [Open Data Platform]. Global Footprint Network. <https://data.footprintnetwork.org>
- Goldman, M. J. (2003). Partitioned Nature, Privileged Knowledge: Community-based Conservation in Tanzania. *Development and Change*, 34(5), 833–862. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7660.2003.00331.x>
- Gomes, L. A. de V., Facin, A. L. F., & Salerno, M. S. (2021). Managing uncertainty propagation in innovation ecosystems. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120945>
- Gordon, D. R., Jaffe, G., Doane, M., Glaser, A., Gremillion, T. M., & Ho, M. D. (2021). Responsible governance of gene editing in agriculture and the environment. *Nature Biotechnology*, 39(9), 1055–1057. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-021-01023-1>
- Grajales, J. (2011). The rifle and the title: Paramilitary violence, land grab and land control in Colombia. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, 38(4), 771–792. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150.2011.607701>

- Greco, M., Campagna, M., Cricelli, L., Grimaldi, M., & Strazzullo, S. (2022). COVID-19-related innovations: A study on underlying motivations and inter-organizational collaboration. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 106, 58–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmaman.2022.07.014>
- Green, A., Murphy, A., Collison, B. R., Sánchez-Nivicela, M., Anderson, H., Morano, J. L., Williams, T. D., & Wilkinson, C. E. (2022). A response to Cafaro, Hansson & Götmark (2022): Shifting the narrative from overpopulation to overconsumption. *Biological Conservation*, 273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109698>
- Green, F., & Healy, N. (2022). How inequality fuels climate change: The climate case for a Green New Deal. *One Earth*, 5(6), 635–649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2022.05.005>
- Grigg, N. S. (2016). Watersheds as Social-Ecological Systems. In N. S. Grigg, *Integrated Water Resource Management* (pp. 139–149). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-57615-6_7
- Grimaldi, M., Greco, M., & Cricelli, L. (2021). A framework of intellectual property protection strategies and open innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 123, 156–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.09.043>
- Grobler, S., & Dittrich, A.-K. (2024). Envisioning quality education for sustainability transformation in teacher education: Perspectives from an international dialogue on Sustainable Development Goal 4. *International Journal of Comparative Education and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCED-06-2023-0048>
- Guerrero, A. M., Bodin, Ö., McAllister, R. R., & Wilson, K. A. (2015). Achieving social-ecological fit through bottom-up collaborative governance: An empirical investigation. *Ecology and Society*, 20(4). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26270301>
- Gunderson, R. (2023). Powerless, Stupefied, and Repressed Actors Cannot Challenge Climate Change: Real Helplessness as a Barrier Between Environmental Concern and Action. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 53(2), 271–295. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jtsb.12366>
- Güneralp, B., Lwasa, S., Masundire, H., Parnell, S., & Seto, K. C. (2017). Urbanization in Africa: Challenges and opportunities for conservation. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa94fe>
- Güneralp, B., & Seto, K. C. (2013). Futures of global urban expansion: Uncertainties and implications for biodiversity conservation. *Environmental Research Letters*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/8/1/014025>
- Gurca, A., Bagherzadeh, M., Markovic, S., & Koporic, N. (2021). Managing the challenges of business-to-business open innovation in complex projects: A multi-stage process model. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 94, 202–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmaman.2020.05.035>
- Gustafsson, K. M., & Hysing, E. (2023). IPBES as a transformative agent: Opportunities and risks. *Environmental Conservation*, 50(1), 7–11. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892922000467>
- Gutierrez, J., Velazquez, J., Rodriguez, J., Hernando, A., Gomez, I., Herraiz, F., & Lopez-Sanchez, A. (2021). Livestock Trails as Keystone Structural Connectors for Pastureland Analysis Based on Remote Sensing and Structural Connectivity Assessment. *SUSTAINABILITY*, 13(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13115971>
- Hajer, M., Nilsson, M., Raworth, K., Bakker, P., Berkhout, F., De Boer, Y., Rockström, J., Ludwig, K., & Kok, M. (2015). Beyond Cockpit-ism: Four Insights to Enhance the Transformative Potential of the Sustainable Development Goals. *Sustainability*, 7(2), 1651–1660. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7021651>
- Hall, K. M. Q. (2016). A Transnational Black Feminist Framework: Rooting in Feminist Scholarship, Framing Contemporary Black Activism. *Meridians*, 15(1), 86–105. <https://doi.org/10.2979/meridians.15.1.06>
- Han, C., & Yang, M. (2022). Stimulating Innovation on Social Product Development: An Analysis of Social Behaviors in Online Innovation Communities. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 69(2), 365–375. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2019.2955073>
- Hanlon, W. W. (2020). Coal Smoke, City Growth, and the Costs of the Industrial Revolution. *The Economic Journal*, 130(626), 462–488. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ej/uez055>
- Hansen, M. (2013). New geographies of conservation and globalisation: The spatiality of development for conservation in the iSimangaliso Wetland Park, South Africa. *Journal of Contemporary African Studies*, 31(3), 481–502. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02589001.2013.807566>
- Harden-Davies, H. (2021). Marine Technology Transfer: Towards a Capacity-Building Toolkit for Marine Biodiversity beyond National Jurisdiction. In M. H. Nordquist & R. Long (Eds.), *Marine Biodiversity of Areas beyond National Jurisdiction* (pp. 231–238). Brill. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1163/j.ctv1sr6jp5.19>
- Harris, C. I. (1993). Whiteness as Property. *Harvard Law Review*, 106(8), 1707–1791. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1341787>
- Hausknost, D. (2020). The environmental state and the glass ceiling of transformation. *Environmental Politics*, 29(1), 17–37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2019.1680062>
- Hay, C. (1994). Environmental security and state legitimacy. *Capitalism Nature Socialism*, 5(1), 83–97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10455759409358577>
- Hemidat, S., Achouri, O., El Fels, L., Elagroudy, S., Hafidi, M., Chaouki, B., Ahmed, M., Hodgkinson, I., & Guo, J. (2022). Solid waste management in the context of a circular economy in the MENA region. *Sustainability*, 14(1), 480. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010480>
- Hempattarasuwan, N., Untong, A., Christakos, G., & Wu, J. (2021). Wetland changes and their impacts on livelihoods in Chiang Saen Valley, Chiang Rai Province, Thailand. *Regional Environmental Change*, 21(4), 115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-021-01842-7>
- Hendlin, Y. H. (2014). From Terra Nullius to Terra Communis: Reconsidering Wild Land in an Era of Conservation and Indigenous Rights. *Environmental Philosophy*, 11(2), 141–174. <https://doi.org/10.5840/ENVIROPHIL20143205>
- Henke, M., Besenfelder, C., Kaczmarek, S., & Fiolka, M. (2020). A Vision of Digitalization in Supply Chain Management and Logistics. S. 277–286. <https://doi.org/10.15488/9669>
- Hess, D. J., & Sovacool, B. (2020). Sociotechnical matters: Reviewing and integrating science and technology studies with energy social science. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101462>

- Hetherington, K. (2009). Privatizing the private in rural Paraguay: Precarious lots and the materiality of rights. *American Ethnologist*, 36(2), 224–241. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1425.2009.01132.x>
- Heynen, N., McCarthy, J., Prudham, S., & Robbins, P. (2007). *Neoliberal Environments: False Promises and Unnatural Consequences*. Routledge.
- Hickel, J. (2017). *The divide: A brief guide to global inequality and its solutions*. William Heinemann.
- Hickel, J., Dorninger, C., Wieland, H., & Suwandi, I. (2022). Imperialist appropriation in the world economy: Drain from the global South through unequal exchange, 1990–2015. *Global Environmental Change*, 73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2022.102467>
- Hoben, A. (1995). Paradigms and politics: The cultural construction of environmental policy in Ethiopia. *World Development*, 23(6), 1007–1021. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X\(95\)00019-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X(95)00019-9)
- Holt-Giménez, E. (2019). Capitalism, Food, and Social Movements: The Political Economy of Food System Transformation. *Journal of Agriculture, Food Systems, and Community Development*, 9(A), 23–35. <https://doi.org/10.5304/jafscd.2019.091.043>
- Hopwood, J. (2022). An inherited animus to communal land: The mechanisms of coloniality in land reform agendas in Acholiland, Northern Uganda. *Critical African Studies*, 14(1), 38–54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21681392.2021.1931383>
- Horváth, D., & Szabó, R. Z. (2019). Driving forces and barriers of Industry 4.0: Do multinational and small and medium-sized companies have equal opportunities? *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 146, 119–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.05.021>
- Hübschle, A. M. (2017). The social economy of rhino poaching: Of economic freedom fighters, professional hunters and marginalized local people. *Current Sociology*, 65(3), 427–447. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011392116673210>
- Hughes, A. C., Tougeron, K., Martin, D. A., Menga, F., Rosado, B. H. P., Villasante, S., Madgulkar, S., Gonçalves, F., Diele-Viegas, L. M., Colla, S. R., De Andrade Kamimura, V., Caggiano, H., Melo, F., De Oliveira Dias, M. G., Kellner, E., & Do Couto, E. V. (2023). Smaller human populations are still not a necessary condition for biodiversity conservation: A response to Cafaro et al. (2023). *Biological Conservation*, 282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2023.110053>
- Hull, V., & Liu, J. (2018). Telecoupling: A new frontier for global sustainability. *Ecology and Society*, 23(4). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10494-230441>
- Hurlbut, J. B. (2019). Human genome editing: Ask whether, not how. *Nature*, 565(7738), 135–136. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-07881-1>
- IGB – processed by Our World in Data. (2017). *Global freshwater use since 1900—IGB [original data]* [Dataset]. <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/global-freshwater-use-over-the-long-run>
- Igba, S. A., & Liaga, E. A. (2021). Coloniality, Legitimacy in Statebuilding, and the Use of Force in Africa. *The Thinker*, 89(4), 45–55. <https://doi.org/10.36615/thethinker.v89i4.689>
- IPBES. (2019a). *Global assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6417333>
- IPBES. (2019b). *Summary for policymakers of the Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (pp. 680–681). IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3553458>
- IPBES. (2021). *Report of the third ILK dialogue workshop for the IPBES values assessment: Reviewing the draft summary for policymakers and second order draft of the assessment*.
- IPBES. (2022a). *Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522522>
- IPBES. (2022b). *Summary for Policymakers of the Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522392>
- IPBES. (2023a). *Report of the second Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop for the IPBES assessment of transformative change: Reviewing the first order draft*. IPBES. https://files.ipbes.net/ipbes-web-prod-public-files/2023-08/IPBES_TfC_2ndILKDialogue_Report_Final_ForWeb.pdf
- IPBES. (2023b). *Report of the third Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop on the IPBES assessment of transformative change: Reviewing the first draft of the summary for policymakers and second drafts of the chapters*. IPBES.
- IPCC. (2018). *Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157940>.
- IRP. (2021). *Building Biodiversity: The Natural Resource Management Approach* (An Opinion Piece of the International Resource Panel Co-Chairs). International Resource Panel. <https://www.resourcepanel.org/reports/building-biodiversity>
- Irvine-Broque, A., & Dempsey, J. (2023). Risky business: Protecting nature, protecting wealth? *Conservation Letters*, 16(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12969>
- Ishikawa, N., & Soda, R. (2020). Commodification of Nature on the Plantation Frontier. In N. Ishikawa & R. Soda (Eds.), *Anthropogenic Tropical Forests* (pp. 1–22). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-7513-2_1
- Jacobi, J., Llanque, A., Mukhovi, S. M., Birachi, E., Von Groote, P., Eschen, R., Hilber-Schöb, I., Kiba, D. I., Frossard, E., & Robledo-Abad, C. (2022). Transdisciplinary co-creation increases the utilization of knowledge from sustainable development research. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 129, 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.12.017>
- Jacobsen, L. F., Pedersen, S., & Thøgersen, J. (2022). Drivers of and barriers to consumers' plastic packaging waste avoidance and recycling—A systematic literature review. *Waste Management*, 141, 63–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2022.01.021>
- Jasanoff, S. (2005). *Technologies of humility: Citizen participation in governing science*. Springer.

- Jasanoff, S., & Hurlbut, J. B. (2018). A global observatory for gene editing. *Nature*, 555(7697), 435–437. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-03270-w>
- Joffre, O. M., Klerkx, L., & Khoa, T. N. D. (2018). Aquaculture innovation system analysis of transition to sustainable intensification in shrimp farming. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 38(3), 34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-018-0511-9>
- Johns, T., Powell, B., Maundu, P., & Eyzaguirre, P. B. (2013). Agricultural biodiversity as a link between traditional food systems and contemporary development, social integrity and ecological health. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 93(14, SI), 3433–3442. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.6351>
- Jokinen, P., Blicharska, M., Primmer, E., Van Herzele, A., Kopperoinen, L., & Ratamäki, O. (2018). How does biodiversity conservation argumentation generate effects in policy cycles? *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 27(7), 1725–1740. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1216-5>
- Jones, E., Qadir, M., Van Vliet, M. T. H., Smakhtin, V., & Kang, S. (2019). The state of desalination and brine production: A global outlook. *Science of The Total Environment*, 657, 1343–1356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.12.076>
- Jones, I., Timoshenko, A., Zuban, I., Zhadan, K., Cusack, J. J., Duthie, A. B., Hodgson, I. D., Minderman, J., Pozo, R. A., Whytock, R. C., & Bunnefeld, N. (2022). Achieving international biodiversity targets: Learning from local norms, values and actions regarding migratory waterfowl management in Kazakhstan. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 59(7), 1911–1924. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14198>
- Jones, P. J. S. (2009). Equity, justice and power issues raised by no-take marine protected area proposals. *Marine Policy*, 33(5), 759–765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2009.02.009>
- Jordan, N. R., Dorn, K. M., Smith, T. M., Wolf, K. E., Ewing, P. M., Fernandez, A. L., Runck, B. C., Williams, A., Lu, Y., & Kuzma, J. (2017). A cooperative governance network for crop genome editing. *EMBO Reports*, 18(10), 1683–1687. <https://doi.org/10.15252/embr.201744394>
- Jouffray, J.-B., Blasiak, R., Norström, A. V., Österblom, H., & Nyström, M. (2020). The Blue Acceleration: The Trajectory of Human Expansion into the Ocean. *One Earth*, 2(1), 43–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.12.016>
- Kaliakparova, G. S., Gridneva, Y. E., Assanova, S. S., Sauranbay, S. B., & Saparbayev, A. D. (2020). International Economic Cooperation of Central Asian Countries on Energy Efficiency and Use of Renewable Energy Sources. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 10(5), 539–545. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijeep.9962>
- Kalikoski, D. C., Vasconcellos, M., & Lavkulich, L. (2002). Fitting institutions to ecosystems: The case of artisanal fisheries management in the estuary of Patos Lagoon. *Marine Policy*, 26(3), 179–196. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-597X\(01\)00048-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-597X(01)00048-3)
- Karamidehkordi, E. (2007). *Knowledge and information systems in watershed management: A study of Bazoft watershed and relevant institutions in Chaharmahal and Bakhtiari Province, Iran* [Ph.D., University of Reading]. <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.555859>
- Karamidehkordi, E. (2013). Public–Private Policy Change and its Influence on the Linkage of Agricultural Research, Extension and Farmers in Iran. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 19(3), 237–255. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2013.782167>
- Kashwan, P., V. Duffy, R., Massé, F., Asiyani, A. P., & Marjinen, E. (2021). From Racialized Neocolonial Global Conservation to an Inclusive and Regenerative Conservation. *Environment: Science and Policy for Sustainable Development*, 63(4), 4–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00139157.2021.1924574>
- Kassem, H. S., Aldosari, F. O., Baig, M. B., Muneer, S., & Elmajem, A. N. (2018). Researchers’ and extension workers’ perspectives on agricultural research-extension linkages in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *JAPS: Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*, 28(5), 1516–1522. <https://thejaps.org.pk/docs/v-28-05/35.pdf>
- Kedward, K., Ryan-Collins, J., & Buller, A. (2021). Quantitative Easing and Nature Loss: Exploring Nature-Related Financial Risks and Impacts in the European Central Bank’s Corporate Bond Portfolio. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3922913>
- Kedward, K., Ryan-Collins, J., & Chenet, H. (2020). *Managing Nature-Related Financial Risks: A Precautionary Policy Approach for Central Banks and Financial Supervisors*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3726637>
- Kedward, K., zu Ermgassen, S., Ryan-Collins, J., & Wunder, S. (2023a). Heavy reliance on private finance alone will not deliver conservation goals. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 7(9), 1339–1342. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02098-6>
- Kedward, K., zu Ermgassen, S., Ryan-Collins, J., & Wunder, S. (2023b). Publisher Correction: Heavy reliance on private finance alone will not deliver conservation goals. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 7(9), 1538–1538. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02178-7>
- Kenner, D. (2019). *Carbon Inequality: The Role of the Richest in Climate Change*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351171328>
- Khan, S. A. R., Zkik, K., Belhadi, A., & Kamble, S. S. (2021). Evaluating barriers and solutions for social sustainability adoption in multi-tier supply chains. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(11), 3378–3397. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2021.1876271>
- Kibria, M. G., Masuk, N. I., Safayet, R., Nguyen, H. Q., & Mourshed, M. (2023). Plastic Waste: Challenges and Opportunities to Mitigate Pollution and Effective Management. *International Journal of Environmental Research*, 17(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41742-023-00507-z>
- Kim, I. S., & Milner, H. V. (2019). Multinational corporations and their influence through lobbying on foreign policy. *Multinational Corporations in a Changing Global Economy*, 497–536. <https://hvmilner.scholar.princeton.edu/publications/multinational-corporations-and-their-influencethrough-lobbying-foreign-policy>
- Kimura, A. H., & Kinchy, A. (2019). *Science by the people: Participation, power, and the politics of environmental knowledge*. Rutgers University Press.
- Kinchy, A. J., Phadke, R., & Smith, J. M. (2018). Engaging the underground: An STS field in formation. *Engaging Science, Technology, and Society*, 4, 22–42. <https://doi.org/10.17351/ests2018.213>
- Kirchhübel, N., & Fantke, P. (2019). Getting the chemicals right: Toward characterizing toxicity and ecotoxicity impacts of inorganic substances. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 227, 554–565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.204>

- Knight, K. W., Schor, J. B., & Jorgenson, A. K. (2017). Wealth Inequality and Carbon Emissions in High-income Countries. *Social Currents*, 4(5), 403–412. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2329496517704872>
- Kofler, N., Collins, J. P., Kuzma, J., Marris, E., Esvelt, K., Nelson, M. P., Newhouse, A., Rothschild, L. J., Vigliotti, V. S., Semenov, M., Jacobsen, R., Dahlman, J. E., Prince, S., Caccone, A., Brown, T., & Schmitz, O. J. (2018). Editing nature: Local roots of global governance. *Science*, 362(6414), 527–529. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat4612>
- Kohler, F., & Brondizio, E. S. (2017). Considering the needs of indigenous and local populations in conservation programs. *Conservation Biology: The Journal of the Society for Conservation Biology*, 31(2), 245–251. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12843>
- Konisky, D. (2007). Regulatory Competition and Environmental Enforcement: Is There A Race to the Bottom? *American Journal of Political Science*, 51, 853–872. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2007.00285.x>
- Korinek, A. (2018). Regulating capital flows to emerging markets: An externality view. *Journal of International Economics*, 111, 61–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2017.12.005>
- Kröger, M. (2017). Inter-sectoral determinants of forest policy: The power of deforesting actors in post-2012 Brazil. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 77, 24–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2016.06.003>
- Kujala, H., Maron, M., Kennedy, C. M., Evans, M. C., Bull, J. W., Wintle, B. A., Iftikhar, S. M., Selwood, K. E., Beissner, K., Osborn, D., & Gordon, A. (2022). Credible biodiversity offsetting needs public national registers to confirm no net loss. *One Earth*, 5(6), 650–662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2022.05.011>
- Kumar, P., Singh, R. K., & Kumar, V. (2021). Managing supply chains for sustainable operations in the era of industry 4.0 and circular economy: Analysis of barriers. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105215>
- Lahsen, M., & Turnhout, E. (2021). How norms, needs, and power in science obstruct transformations towards sustainability. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(2). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abdcef0>
- Landry, N., Gifford, R., Milfont, T., Weeks, A., & Arnocky, S. (2018). Learned helplessness moderates the relationship between environmental concern and behavior. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2017.12.003>
- Lanz, B., Dietz, S., & Swanson, T. (2018). The Expansion of Modern Agriculture and Global Biodiversity Decline: An Integrated Assessment. *Ecological Economics*, 144, 260–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.07.018>
- Lazonick, W., & O'Sullivan, M. (2000). Maximizing shareholder value: A new ideology for corporate governance. *Economy and Society*, 29(1), 13–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/030851400360541>
- Lazonick, W., & Shin, J.-S. (2019). *Predatory Value Extraction: How the Looting of the Business Corporation Became the US Norm and How Sustainable Prosperity Can Be Restored*. Oxford University Press.
- Leclère, D., Obersteiner, M., Barrett, M., Butchart, S. H. M., Chaudhary, A., De Palma, A., DeClerck, F. A. J., Di Marco, M., Doelman, J. C., Dürauer, M., Freeman, R., Harfoot, M., Hasegawa, T., Hellweg, S., Hilbers, J. P., Hill, S. L. L., Humpenöder, F., Jennings, N., Krisztin, T., ... Young, L. (2020). Bending the curve of terrestrial biodiversity needs an integrated strategy. *Nature*, 585(7826), 551–556. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2705-y>
- Lee, D. (2024). *Quantitative Easing and Inequality* (Staff Reports (Federal Reserve Bank of New York) [Staff Reports (Federal Reserve Bank of New York)]. Federal Reserve Bank of New York. <https://doi.org/10.59576/sr.1108>
- Leichenko, R., Gram-Hanssen, I., & O'Brien, K. (2022). Teaching the “how” of transformation. *Sustainability Science*, 17(2), 573–584. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00964-5>
- Lemly, A. D., & Skorupa, J. P. (2012). Wildlife and the Coal Waste Policy Debate: Proposed Rules for Coal Waste Disposal Ignore Lessons from 45 Years of Wildlife Poisoning. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 46(16), 8595–8600. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es301467q>
- Lenzen, M., Moran, D., Kanemoto, K., Foran, B., Lobefaro, L., & Geschke, A. (2012). International trade drives biodiversity threats in developing nations. *Nature*, 486(7401), 109–112. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11145>
- Leviston, Z., & Walker, I. (2012). Beliefs and Denials About Climate Change: An Australian Perspective. *Ecopsychology*, 4(4), 277–285. <https://doi.org/10.1089/eco.2012.0051>
- Li, T. M. (2010). To Make Live or Let Die? Rural Dispossession and the Protection of Surplus Populations. *Antipode*, 41(s1), 66–93. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8330.2009.00717.x>
- Li, X. (2015). *Multi-Dimensional Assessment of Transit System Efficiency and Incentive-based Subsidy Allocation*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Multi-Dimensional-Assessment-of-Transit-System-and-Li/04b2e0eb74c996eeda9c7b05fbd4bf6f03246242>
- Lightfoot, K. G., Panich, L. M., Schneider, T. D., & Gonzalez, S. L. (2013). European colonialism and the Anthropocene: A view from the Pacific Coast of North America. *Anthropocene*, 4, 101–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ancene.2013.09.002>
- Lin, D., Hanscom, L., Murthy, A., Galli, A., Evans, M., Neill, E., Mancini, M., Martindill, J., Medouar, F.-Z., Huang, S., & Wackernagel, M. (2018). Ecological Footprint Accounting for Countries: Updates and Results of the National Footprint Accounts, 2012–2018. *Resources*, 7(3), 58. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources7030058>
- Lindenmayer, D. B., & Laurance, W. F. (2012). A history of hubris – Cautionary lessons in ecologically sustainable forest management. *Biological Conservation*, 151(1), 11–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2011.10.032>
- Linder, N., Giusti, M., Samuelsson, K., & Barthel, S. (2022). Pro-environmental habits: An underexplored research agenda in sustainability science. *Ambio*, 51(3), 546–556. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01619-6>
- Lippolis, S., Ruggieri, A., & Leopizzi, R. (2023). Open Innovation for sustainable transition: The case of Enel “Open Power.” *Business Strategy and the Environment*, n/a(n/a). <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3361>
- Lister, J. (2018). The Policy Role of Corporate Carbon Management: Co-regulating Ecological Effectiveness. *Global Policy*, 9(4), 538–548. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.12618>
- Liu, J. (2022). *Consumption patterns and biodiversity*. The Royal Society. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/topics-policy/projects/biodiversity/consumption-patterns-and-biodiversity/>

- Liu, J. (2023). Leveraging the metacoupling framework for sustainability science and global sustainable development. *National Science Review*, 10(7). <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwad090>
- Liu, J., Herzberger, A., Kapsar, K., Carlson, A. K., & Connor, T. (2019). What Is Telecoupling? In C. Friis & J. Ø. Nielsen (Eds.), *Telecoupling: Exploring Land-Use Change in a Globalised World* (pp. 19–48). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11105-2_2
- Liu, J., Hull, V., Batistella, M., DeFries, R., Dietz, T., Fu, F., Hertel, T., Izaurralde, R. C., Lambin, E., Li, S., Martinelli, L., McConnell, W., Moran, E., Naylor, R., Ouyang, Z., Polenske, K., Reenberg, A., de Miranda Rocha, G., Simmons, C., ... Zhu, C. (2013). Framing Sustainability in a Telecoupled World. *Ecology and Society*, 18(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05873-180226>
- Liverman, D. M., & Vilas, S. (2006). Neoliberalism and the Environment in Latin America. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 31(1), 327–363. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.energy.29.102403.140729>
- Lizardo, O. (2021). Habit and the explanation of action. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 51(3), 391–411. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jtsb.12273>
- Long, D., & Hoogendoorn, G. (2014). Second Home Owner Perceptions of Their Environmental Impacts: The Case of Hartbeespoort. *Urban Forum*, 25(4), 517–530. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12132-013-9208-y>
- Longoria, L. C., López-Forniés, I., Sáenz, D. C., & Sierra-Pérez, J. (2021). Promoting sustainable consumption in Higher Education Institutions through integrative co-creative processes involving relevant stakeholders. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 28, 445–458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.06.009>
- Loorbach, D., Frantzeskaki, N., & Avelino, F. (2017). Sustainability Transitions Research: Transforming Science and Practice for Societal Change. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 42(1), 599–626. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-102014-021340>
- Lucas, A. (2021). Investigating networks of corporate influence on government decision-making: The case of Australia's climate change and energy policies. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102271>
- Lunstrum, E. (2018). Capitalism, Wealth, and Conservation in the Age of Security: The Vitalization of the State. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 108(4), 1022–1037. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2017.1407629>
- Lute, M. L., & Carter, N. H. (2020). Are We Coexisting With Carnivores in the American West? *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2020.00048>
- Lynch, A. J. J., Kalumanga, E., Ospina, G. A., Lynch, A. J. J., Kalumanga, E., & Ospina, G. A. (2016). Socio-ecological aspects of sustaining Ramsar wetlands in three biodiverse developing countries. *Marine and Freshwater Research*, 67(6), 850–868. <https://doi.org/10.1071/MF15419>
- Mabele, M. B. (2017). Beyond forceful measures: Tanzania's 'war on poaching' needs diversified strategies more than militarised tactics. *Review of African Political Economy*, 44(153), 487–498. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03056244.2016.1271316>
- MacDuffee, M., Barrett-Lennard, L., Chhor, A., Dennert, A. M., Ross, P. S., Scott, D. C., Vergara, V., & Walters, K. (2023). Will Canada permit killer whale extinction? *Science*, 380(6652), 1330–1330. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adi5984>
- MacKinnon, I. (2018). Decommonising the mind': Historical impacts of British imperialism on indigenous tenure systems and self-understanding in the Highlands and Islands of Scotland. *The Commons Journal*, 12(1), 278–300. <https://doi.org/10.18352/jic.814>
- Madanaguli, A., Dhir, A., Talwar, S., Clauss, T., Kraus, S., & Kaur, P. (2023). Diving into the uncertainties of open innovation: A systematic review of risks to uncover pertinent typologies and unexplored horizons. *Technovation*, 119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2022.102582>
- Mader, A. (2020). *Policy brief: Biodiversity challenges and solutions in Asia and the Pacific Outline*. <https://policycommons.net/artifacts/1556497/policy-brief/2246306/>
- Maestre Andrés, S., Calvet Mir, L., Van Den Bergh, J. C. J. M., Ring, I., & Verburg, P. H. (2012). Ineffective biodiversity policy due to five rebound effects. *Ecosystem Services*, 1(1), 101–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2012.07.003>
- Makate, C. (2020). Local institutions and indigenous knowledge in adoption and scaling of climate-smart agricultural innovations among sub-Saharan smallholder farmers. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, 12(2), 270–287. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-07-2018-0055>
- Malhotra, A., Majchrzak, A., & Niemiec, R. M. (2017). Using Public Crowds for Open Strategy Formulation: Mitigating the Risks of Knowledge Gaps. *Long Range Planning*, 50(3), 397–410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2016.06.004>
- Manning, P., & Gills, B. K. (2011). *Andre Gunder Frank and global development: Visions, remembrances and explorations*. Routledge.
- Maron, M., Bull, J. W., Evans, M. C., & Gordon, A. (2015). Locking in loss: Baselines of decline in Australian biodiversity offset policies. *Biological Conservation*, 192, 504–512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2015.05.017>
- Mashhadi Rajabi, M. (2022). Dilemmas of energy efficiency: A systematic review of the rebound effect and attempts to curb energy consumption. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102661>
- Massé, F., & Lunstrum, E. (2016). Accumulation by securitization: Commercial poaching, neoliberal conservation, and the creation of new wildlife frontiers. *Geoforum*, 69, 227–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2015.03.005>
- Matikainen, S., Campiglio, E., & Zenghelis, D. (2017). *The climate impact of quantitative easing*. https://www.lse.ac.uk/granthaminstitute/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ClimateImpactQuantEasing_Matikainen-et-al.pdf
- McAfee, K. (1999). Selling Nature to save It? Biodiversity and Green Developmentalism. *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space*, 17(2), 133–154. <https://doi.org/10.1068/d170133>
- McCarthy, J. (2004). Privatizing conditions of production: Trade agreements as neoliberal environmental governance. *Geoforum*, 35(3), 327–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2003.07.002>
- McCarthy, J., & Prudham, S. (2004). Neoliberal nature and the nature of neoliberalism. *Geoforum*, 35(3), 275–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2003.07.003>
- McCulloch, N. (2023). *Ending Fossil Fuel Subsidies: The politics of saving the planet*. Practical Action Publishing.

- McGlynn, B., Plummer, R., Guerrero, A. M., & Baird, J. (2023). Assessing social-ecological fit of flood planning governance. *Ecology and Society*, 28(1), Article-number. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-13842-280123>
- Mehmood, A., Ahmed, S., Viza, E., Bogush, A., & Ayyub, R. M. (2021). Drivers and barriers towards circular economy in agri-food supply chain: A review. *Business Strategy & Development*, 4(4), 465–481. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.171>
- Meinzen-Dick, R. (2007). Beyond panaceas in water institutions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(39), 15200–15205. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0702296104>
- Meira-Neto, J. A. A., & Neri, A. V. (2017). Appealing the death sentences of the Doce, São Francisco and Amazonas rivers: Stopping the Mining Lobby and creating ecosystem services reserves. *Perspectives in Ecology and Conservation*, 15(3), 199–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecon.2017.06.008>
- Mei-Singh, L. (2016). Carceral Conservationism: Contested Landscapes and Technologies of Dispossession at Ka'ena Point, Hawai'i. *American Quarterly*, 68(3), 695–721. <https://doi.org/10.1353/aq.2016.0059>
- Mellal, M. A. (2020). Obsolescence – A review of the literature. *Technology in Society*, 63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101347>
- Mellegård, V., & Boonstra, W. J. (2020). Craftsmanship as a Carrier of Indigenous and Local Ecological Knowledge: Photographic Insights from Sámi Duodji and Archipelago Fishing. *Society & Natural Resources*, 33(10), 1252–1272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2020.1729911>
- Melnikovych, M., Nijnik, M., Soloviy, I., Nijnik, A., Sarkki, S., & Bihun, Y. (2018). Social-ecological innovation in remote mountain areas: Adaptive responses of forest-dependent communities to the challenges of a changing world. *Science of The Total Environment*, 613–614, 894–906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.07.065>
- Menon, D. M. (2002). Religion and Colonial Modernity: Rethinking Belief and Identity. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 37(17), 1662–1667. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4412047>
- Merchant, C. (1980). *The death of nature: Women, ecology, and the scientific revolution* (1st ed). Harper & Row. <https://philpapers.org/rec/MERTDO-7>
- Merchant, E. K. (2022). Environmental Malthusianism and demography. *Social Studies of Science*, 52(4), 536–560. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03063127221104929>
- Meyerson, F. A., Merino, L., & Durand, J. (2007). Migration and environment in the context of globalization. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 5, 182–190. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295\(2007\)5\[182:MAEITC\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295(2007)5[182:MAEITC]2.0.CO;2)
- M'Gonigle, M., & Takeda, L. (2013). The Liberal Limits of Environmental Law: A Green Legal Critique. *Pace Environmental Law Review*, 30(3). <https://doi.org/10.58948/0738-6206.1730>
- Mhlanga, D. (2022). Stakeholder Capitalism, the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), and Sustainable Development: Issues to Be Resolved. *Sustainability*, 14(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14073902>
- Mies, M. (1986). Patriarchy and Accumulation on a World Scale. Women in the international division of labour. *Labour, Capital and Society / Travail, Capital et Société*, 2. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43157768>
- Milana, E., & Ulrich, F. (2022). Do open innovation practices in firms promote sustainability? *Sustainable Development*, 30(6), 1718–1732. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2337>
- Miloslavich, P., Seeyave, S., Muller-Karger, F., Bax, N., Ali, E., Delgado, C., Evers-King, H., Loveday, B., Lutz, V., Newton, J., Nolan, G., Peralta Brichtova, A. C., Traeger-Chatterjee, C., & Urban, E. (2019). Challenges for global ocean observation: The need for increased human capacity. *Journal of Operational Oceanography*, 12(sup2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/1755876X.2018.1526463>
- Monast, J. J. (2018). Governing Extinction in the Era of Gene Editing. *NCL Rev.*, 97. <https://scholarship.law.unc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=6741&context=nclr>
- Moore, J. W. (2017). The Capitalocene, Part I: on the nature and origins of our ecological crisis. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150.2016.1235036>, 44(3), 594–630. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150.2016.1235036>
- Moosa, I., Al-Saad, K., & Khatatbeh, I. (2024). The Quantity Theory of Money, Quantitative Easing and the Missing Inflation Phenomenon. *Journal of Central Banking Theory and Practice*, 13, 71–88. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jcbtp-2024-0013>
- Moreno-Mateos, D., Maris, V., Bechet, A., & Curran, M. (2015). The true loss caused by biodiversity offsets. *BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION*, 192, 552–559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2015.08.016>
- Moss, T. (2012). Spatial Fit, from Panacea to Practice: Implementing the EU Water Framework Directive. *Ecology and Society*, 17(3). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26269060>
- Muchhala, B. (2022). The Structural Power of the State-Finance Nexus: Systemic Delinking for the Right to Development. *Development*, 65(2), 124–135. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41301-022-00343-2>
- Müller, J. M., Kiel, D., & Voigt, K.-I. (2018). What Drives the Implementation of Industry 4.0? The Role of Opportunities and Challenges in the Context of Sustainability. *Sustainability*, 10(1), 247. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10010247>
- Mungekar, N., Janssen, A., Hölscher, K., & Loorbach, D. (2023). *Decolonizing governance in Indian cities through reparative capacities. Case – Bhuj*. <https://www.ippapublicpolicy.org/file/paper/6477c70da7e7b.pdf>
- Munroe, D. K., Batistella, M., Friis, C., Gasparri, N. I., Lambin, E. F., Liu, J., Meyfroidt, P., Moran, E., & Nielsen, J. Ø. (2019). Governing flows in telecoupled land systems. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 38, 53–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2019.05.004>
- Münster, D., & Münster, U. (2012). Consuming the Forest in an Environment of Crisis: Nature Tourism, Forest Conservation and Neoliberal Agriculture in South India: *The Neoliberalization of Nature, South India. Development and Change*, 43(1), 205–227. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7660.2012.01754.x>
- Murau, S., & Klooster, J. van 't. (2022). Rethinking Monetary Sovereignty: The Global Credit Money System and the State. *Perspectives on Politics*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S153759272200127X>
- Nana, E. D., Njabo, K. Y., Tarla, F. N., Tah, E. K., Mavakala, K., Iponga, D. M., Demetrio, B. M., Kinzonzi, L., Embolo, L. E., & Mpouam, S. (2022). Putting conservation efforts in Central Africa on the right track for interventions that last. *Conservation Letters*, 15(6). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12913>

- Natalicchio, A., Messeni Petruzzelli, A., & Garavelli, A. C. (2017). Innovation problems and search for solutions in crowdsourcing platforms – A simulation approach. *Technovation*, 64–65, 28–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2017.05.002>
- Ndlovu-Gatsheni, S. J. (2013). *Empire, Global Coloniality and African Subjectivity* (1st ed.). Berghahn Books. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt9qcvmf>
- Nelson, V., & Flint, M. (2019). *Critical reflections on responsible business initiatives and systemic constraints for achieving a safe and just operating space for humanity* (P. Lund-Thomsen, M. Hansen, & A. Lindgreen, Eds.). Routledge. <https://gala.gre.ac.uk/id/eprint/24233/>
- Nelson, V., & Tallontire, A. (2014). Battlefields of ideas: Changing narratives and power dynamics in private standards in global agricultural value chains. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 31(3), 481–497. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-014-9512-8>
- Neumayer, E. (2001). Do countries fail to raise environmental standards? An evaluation of policy options addressing “regulatory chill.” *International Journal of Sustainable Development*, 4(3), 231–244. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJSD.2001.004446>
- Newig, J., Schulz, D., & Jager, N. W. (2016). Disentangling Puzzles of Spatial Scales and Participation in Environmental Governance—The Case of Governance Re-scaling Through the European Water Framework Directive. *Environmental Management*, 58(6), 998–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-016-0753-8>
- Nightingale, A. J. (2011). Bounding difference: Intersectionality and the material production of gender, caste, class and environment in Nepal. *Geoforum*, 42(2), 153–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2010.03.004>
- Ocholla, D. (2020). *Decolonizing higher education in Africa: Implications and possibilities for university libraries* | Ocholla | College & Research Libraries News. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.81.6.289>
- OECD. (2005). *Environmentally Harmful Subsidies: Challenges for Reform*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264012059-en>
- OECD. (2020). *A Comprehensive Overview of Global Biodiversity Finance* (p. 41). Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). <https://www.oecd.org/environment/resources/biodiversity/report-a-comprehensive-overview-of-global-biodiversity-finance.pdf>
- OECD. (2021). *Biodiversity, natural capital and the economy: A policy guide for finance, economic and environment ministries* (OECD Environment Policy Papers No. 26; OECD Environment Policy Papers, Vol. 26). <https://doi.org/10.1787/1a1ae114-en>
- Ojeda, D. (2021). Social reproduction, dispossession, and the gendered workings of agrarian extractivism in Colombia. *Agrarian Extractivism in Latin America*, 85. https://www.academia.edu/50677660/Social_reproduction_dispossession_and_the_gendered_workings_of_agrarian_extractivism_in_Colombia
- Ojeda, D. (2022). Beyond Land as Property: A Feminist Perspective. In S. M. Borras Jr. & J. C. Franco (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Land Politics*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhob/9780197618646.013.17>
- Okada, T., Mito, Y., Tokunaga, K., Sugino, H., Kubo, T., Akiyama, Y. B., Endo, T., Otani, S., Yamochi, S., Kozuki, Y., Kusakabe, T., Otsuka, K., Yamanaka, R., Shigematsu, T., & Kuwae, T. (2021). A comparative method for evaluating ecosystem services from the viewpoint of public works. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2021.105848>
- Olsson, P., Folke, C., & Hahn, T. (2004). Social-Ecological Transformation for Ecosystem Management: The Development of Adaptive Co-management of a Wetland Landscape in Southern Sweden. *Ecology and Society*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-00683-090402>
- Oman, W., Salin, M., & Svartzman, R. (2024). Three tales of central banking and financial supervision for the ecological transition. *WIREs Climate Change*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.876>
- Orecchia, C., & Zoppoli, P. (2007). Consumerism and Environment: Does Consumption Behaviour Affect Environmental Quality? *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1719507>
- O'Rourke, E. (2019). Drivers of Land Abandonment in the Irish Uplands: A Case Study. *European Countryside*, 11(2), 211–228. <https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2019-0011>
- Orozco-Ramirez, Q., Astier, M., & Barrasa, S. (2017). Agricultural Land Use Change after NAFTA in Central West Mexico. *LAND*, 6(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land6040066>
- Osakwe, P. N., & Solleder, O. (2023). Wealth Distribution, Income Inequality and Financial Inclusion: A Panel Data Analysis. *UNCTAD Working Papers*. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/unc/wwpaper/4.html>
- Österblom, H., Jouffray, J.-B., Folke, C., Crona, B., Troell, M., Merrie, A., & Rockström, J. (2015). Transnational Corporations as ‘Keystone Actors’ in Marine Ecosystems. *PLOS ONE*, 10(5). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0127533>
- Otero, I., Farrell, K. N., Pueyo, S., Kallis, G., Kehoe, L., Haberl, H., Plutzar, C., Hobson, P., García-Márquez, J., Rodríguez-Labajos, B., Martin, J. L., Erb, K. H., Schindler, S., Nielsen, J., Skorin, T., Settele, J., Essl, F., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Brotons, L., ... Pe'er, G. (2020). Biodiversity policy beyond economic growth. *Conservation Letters*, 13(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12713>
- Page, B. I., Bartels, L. M., & Seawright, J. (2013). Democracy and the Policy Preferences of Wealthy Americans. *Perspectives on Politics*, 11(1), 51–73. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S153759271200360X>
- Pahl-Wostl, C., Lukat, E., Stein, U., Tröltzsch, J., & Yousefi, A. (2023). Improving the socio-ecological fit in water governance by enhancing coordination of ecosystem services used. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 139, 11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.10.010>
- Pappas, I. O., Mikalef, P., Giannakos, M. N., Krogstie, J., & Lekakos, G. (2018). Big data and business analytics ecosystems: Paving the way towards digital transformation and sustainable societies. *Information Systems and E-Business Management*, 16(3), 479–491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10257-018-0377-z>
- Parris-Piper, N., Dressler, W. H., Satizábal, P., & Fletcher, R. (2023). Automating violence? The anti-politics of ‘smart technology’ in biodiversity conservation. *Biological Conservation*, 278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109859>
- Pascual, U., Balvanera, P., Anderson, C., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Christie, M., González-Jiménez, D., Martin, A., Raymond, C. M., Termansen, M., Vatn, A., Athayde, S., Baptiste, B., Barton, D. N., Jacobs, S., Kelemen, E., Kumar, R., Lazos, E., Mwampamba, T. H., Nakangu, B., ... Zent, E. (2023). Diverse values of nature for sustainability. *Nature*, 620(7975),

- 813–823. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06406-9>
- Patterson, J., Feola, G., & Kim, R. E. (2024). Negotiating discord in sustainability transformations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121(21). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2310186121>
- Patterson, J., Schulz, K., Vervoort, J., Van Der Hel, S., Widerberg, O., Adler, C., Hurlbert, M., Anderton, K., Sethi, M., & Barau, A. (2017). Exploring the governance and politics of transformations towards sustainability. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 24, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2016.09.001>
- Pauly, D., Watson, R., & Alder, J. (2005). Global trends in world fisheries: Impacts on marine ecosystems and food security. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 360(1453), 5–12. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1098/rstb.2004.1574>
- Peck, J., Theodore, N., & Brenner, N. (2010). Postneoliberalism and its Malcontents. In N. Castree, P. Chatterton, N. Heynen, W. Larner, & M. W. Wright (Eds.), *The Point is to Change it*. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444397352.ch5>
- Pendrill, F., Persson, U. M., Godar, J., & Kastner, T. (2019). Deforestation displaced: Trade in forest-risk commodities and the prospects for a global forest transition. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(5). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab0d41>
- Perino, A., Pereira, H. M., Felipe-Lucia, M., Kim, H., Kühl, H. S., Marselle, M. R., Meya, J. N., Meyer, C., Navarro, L. M., van Klink, R., Albert, G., Barratt, C. D., Bruelheide, H., Cao, Y., Chamoin, A., Darbi, M., Dornelas, M., Eisenhauer, N., Essl, F., ... Bonn, A. (2022). Biodiversity post-2020: Closing the gap between global targets and national-level implementation. *Conservation Letters*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12848>
- Persson, L., Carney Almroth, B. M., Collins, C. D., Cornell, S., De Wit, C. A., Diamond, M. L., Fantke, P., Hassellöv, M., MacLeod, M., Ryberg, M. W., Sogaard Jørgensen, P., Villarubia-Gómez, P., Wang, Z., & Hauschild, M. Z. (2022). Outside the Safe Operating Space of the Planetary Boundary for Novel Entities. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 56(3), 1510–1521. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c04158>
- Pezeshki-Raad, G., & Karamidehkordi, E. (2006). Linking agricultural research with extension: Iranian agricultural researchers' attitude toward collaboration with extension workers. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 8, 35–46. <https://jast.modares.ac.ir/article-23-923-en.pdf>
- Pietsch, N., Ribeiro, J. L. D., & de Medeiros, J. F. (2017). Benefits, challenges and critical factors of success for Zero Waste: A systematic literature review. *Waste Management*, 67, 324–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.05.004>
- Piketty, T. (2014). *Capital in the Twenty First Century*. The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Pittman, J. (2019). The struggle for local autonomy in biodiversity conservation governance. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 62(1), 172–188. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2018.1511416>
- Pixley, K. V., Falck-Zepeda, J. B., Paarlberg, R. L., Phillips, P. W. B., Slamet-Loedin, I. H., Dhugga, K. S., Campos, H., & Gutterson, N. (2022). Genome-edited crops for improved food security of smallholder farmers. *Nature Genetics*, 54(4), 364–367. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-022-01046-7>
- Plumwood, V. (1993). *Feminism and the mastery of nature*. Routledge. <https://www.routledge.com/Feminism-and-the-Mastery-of-Nature/Plumwood/p/book/9780415068109>
- Pocas Ribeiro, A. S. (2023). *Consumption: the elephant in the room: Understanding, changing, and reducing consumption for sustainability* [Utrecht University]. <https://doi.org/10.33540/1659>
- Pörtner, H.-O., Scholes, R. J., Agard, J., Archer, E., Bai, X., Barnes, D., Burrows, M., Chan, L., Cheung, W. L., Diamond, S., Donatti, C., Duarte, C., Eisenhauer, N., Foden, W., Gasalla, M. A., Handa, C., Hickler, T., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., Ichii, K., ... Ngo, H. (2021). *IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop report on biodiversity and climate change*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4782538>
- Porto, R. G., de Almeida, R. F., Cruz-Neto, O., Tabarelli, M., Viana, B. F., Peres, C. A., & Lopes, A. V. (2020). Pollination ecosystem services: A comprehensive review of economic values, research funding and policy actions. *Food Security*, 12(6), 1425–1442. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-020-01043-w>
- Prévost, B., & Rivaud, A. (2019). From conservation to offsetting and neoliberalization: Institutional change, risks and opportunities in the French context. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*, 2(2), 323–347. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2514848619836039>
- Prip, C., Rosendal, G. K., & Tvedt, M. W. (2015). *The state of technology transfer obligations in global environmental*. <https://www.sprep.org/attachments/VirLib/Global/state-technology-transfer.pdf>
- Qiu, S., Yue, W., Zhang, H., & Qi, J. (2017). Island ecosystem services value, land-use change, and the National New Area Policy in Zhoushan Archipelago, China. *Island Studies Journal*, 12(2), 177–197. <https://doi.org/10.24043/isj.20>
- Quijano, A. (2007). Coloniality and Modernity/Rationality. *Cultural Studies*, 21(2–3), 168–178. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09502380601164353>
- Quijano, A., & Ennis, M. (2000). Coloniality of Power, Eurocentrism, and Latin America. *Nepantla: Views from South*, 1(3), 533–580. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268580900015002005>
- Ragasa, C. (2011). *Are research-extension-farmer-linkage committees effective and inclusive? Perspective of agricultural researchers and extension agents in Nigeria and Ghana*. International Conference on Innovations in Extension and Advisory Services Proceedings, 15-17 November 2011. https://extension.cta.int/pages/Documents/Learning%20Networks/3.Institutional%20Arrangements/CTA129%20Institutional%20Arrangements_Ragasa_04.pdf
- Rahbar, E., & Abdul Wahid, N. (2011). Investigation of green marketing tools' effect on consumers' purchase behavior. *Business Strategy Series*, 12(2), 73–83. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17515631111114877>
- Rahut, Dil, Azhgaliyeva, D., & Yao, Y. (2022). *Biodiversity protection through reward mechanisms and governance*. https://think7.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Climate_Biodiversity-Protection-through-Reward-Technology-Transfer-and-improving-Governance_Dil-Rahut_Dina-Azhgaliyeva_Yixin-Yao.pdf
- Rammelt, C. F., Gupta, J., Liverman, D., Scholtens, J., Ciobanu, D., Abrams, J. F., Bai, X., Gifford, L., Gordon, C., Hurlbert, M., Inoue, C. Y. A., Jacobson, L., Lade, S. J., Lenton, T. M., McKay, D. I. A., Nakicenovic, N., Okereke, C., Otto, I. M., Pereira, L. M., ... Zimm, C. (2022). Impacts of meeting minimum access on critical earth systems amidst the Great Inequality. *Nature Sustainability*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-00995-5>

- Rani, L., Thapa, K., Kanojia, N., Sharma, N., Singh, S., Grewal, A. S., Srivastav, A. L., & Kaushal, J. (2021). An extensive review on the consequences of chemical pesticides on human health and environment. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124657>
- Rathore, S., Intodia, S. L., & Singh, R. P. (2008). *Analysis of Research – Extension – Farmer Linkage in the Arid Zone of India*.
- Raymond, C. M., Brown, G., & Weber, D. (2010). The measurement of place attachment: Personal, community, and environmental connections. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 30(4), 422–434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2010.08.002>
- Rayner, S. (2014). Uncomfortable knowledge: The social construction of ignorance in science and environmental policy discourses. In *An introduction to the sociology of ignorance* (pp. 107–125). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315771106>
- Redvers, N., Faerron Guzmán, C. A., & Parkes, M. W. (2023). Towards an educational praxis for planetary health: A call for transformative, inclusive, and integrative approaches for learning and relearning in the Anthropocene. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 7(1). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00332-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00332-1)
- Requena-i-Mora, M., & Brockington, D. (2021). Seeing environmental injustices: The mechanics, devices and assumptions of environmental sustainability indices and indicators. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 28(1). <https://doi.org/10.2458/jpe.4765>
- Reuters. (2022, September 27). Nearly half of asset managers don't base any sell orders on ESG, survey shows. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/sustainable-business/nearly-half-asset-managers-dont-base-any-sell-orders-esg-survey-2022-09-27/>
- Ribeiro, A. S. P. (2023). *Consumption: The elephant in the room* [Utrecht University]. <https://dSPACE.library.uu.nl/bitstream/handle/1874/427027/164709apoc/asribeiroemail%20-%2063f5299a95f48.pdf>
- Ripple, W. J., Wolf, C., Newsome, T. M., Barnard, P., & Moomaw, W. R. (2019). World Scientists' Warning of a Climate Emergency. *Bioscience*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biz088>
- Ripple, W. J., Wolf, C., Newsome, T. M., Galetti, M., Alamgir, M., Crist, E., Mahmoud, M. I., Laurance, W. F., & 15,364 scientist signatories from 184 countries. (2017). World Scientists' Warning to Humanity: A Second Notice. *BioScience*, 67(12), 1026–1028. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/bix125>
- Ritchie, H., & Roser, M. (2024, February 16). *Land Use*. Our World in Data. <https://ourworldindata.org/land-use>
- Rivera, J. L., & Lallmahomed, A. (2016). Environmental implications of planned obsolescence and product lifetime: A literature review. *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering*, 9(2), 119–129. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19397038.2015.1099757>
- Robbins, P. (2000). The Practical Politics of Knowing: State Environmental Knowledge and Local Political Economy. *Economic Geography*, 76(2), 126–144. <https://doi.org/10.2307/144550>
- Robertson, M. M. (2000). No Net Loss: Wetland Restoration and the Incomplete Capitalization of Nature. *Antipode*, 32(4), 463–493. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8330.00146>
- Robertson, M. M. (2004). The neoliberalization of ecosystem services: Wetland mitigation banking and problems in environmental governance. *Geoforum*, 35(3), 361–373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2003.06.002>
- Rocheleau, D., & Edmunds, D. (1997). Women, men and trees: Gender, power and property in forest and agrarian landscapes. *World Development*, 25(8), 1351–1371. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(97\)00036-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(97)00036-3)
- Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin, F. S., Lambin, E. F., Lenton, T. M., Scheffer, M., Folke, C., Schellnhuber, H. J., Nykvist, B., De Wit, C. A., Hughes, T., Van Der Leeuw, S., Rodhe, H., Sörlin, S., Snyder, P. K., Costanza, R., Svedin, U., ... Foley, J. A. (2009). A safe operating space for humanity. *Nature*, 461(September), 472–475. <https://doi.org/10.1038/461472a>
- Romero-Toledo, H. (2023). Producing Territories for Extractivism: Encomiendas, Estancias and Forts in the Long-Term Political Ecology of Colonial Southern Chile. *Land*, 12(4), 857. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12040857>
- Rose, D. C., Mukherjee, N., Simmons, B. I., Tew, E. R., Robertson, R. J., Vadrot, A. B. M., Doubleday, R., & Sutherland, W. J. (2020). Policy windows for the environment: Tips for improving the uptake of scientific knowledge. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 113, 47–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2017.07.013>
- Rossiter, D. A. (2007). Lessons in possession: Colonial resource geographies in practice on Vancouver Island, 1859–1865. *Journal of Historical Geography*, 33(4), 770–790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhg.2006.12.001>
- Roy, M.-E., Surget-Groba, Y., & Rivest, D. (2021). Legacies of forest harvesting on plant diversity and plant community composition in temperate deciduous forest. *APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE*, 24(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12620>
- Rubino, M. C. (2000). Biodiversity Finance. *International Affairs*, 76(2), 223–240. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2346.00131>
- Rudel, T. K. (2013). The national determinants of deforestation in sub-Saharan Africa. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 368(1625). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2012.0405>
- Sachs, J. D., Schmidt-Traub, G., Mazzucato, M., Messner, D., Nakicenovic, N., & Rockström, J. (2019). Six Transformations to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals. *Nature Sustainability*, 2(9), 805–814. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0352-9>
- Samanta, N. (2019). Convergence to shareholder primacy corporate governance: Evidence from a leximetric analysis of the evolution of corporate governance regulations in 21 countries, 1995–2014. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 19(5), 849–883. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-07-2018-0249>
- Samari, M., Ghodrati, N., Esmaeilifar, R., Olfat, P., & Mohd Shafiei, M. W. (2013). The Investigation of the Barriers in Developing Green Building in Malaysia. *Modern Applied Science*, 7(2), p1. <https://doi.org/10.5539/mas.v7n2p1>
- Santika, T., Nelson, V., Flint, M., MacEwen, M., Cerretelli, S., & Brack, D. (2024). Leverage points for tackling unsustainable global value chains: Market-based measures versus transformative alternatives. *Sustainability Science*, 19(1), 285–305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01430-0>
- Santos, A. N., de Souza, G. M., Abdalla, M. M., Ferreira, A., & Nogueira, N. J. (2024). Lobbying and environmental crimes: An

- analysis based on the Brazilian mining sector. *The Extractive Industries and Society*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exis.2024.101419>
- Sarkar (Paria), D., & Maji, N. (2022). Status and Threats of Wetland Change in Land Use Pattern and Planning: Impact of Land Use Patterns and Urbanization. In *Handbook of Research on Monitoring and Evaluating the Ecological Health of Wetlands* (pp. 106–127). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-9498-8.ch007>
- Satyro, W. C., Sacomano, J. B., Contador, J. C., & Telles, R. (2018). Planned obsolescence or planned resource depletion? A sustainable approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 195, 744–752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.222>
- Schipper, E. L. F., Revi, A., Preston, B. L., Carr, E. R., Eriksen, S. H., Fernández-Carril, L. R., Glavovic, B., Hilmi, N. J. M., Ley, D., Mukerji, R., Araujo, M. S. M. de, Perez, R., Rose, S. K., & Singh, P. K. (2022). Climate resilient development pathways. In H.-O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, M. M. B. Tignor, E. S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Löschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, & B. Rama (Eds.), *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (pp. 2655–2807). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844.027>
- Schleicher, J., Peres, C. A., Amano, T., Lactayo, W., & Leader-Williams, N. (2017). Conservation performance of different conservation governance regimes in the Peruvian Amazon. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-10736-w>
- Schlogl, L., & Sumner, A. (2018). The Rise of the Robot Reserve Army: Automation and the Future of Economic Development, Work, and Wages in Developing Countries. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3208816>
- Schneider, M., & McMichael, P. (2010). Deepening, and repairing, the metabolic rift. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, 37(3), 461–484. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150.2010.494371>
- Schroeder, B., Rudner, M., Biedermann, R., Koegl, H., & Kleyer, M. (2008). A landscape model for quantifying the trade-off between conservation needs and economic constraints in the management of a semi-natural grassland community. *Biological Conservation*, 141(3), 719–732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.12.017>
- Schröter, M., Kraemer, R., Remme, R. P., & van Oudenhoven, A. P. E. (2020). Distant regions underpin interregional flows of cultural ecosystem services provided by birds and mammals. *Ambio*, 49(5), 1100–1113. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-019-01261-3>
- Schulte, P. A., Streit, J. M. K., Sheriff, F., Delclos, G., Felkner, S. A., Tamers, S. L., Fendinger, S., Grosch, J., & Sala, R. (2020). Potential Scenarios and Hazards in the Work of the Future: A Systematic Review of the Peer-Reviewed and Gray Literatures. *Annals of Work Exposures and Health*, 64(8), 786–816. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annweh/wxaa051>
- Schütte, G., Eckerstorfer, M., Rastelli, V., Reichenbecher, W., Restrepo-Vassalli, S., Ruohonen-Lehto, M., Saucy, A.-G. W., & Mertens, M. (2017). Herbicide resistance and biodiversity: Agronomic and environmental aspects of genetically modified herbicide-resistant plants. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 29(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-016-0100-y>
- Schwarzmueller, F., & Kastner, T. (2022). Agricultural trade and its impacts on cropland use and the global loss of species habitat. *Sustainability Science*, 17(6), 2363–2377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01138-7>
- Scoones, I., Leach, M., & Newell, P. (Eds.). (2015). *The politics of green transformations*. Routledge. https://www.routledge.com/The-Politics-of-Green-Transformations/Scoones-Leach-Newell/p/book/9781138792906?srsltid=AfmBOoQnMeza-kf-IsBaCL_rdl9Dr_mLbvTG9_GhsEkD1Wj0VbRwidY0
- Scott, J. C. (1998). *Seeing like a state: How certain schemes to improve the human condition have failed*. Yale University Press.
- SEI/JNCC. (2023). *Commodity Footprints Dashboard* (www.commodityfootprints.earth) (Croft, S., West, C., Harris, M., Egan, C., Green, J., Molotoks, A., Wood, E., & Way, L., Eds.). <https://commodityfootprints.earth/>
- Seto, K. C., Reenberg, A., Boone, C. G., Fragkias, M., Haase, D., Langanke, T., Marcotullio, P., Munroe, D. K., Olah, B., & Simon, D. (2012). Urban land teleconnections and sustainability. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(20), Article 20. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1117622109>
- Sette, C. M., & Wheeler, S. A. (2017). A century of intervention in a Ramsar wetland – the case of the Coorong, Lower Lakes and Murray Mouth. *Australasian Journal of Environmental Management*, 24(2), 163–183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14486563.2017.1300952>
- Shandra, J. M., McKinney, L. A., Leckband, C., & London, B. (2010). Debt, Structural Adjustment, and Biodiversity Loss: A Cross-National Analysis of Threatened Mammals and Birds. *Human Ecology Review*, 17(1), 18–33. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24707512>
- Shanley, P., & López, C. (2009). Out of the Loop: Why Research Rarely Reaches Policy Makers and the Public and What Can be Done. *Biotropica*, 41(5), 535–544. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7429.2009.00561.x>
- Sharma, M. (2017). *Radical Transformational Leadership: Strategic Action for Change Agents* (Illustrated edition). North Atlantic Books.
- Shin, Y.-J., Midgley, G. F., Archer, E. R. M., Arneth, A., Barnes, D. K. A., Chan, L., Hashimoto, S., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., Insarov, G., Leadley, P., Levin, L. A., Ngo, H. T., Pandit, R., Pires, A. P. F., Pörtner, H.-O., Rogers, A. D., Scholes, R. J., Settele, J., & Smith, P. (2022). Actions to halt biodiversity loss generally benefit the climate. *Global Change Biology*, 28(9), 2846–2874. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16109>
- Shiva, V. (1988). *Staying Alive: Women, Ecology and Development*. Zed Books.
- Shove, E., Watson, M., & Spurling, N. (2015). Conceptualizing connections: Energy demand, infrastructures and social practices. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 18(3), 274–287. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368431015579964>
- Shtaltovna, A. (2016). Knowledge Gaps and Rural Development in Tajikistan: Agricultural Advisory Services as a Panacea? *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 22(1), 25–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2014.997257>
- Shwartz, A., Muratet, A., Simon, L., & Julliard, R. (2013). Local and management variables outweigh landscape effects in enhancing the diversity of different taxa in a big metropolis. *Biological Conservation*, 157, 285–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.09.009>
- Sieber, I. M., Biesbroek, R., & de Block, D. (2018). Mechanism-based explanations of impasses in the governance of ecosystem-based adaptation. *Regional Environmental Change*, 18(8), 2379–2390. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-018-1347-1>

- Siekmann, F., Schlör, H., & Venghaus, S. (2023). Linking sustainability and the Fourth Industrial Revolution: A monitoring framework accounting for technological development. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 13(1), 26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-023-00405-4>
- Sikor, T., Auld, G., Bebbington, A. J., Benjaminsen, T. A., Gentry, B. S., Hunsberger, C., Izac, A.-M., Margulis, M. E., Plieninger, T., Schroeder, H., & Upton, C. (2013). Global land governance: From territory to flow? *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 5(5), 522–527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2013.06.006>
- Sikor, T., & Lund, C. (2009). Access and Property: A Question of Power and Authority. *Development and Change*, 40(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7660.2009.01503.x>
- Sikor, T., & Newell, P. (2014). Globalizing environmental justice? *Geoforum*, 54, 151–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2014.04.009>
- Simkin, R. D., Seto, K. C., McDonald, R. I., & Jetz, W. (2022). Biodiversity impacts and conservation implications of urban land expansion projected to 2050. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(12). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2117297119>
- Singh, P. K., & Maheswaran, R. (2023). Analysis of social barriers to sustainable innovation and digitisation in supply chain. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-023-02931-9>
- Slater, H., Fisher, J., Holmes, G., Sandbrook, C., & Keane, A. (2024). Assessing the breadth and multidisciplinary of the conservation curriculum in the United Kingdom and Australia. *BioScience*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae059>
- Smith, N., & O’Keefe, P. (1980). Geography, Marx and the Concept of Nature. *Antipode*, 12(2), 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8330.1980.tb00647.x>
- Sneddon, C., & Fox, C. (2006). Rethinking transboundary waters: A critical hydropolitics of the Mekong basin. *Political Geography*, 25(2), 181–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polgeo.2005.11.002>
- Song, X.-P., Hansen, M. C., Potapov, P., Adusei, B., Pickering, J., Adami, M., Lima, A., Zalles, V., Stehman, S. V., Di Bella, C. M., Conde, M. C., Copati, E. J., Fernandes, L. B., Hernandez-Serna, A., Jantz, S. M., Pickens, A. H., Turubanova, S., & Tyukavina, A. (2021). Massive soybean expansion in South America since 2000 and implications for conservation. *Nature Sustainability*, 4(9), 784–792. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-021-00729-z>
- Sonter, L. J., Dade, M. C., Watson, J. E. M., & Valenta, R. K. (2020). Renewable energy production will exacerbate mining threats to biodiversity. *Nature Communications*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-17928-5>
- Spash, C. L., & Aslaksen, I. (2015). Re-establishing an ecological discourse in the policy debate over how to value ecosystems and biodiversity. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 159, 245–253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2015.04.049>
- Spierenburg, M. (2012). Getting the Message Across Biodiversity Science and Policy Interfaces – A Review. *GAIA – Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 21(2), 125–134. <https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.21.2.11>
- Stanley, D. (2022). *Global Inequalities*. International Monetary Fund. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/fandd/issues/2022/03/Global-inequalities-Stanley>
- Steffen, W., Crutzen, P. J., & McNeill, J. R. (2007). The Anthropocene: Are Humans Now Overwhelming the Great Forces of Nature. *AMBIO: A Journal of the Human Environment*, 36(8), 614–621. [https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447\(2007\)36\[614:TAAH\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447(2007)36[614:TAAH]2.0.CO;2)
- Steffen, W., Rockström, J., Richardson, K., Lenton, T. M., Folke, C., Liverman, D., Summerhayes, C. P., Barnosky, A. D., Cornell, S. E., Crucifix, M., Donges, J. F., Fetzer, I., Lade, S. J., Scheffer, M., Winkelmann, R., & Schellnhuber, H. J. (2018). Trajectories of the Earth System in the Anthropocene. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(33), 8252–8259. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1810141115>
- Steinberg, P. F. (2009). Institutional Resilience Amid Political Change: The Case of Biodiversity Conservation. *Global Environmental Politics*, 9(3), 61–81. <https://doi.org/10.1162/glep.2009.9.3.61>
- Stirling, A. (2019). Engineering and Sustainability: Control and Care in Unfoldings of Modernity. *SPRU Working Paper Series*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3336826>
- Stirling, A. (2023). Against misleading technocratic precision in research evaluation and wider policy – A response to Franzoni and Stephan (2023), ‘uncertainty and risk-taking in science.’ *Research Policy*, 52(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2022.104709>
- Stubbs, T., Kentikelenis, A., Gabor, D., Ghosh, J., & McKee, M. (2023). The return of austerity imperils global health. *BMJ Global Health*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2022-011620>
- Sucre Romero, L. (2022). *Forest Equity: What Indigenous People Want from Carbon Credits*. Yale E360. <https://e360.yale.edu/features/levi-sucre-romero-indigenous-lands-carbon-credits>
- Sun, W., Xu, N., Wang, L., Zhang, H., & Zhang, Y. (2022). Dynamic digital twin and federated learning with incentives for air-ground networks. *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering*, 9(1), 321–333. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNSE.2020.3048137>
- Sundström, A. (2015). Covenants with broken swords: Corruption and law enforcement in governance of the commons. *Global Environmental Change*, 31, 253–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.02.002>
- Suttor-Sorel, L., & Hercelin, N. (2020). *Nature’s Return—Embedding environmental goals at the heart of economic and financial decision-making* | Green Finance Platform. Finance Watch. <https://www.greenfinanceplatform.org/research/natures-return-embedding-environmental-goals-heart-economic-and-financial-decision-making>
- Svampa, M., & Viale, E. (2014). *Maldesarrollo: La Argentina del extractivismo y el despojo* (1. ed). Katz Editores.
- Svartzman, R., & Althouse, J. (2022). Greening the international monetary system? Not without addressing the political ecology of global imbalances. *Review of International Political Economy*, 29(3), 844–869. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290.2020.1854326>
- Svartzman, R., Espagne, E., Julien, G., Paul, H.-L., Mathilde, S., Allen, T., Berger, J., Calas, J., Godin, A., & Vallier, A. (2021). *A “Silent Spring” for the Financial System? Exploring Biodiversity-Related Financial Risks in France*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4028442>
- Tasmim, S., Sommer, J. M., & Shandra, J. M. (2022). Feed me! China, agriculture, ecologically unequal exchange, and forest loss in a cross-national perspective. *Environmental Policy and Governance*,

- 32(1), 29–42. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1959>
- Terton *et al.* (2022). *Synergies Between Biodiversity and Climate Policy Frameworks – A Series of Thematic Papers*. International Institute for Sustainable Development. <https://www.iisd.org/publications/report/synergies-biodiversity-climate-policy-frameworks>
- Tienhaara, K. (2018). Regulatory Chill in a Warming World: The Threat to Climate Policy Posed by Investor-State Dispute Settlement. *Transnational Environmental Law*, 7(2), 229–250. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S2047102517000309>
- Tienhaara, K., Thrasher, R., Simmons, B. A., & Gallagher, K. P. (2022). Investor-state disputes threaten the global green energy transition. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 376(6594), 701–703. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abo4637>
- Tiffany, B., Chaudhry, T., Hofstetter, R. W., & Aslan, C. (2022). The Impact of Administrative Partitioning on the Regional Effectiveness of Forest Pest Management in Protected Area-Centered Ecosystems. *Forests*, 13(3), 395. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f13030395>
- Többen, J., Wiebe, K. S., Veronesi, F., Wood, R., & Moran, D. D. (2018). A novel maximum entropy approach to hybrid monetary-physical supply-chain modelling and its application to biodiversity impacts of palm oil embodied in consumption. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(11). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aae491>
- Tokunaga, K., Sugino, H., Nomura, H., & Michida, Y. (2020). Norms and the willingness to pay for coastal ecosystem restoration: A case of the Tokyo Bay intertidal flats. *Ecological Economics*, 169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106423>
- Toly, N. J. (2004). Globalization and the Capitalization of Nature: A Political Ecology of Biodiversity in Mesoamerica. *Bulletin of Science, Technology & Society*, 24(1), 47–54. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0270467604263176>
- Tong, R., & Botts, T. F. (2024). *Feminist Thought: A More Comprehensive Introduction* (6th ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003016939>
- Torres de Oliveira, R., Gentile-Lüdecke, S., & Figueira, S. (2022). Barriers to innovation and innovation performance: The mediating role of external knowledge search in emerging economies. *Small Business Economics*, 58(4), 1953–1974. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-021-00491-8>
- Tørsløv, T., Wier, L., & Zucman, G. (2023). The Missing Profits of Nations. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 90(3), 1499–1534. <https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdac049>
- Toth, G., & Sziget, C. (2016). The historical ecological footprint: From over-population to over-consumption. *Ecological Indicators*, 60, 283–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.06.040>
- Treml, E. A., Fidelman, P. I. J., Kininmonth, S., Ekstrom, J. A., & Bodin, Ö. (2015). Analyzing the (mis)fit between the institutional and ecological networks of the Indo-West Pacific. *Global Environmental Change*, 31, 263–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.01.012>
- Trisos, C. H., Auerbach, J., & Katti, M. (2021). Decoloniality and anti-oppressive practices for a more ethical ecology. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 5(9), 1205–1212. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-021-01460-w>
- Tucker, P. (2018). *Unelected power: The quest for legitimacy in central banking and the regulatory state*. Princeton University Press.
- Turnhout, E., Dewulf, A., & Hulme, M. (2016). What does policy-relevant global environmental knowledge do? The cases of climate and biodiversity. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 18, 65–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.09.004>
- Turnhout, E., McElwee, P., Chiroleu-Assouline, M., Clapp, J., Isenhour, C., Kelemen, E., Jackson, T., Miller, D. C., Rusch, G. M., Spangenberg, J. H., & Waldron, A. (2021). Enabling transformative economic change in the post-2020 biodiversity agenda. *Conservation Letters*, 14(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12805>
- Ulloa, A. (2017). The Geopolitics of Carbonized Nature and the Zero Carbon Citizen. *South Atlantic Quarterly*, 116(1), 111–120. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00382876-3749359>
- UN. (1972). *Report of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment*. <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n17/300/05/pdf/n1730005.pdf>
- UNEP. (2021, May 20). *Building Biodiversity—The Natural Resource Management Approach*. UNEP – UN Environment Programme. <http://www.unep.org/resources/report/building-biodiversity-natural-resource-management-approach>
- UNEP. (2023). *Inclusive Wealth Report 2023: Measuring Sustainability and Equity*. United Nations Environment Programme. <https://doi.org/10.59117/20.500.11822%2F43131>
- United Nations. (2014). *World Urbanization Prospects: The 2014 Revision*. New York: United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs/Population Division. <http://esa.un.org/unpd/wup/>
- United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2018). *World Urbanization Prospects—Population Division—United Nations*. <https://population.un.org/wup/>
- United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2022). *World Population Prospects 2022: Summary of Results*. https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/sites/www.un.org.development.desa/pd/files/wpp2022_summary_of_results.pdf
- United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2023). *The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2023: Special Edition*. United Nations. <https://doi.org/10.18356/9789210024914>
- United Nations Environment Programme. (2023, July 12). *State of Finance for Nature 2023*. UNEP – UN Environment Programme. <http://www.unep.org/resources/state-finance-nature-2023>
- United Nations Women. (2024, May 31). *Facts and figures: Women's leadership and political participation*. UN Women – Headquarters. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/leadership-and-political-participation/facts-and-figures>
- Vallet, G. (2021). Great Power, Great Responsibility: Addressing the Underestimated Issue of Central Bank's Social Responsibility 1. *Journal of Central Banking Theory and Practice*, 10(3), 23–39. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jcbtp-2021-0022%0A>
- Vandermeer, J., & Perfecto, I. (2013). Complex traditions: Intersecting theoretical frameworks in agroecological research. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems*, 37(1), 76–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10440046.2012.717904>
- Venditti, B. (2022). *This chart shows the impact rising urbanization will have on the world*. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2022/04/global-urbanization-material-consumption/>

- Venkataramana, G. V., Sreenivasa, & Lingaraju, H. G. (2017). An assessment of crop damage and economic loss caused by elephants in Harohalli and Kodihalli ranges of Bannerghatta National Park, Karnataka, India. *Current Science*, 113(1), 161–167. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26163921>
- Venter, O., Sanderson, E. W., Magrath, A., Allan, J. R., Beher, J., Jones, K. R., Possingham, H. P., Laurance, W. F., Wood, P., Fekete, B. M., Levy, M. A., & Watson, J. E. M. (2016). Sixteen years of change in the global terrestrial human footprint and implications for biodiversity conservation. *NATURE COMMUNICATIONS*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms12558>
- Vernengo, M. (2006). Technology, Finance, and Dependency: Latin American Radical Political Economy in Retrospect. *Review of Radical Political Economics*, 38(4), 551–568. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0486613406293220>
- Virdin, J., Vegh, T., Jouffray, J.-B., Blasiak, R., Mason, S., Österblom, H., Vermeer, D., Wachtmeister, H., & Werner, N. (2021). The Ocean 100: Transnational corporations in the ocean economy. *Science Advances*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abc8041>
- von Briel, F., & Recker, J. (2017). Lessons from a failed implementation of an online open innovation community in an innovative organization. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 16(1), 35–46. <http://misqe.org/ojs2/index.php/misqe/article/viewFile/656/456>
- Wallington, T. J., Hobbs, R. J., & Moore, S. A. (2005). Implications of Current Ecological Thinking for Biodiversity Conservation: A Review of the Salient Issues. *Ecology and Society*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-01256-100115>
- Wamsler, C., Mundaca, L., & Osberg, G. (2022). Rethinking political agency: The role of individuals' engagement, perceptions and trust in transitioning to a low-carbon transport system. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132197>
- Wamsler, C., Osberg, G., Janss, J., & Stephan, L. (2023). Revolutionising sustainability leadership and education: Addressing the human dimension to support flourishing, culture and system transformation. *Climatic Change*, 177(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-023-03636-8>
- Wamsler, C., Osberg, G., Panagiotou, A., Smith, B., Stanbridge, P., Osika, W., & Mundaca, L. (2022). Meaning-making in a context of climate change: Supporting agency and political engagement. *Climate Policy*, 23, 829–844. <https://doi.org/10.1080/014693062.2022.2121254>
- Wamsler, C., & Riggers, S. (2018). Principles for supporting city–citizen commoning for climate adaptation: From adaptation governance to sustainable transformation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 85, 81–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.03.021>
- Ward, B. (2013). The Promise of Jobs: Blackmail and Environmental Justice in Flint, Michigan, 1991–1995. *Environmental Justice*, 6(5), 163–168. <https://doi.org/10.1089/env.2013.0030>
- Weber, K., & Rohrer, H. (2012). Legitimizing research, technology and innovation policies for transformative change: Combining insights from innovation systems and multi-level perspective in a comprehensive 'failures' framework. *Research Policy*, 41(6), 1037–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2011.10.015>
- Weldemichel, T. G. (2020). Othring Pastoralists, State Violence, and the Remaking of Boundaries in Tanzania's Militarised Wildlife Conservation Sector. *Antipode*, 52(5), 1496–1518. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12638>
- Wells, M. P., & McShane, T. O. (2004). Integrating Protected Area Management with Local Needs and Aspirations. *AMBIO: A Journal of the Human Environment*, 33(8), 513–519. <https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447-33.8.513>
- Whatmore, S., & Thorne, L. (1998). Wild(er)ness: Reconfiguring the Geographies of Wildlife. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 23(4), 435–454. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0020-2754.1998.00435.x>
- Widmer, A., Herzog, L., Moser, A., & Ingold, K. (2019). Multilevel water quality management in the international Rhine catchment area: How to establish social-ecological fit through collaborative governance. *Ecology and Society*, 24(3). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26796989>
- Wiedmann, T., Lenzen, M., Keyßer, L. T., & Steinberger, J. K. (2020). Scientists' warning on affluence. *Nature Communications* 2020 11:1, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-16941-y>
- Wilhite, H. (2016). *The Political Economy of Low Carbon Transformation: Breaking the habits of capitalism*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315745787>
- Williams, G. (2017). Cost-effective landscape revegetation and restoration of a grazing property on the Northern Tablelands of New South Wales: 65 years of change and adaptation at 'Eastlake'. *Rangeland Journal*, 39(5–6, SI), 461–476. <https://doi.org/10.1071/RJ17110>
- Williams, J. (2013). Humans and biodiversity: Population and demographic trends in the hotspots. *Population and Environment*, 34, 510–523. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11111-012-0175-3>
- Winter, M. (1997). New Policies and New Skills: Agricultural Change and Technology Transfer. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 37(3), 363–381. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9523.1997.tb00056.x>
- Witter, R., & Satterfield, T. (2019). The Ebb and Flow of Indigenous Rights Recognitions in Conservation Policy. *Development and Change*, 50(4), 1083–1108. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12456>
- Wolf, M., Semm, A., & Erfurth, C. (2018). Digital Transformation in Companies – Challenges and Success Factors. In M. Hodoň, G. Eichler, C. Erfurth, & G. Fahrnberger (Eds.), *Innovations for Community Services* (pp. 178–193). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93408-2_13
- Woodruff, D. M. (2019). To Democratize Finance, Democratize Central Banking. *Politics & Society*, 47(4), 593–610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0032329219879275>
- World Economic Forum. (2021). *Global Gender Gap Report: Drop to the Top*. <https://www.weforum.org/videos/global-gender-gap-report-csuite/>
- Wouterse, F., Deininger, K., Selod, H., Badiane, O., Swinnen, J., von Braun, J., & Zilberman, D. (2011). *Foreign Direct Investment in Land in West Africa The Status Quo, Lessons from Other Regions, Implications for Research*. International Food Policy Research Institute. https://au.int/sites/default/files/documents/30933-doc-ifpri_wcao_trn1_land_fdi_0.pdf
- Wright, T., & Zucman, G. (2018). *The Exorbitant Tax Privilege*. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w24983>
- Wu, L., Subramanian, N., Abdulrahman, M. D., Liu, C., & Pawar, K. S. (2017). Short-term versus long-term benefits: Balanced sustainability framework and research propositions. *Sustainable Global*

- Operations Management and Frugal Innovative Sustainable Production Methods: Advancing Theory and Practice for a Truly Sustainable Society*, 11, 18–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2016.09.003>
- WWF. (2020). *Living Planet Report 2020-Bending the curve of biodiversity loss*. WWF Living Planet Report. https://www.lpr.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/lpr_2022_full_report.pdf
- Wynter, S. (2003). Unsettling the Coloniality of Being/Power/Truth/Freedom: Towards the Human, After Man, Its Overrepresentation—An Argument. *CR: The New Centennial Review*, 3(3), 257–337. <https://doi.org/10.1353/ncr.2004.0015>
- Ybarra, M. (2009). Violent visions of an ownership society: The land administration project in Petén, Guatemala. *Land Use Policy*, 26(1), 44–54. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264837708000033>
- Ybarra, M. (2012). Taming the jungle, saving the Maya Forest: Sedimented counterinsurgency practices in contemporary Guatemalan conservation. *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 39(2), 479–502. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150.2012.666974>
- Young, O. (2008). Institutions and Environmental Change: The Scientific Legacy of a Decade of IDGEC Research. In O. Young, L. A. King, & H. Schroeder (Eds.), *Institutions and Environmental Change: Principal Findings, Applications, and Research Frontiers* (pp. 3–46). The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9780262240574.003.0001>
- Yu, X., E, M., Sun, M., Xue, Z., Lu, X., Jiang, M., & Zou, Y. (2018). Wetland recreational agriculture: Balancing wetland conservation and agro-development. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 87, 11–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.05.015>
- Zallio, M., & Berry, D. (2017). Design and Planned Obsolescence. Theories and Approaches for Designing Enabling Technologies. *The Design Journal*, 20(sup1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/14606925.2017.1352879>
- Zhang, W. (2018). Global pesticide use: Profile, trend, cost / benefit and more. *Proceedings of the International Academy of Ecology and Environmental Sciences*, 8(1), 1–27. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/global-pesticide-use-profile-trend-cost-benefit/docview/2050588723/se-2>
- Zimmerer, K. S., Lambin, E. F., & Vanek, S. J. (2018). Smallholder telecoupling and potential sustainability. *Ecology and Society*, 23(1). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-09935-230130>
- Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Baker, J., Griffiths, R. A., Strange, N., Struebig, M. J., & Bull, J. W. (2019). The ecological outcomes of biodiversity offsets under “no net loss” policies: A global review. *Conservation Letters*, 12(6). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12664>
- Zuluaga, S., Speziale, K., & Lambertucci, S. A. (2021). Global Aerial Habitat Conservation Post-COVID-19 Anthroause. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 36(4), 273–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2021.01.009>

